

**Heat Transfer Fluids for the
Enhancement of
Heating Energy Applications**

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ABSTRACT

Driven by the growing cost of domestic heating and the rising fuel price, this work looks at surfactant solution-based energy-efficient heat transfer fluids using nanofluids. Particularly silicone-based surfactant (low molecular weight ethoxylated polydimethylsiloxane) that have shown encouraging effects in lowering energy consumption for domestic heating. This work complements the aim of the UK to have zero emissions from residential buildings by 2050, a sector that today makes 17% of all national greenhouse gas emissions.

The goal of this work was to create several new Nano fluids for enhancing built environments' energy efficiency. The work was successful with taking research from lab formulation, through modelling and finally the formulated product for real build environment of two council building heat systems.

Under turbulent flow conditions in small-diameter pipes, the thermophysical performance of several nanofluid formulations including nanoparticles such silica, alumina, and graphene oxide suspended in base fluids such as water and ethylene glycol was investigated in this work. Heat transfer properties were assessed using computational fluid dynamics (CFD) simulations, with a focus towards Nusselt number.

Raman spectroscopy, dynamic light scattering (DLS), scanning transmission electron microscopy (STEM), and X-ray diffraction (XRD) were used in comprehensive characterisation of the nanofluids and their component nanoparticles. These studies gave understanding of structural integrity, particle dispersion, and morphology. Further in-lab development of thermal conductivity instrument provided an iteration toward effective formulation component for heat transfer application.

In summary from our result the most effective formulation component was alumina nanofluid and silicone as surfactant. An important result of this work was the creation of a silicone-based

heat transfer fluid, tested in situ in association with Bradford and Durham councils. As Chapter 7 goes into depth resulting with up to >20% of energy saving, so a possible major impact.

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Abbreviations

AC: Alternating Current

ADC: Analogue-to-Digital Converter

APG: Alkyl Polyglycoside

BHTC: Boiling Heat Transfer Coefficient

BMS: Building Management System

CHF: Critical Heat Flux

CFD: Computational Fluid Dynamics

CMC: Critical Micelle Concentration

CQDs: Carbon Quantum Dots

CTAB: Cetyltrimethylammonium Bromide

DC: Direct Current

DHW: Domestic Hot Water

DLS: Dynamic Light Scattering

DLVO: Derjaguin-Landau-Verwey-Overbeek Theory

DSO: Digital Storage Oscilloscope

EDX: Energy-Dispersive X-ray Spectroscopy

EG: Ethylene Glycol

ETP: Energy Technology Partnership

GO: Graphene Oxide

GPIO: General-Purpose Input/Output

GUI: Graphical User Interface

HDD: Heating Degree Day

HTC: Heat Transfer Coefficient

I²C: I²C Interface (also I2C)

LMTD: Log Mean Temperature Difference

MWCNT: Multi-Walled Carbon Nanotubes

Nu: Nusselt Number

PCB: Printed Circuit Boards

PDMS: Polydimethylsiloxane

PEO: Polyether

PGA: Programmable Gain Amplifier

PPO: Polypropylene Oxide

PTFE: Polytetrafluoroethylene (Teflon)

PVP: Polyvinylpyrrolidone

Pr: Prandtl Number

Re: Reynolds Number

RHTC: Relative Heat Transfer Coefficient

ROI: Return on Investment

RS Box: Room Simulation Box

RTD: Resistance Temperature Detection

SDBS: Sodium Dodecylbenzenesulfonate

SDGs: Sustainable Development Goals

SDS: Sodium Dodecyl Sulfate (also SLS)

SMD: Surface Mount Device

SiNPs: Silica Nanoparticles

SPI: Serial Peripheral Interface

STEM: Scanning Transmission Electron Microscopy

TBAB: Tetrabutylammonium Bromide

XRD: X-ray Diffraction

Symbols

V : Sedimentation velocity of a nanoparticle (Stokes' Equation). Velocity vector in CFD equations (continuity, momentum, energy).

R : Sphere radius (Stokes' Equation). Actual wire resistance

μ : Dynamic viscosity of the fluid (Stokes' Equation, Prandtl number).

ρ_p : Density of the nanoparticle sphere (Stokes' Equation).

ρ_1 : Fluid density (Stokes' Equation).

g : Gravitational acceleration (Stokes' Equation).

ρ_{nf} : Density of the nanofluid (CFD equations).

μ_{nf} : Effective viscosity of the nanofluid (Einstein-Batchelor model).

μ_f : Viscosity of the base fluid (Einstein-Batchelor model).

f : Friction factor (flow resistance in pipes).

Re : Reynolds number

u : Fluid velocity (Reynolds number).

L : Characteristic length (Reynolds number) or pipe length (pressure loss).

ν : Kinematic viscosity (Reynolds and Prandtl numbers).

P : Pressure (momentum equation).

τ : Stress tensor (momentum equation).

D : Pipe diameter (pressure loss equation).

V_{avg} : Average velocity (pressure loss equation).

C_p : Specific heat (Prandtl number, thermal diffusivity).

C_{pnf} : Specific heat capacity of the nanofluid (energy equation, CFD).

$(C_p)_{nf}$: Specific heat capacity of the nanofluid (alternative notation).

$(\rho C_p)_{bf}$: Volumetric heat capacity of the base fluid.

$(\rho C_p)_s$: Volumetric heat capacity of solid nanoparticles.

k : Thermal conductivity

k_{nf} : Effective thermal conductivity of the nanofluid (Maxwell model).

k_s : Thermal conductivity of solid nanoparticles (Maxwell model).

k_f : Thermal conductivity of the base fluid (Maxwell model, transient hot wire method).

α : Thermal diffusivity

Nu : Nusselt number

h : Convective heat transfer coefficient

L_c : Characteristic length (Nusselt number).

Pr : Prandtl number

T : Temperature

ΔT_{lmtd} : Log Mean Temperature Difference (**LMTD**).

T_{in} : Inlet temperature (LMTD calculation).

T_{wall} : Wall temperature (LMTD calculation).

T_{out} : Outlet temperature (LMTD calculation).

q : Heat flux during boiling. Heat energy supplied per unit length per unit time (transient hot wire method). Electrical power dissipated from the wire (hot wire method).

HTC : Heat Transfer Coefficient

$RHTC$: Relative Heat Transfer Coefficient

ΔT : Temperature increment (transient hot wire method). Wall superheat.

ΔT_{water} : Temperature difference for water.

$\Delta T_{surfactant}$: Temperature difference for surfactant solution.

V_{total} : Total electrostatic interaction potential (DLVO theory).

$V_{van\ der\ Waal}$: Van der Waals interaction potential (DLVO theory).

$V_{electrostatic}$: Electrostatic interaction potential (DLVO theory).

ϕ (or ϕ): Volume fraction of nanoparticles

V_{np} : Volume of nanoparticles.

V_{bf} : Volume of the base fluid.

W_{np} : Weight of nanoparticles.

ρ_{np} : Density of nanoparticles.

W_{bf} : Weight of the base fluid.

ρ_{bf} : Density of the base fluid.

ρ_s : Density of solid nanoparticles.

ρ_{bf} : Density of the base fluid (e.g., water or oil).

D_h : Hydrodynamic radius (Stokes-Einstein equation: $D_h = K_b T / (6\pi\eta_0 D_t)$).

K_b : Boltzmann constant.

η_0 : Solvent viscosity (Stokes-Einstein equation).

D_t : Translational diffusion coefficient (Stokes-Einstein equation).

η : Dynamic viscosity (Ostwald Viscometer), Dynamic viscosity of the test liquid (Ostwald Viscometer calculation).

K : Constant determined by viscometer dimensions (Ostwald Viscometer).

ρ : Fluid density (Ostwald Viscometer), Specific resistance

t : Efflux time (Ostwald Viscometer), Time (transient hot wire method).

ρ_{sample} : Density of the sample (pycnometer calculation).

$m_{pyc+sample}$: Mass of pycnometer filled with the sample.

m_{pyc} : Mass of empty pycnometer.

$m_{pyc+water}$: Mass of pycnometer filled with water.

ρ_{water} : Density of water at measurement temperature (pycnometer).

η_{test} : Dynamic viscosity of the test liquid (Ostwald Viscometer).

η_{std} : Dynamic viscosity of the standard fluid (Ostwald Viscometer).

ρ_{test} : Density of the test liquid (Ostwald Viscometer).

ρ_{std} : Density of the standard fluid (Ostwald Viscometer).

t_{test} : Efflux time of the test liquid (Ostwald Viscometer).

t_{std} : Efflux time of the standard fluid (Ostwald Viscometer).

Ei : Exponential integral function.

r_0 : Wire radius.

C : Constant (related to Euler constant in hot wire method).

β : Euler constant ($\beta = 0.5772$).

q . : Rate of heat generated per unit time per unit length.

L_w : Thin wire length.

$V_{bridgeGain}$: Real bridge gain.

$V_{oscilloscope}$: Oscilloscope's amplified signal.

R_{0wire} : Initial wire resistance under bridge balance.

R_{20}, R_{1000} : Bridge fixed resistances.

$R_{potentiometer}, R_{pot}$: Variable resistor for bridge balancing.

R_t : Instantaneous wire resistance.

R_{wire} : Thin wire's instantaneous or average resistance.

G : Bridge real gain voltage.

V_s, V_{in} : Input voltage for the bridge.

T_{wire} : Wire temperature at time t.

T_0 : Initial wire temperature.

ΔT_{wire} : Change in wire temperature.

A : Area of heat transfer ,Cross-section area

Table of Contents

Chapter 1	19
1.1 Introduction	20
1.2 Importance of Decarbonising Heat in Homes	21
1.3 Heat Transfer Fluids to Improve Heating Efficiency.....	24
1.4 Summary	25
Chapter 2	26
2.1 Nanofluids as Heat Transfer Fluids	27
2.2 Preparation of Nanofluids	28
2.3 Stability Theory of Nanofluids (DLVO).....	29
2.4 Stabilising Methods	33
2.5 Thermal Instability	38
2.6 How Stability Affect the Rheological Properties of The Nanofluids	39
2.7 Mechanism Of Heat Transfer Enhancement by Nanofluids	40
2.8 Thermal conductivity of nanofluids.....	43
2.9 Specific heat capacity of nanofluids	47
2.10 Introduction to surfactants	49
2.11 Effect of Surfactants on Thermal Conductivity of Base Fluids	51
2.12 Effect of Surfactants on Critical Heat Flux and heat transfer coefficient	57
2.13 Mechanism Of Boiling Heat Transfer Enhancement by Surfactants.....	61
2.14 Silicone Surfactants	64
2.15 Summary	66

	11
2.16	References chapter 1&2 68
Chapter 3 73
3.1	Graphite..... 74
3.2	Silica, Alumina and Titania Nanoparticles..... 75
3.3	Alkyl Polyglycoside (APG) 76
3.3.1	Simulso SL 11 W 76
3.3.2	Simulsol SL 4..... 77
3.4	Silicone Surfactants 77
3.4.1	Silicone surfactant; Silsurf A008 78
3.4.2	Silicone surfactant; Silsurf A004 78
3.5	Electronic Components..... 79
3.5.1	Platinum Wire 79
3.5.2	Printed circuit boards PCBs..... 80
3.6	Power Supply Breakout Boards 80
3.6.1	HW-140 DC-DC Buck Boost Power Converter 80
3.6.2	DC-DC Positive & Negative Voltage Boost-Buck Converter 81
3.7	Raspberry Pi 83
3.8	Analogue To Digital Converters..... 83
3.8.1	ADS1115 83
3.8.2	ADS1263 85
3.8.3	Amplifier INA 131 86

	12
3.9 Oscilloscope And Power Supply	87
3.10 Marvel Zetaseizer	88
3.11 The room simulation Box and The Fluid Circulator	89
3.12 Pycnometer.....	91
3.13 Ostwald Viscometer.....	93
3.14 Summary	95
Chapter 4	97
4.1 Introduction.....	98
4.2 Geometry and meshing	99
4.3 Boundary conditions and governing equations	103
4.4 Properties of nanofluids	103
4.4.1 Volume fraction calculations	103
4.4.2 Density calculation.....	105
4.4.3 Specific heat capacity calculation.....	105
4.4.4 Thermal conductivity calculation	106
4.4.5 Kinematic viscosity calculation.....	107
4.4.6 Tables of thermophysical properties of nanofluids.....	107
4.4.7 Friction factor	109
4.4.8 Renolds number	109
4.4.9 Prandtl number.....	110
4.4.10 Nusselt number	111

4.4.11	Friction factor/Nusselt relationship.....	111
4.4.12	Petukhov equation.....	112
4.4.13	Log Mean Temperature Difference.....	113
4.5	Validation of the results	114
4.5.1	Validation of the software results using Water	114
4.5.2	Validation with Alumina.....	118
4.5.3	Validation with Silica	120
4.5.4	Validation with Titania	123
4.5.5	Validation with Graphene oxide	125
4.6	Water based Nanofluid heat transfer.....	127
4.6.1	Velocity simulation at 0.5 m/s	135
4.6.2	Velocity simulation at 1 m/s	138
4.6.3	Velocity simulation at 1.5 m/s	140
4.6.4	Velocity simulation at 2 m/s	142
4.7	Ethylene glycol Nanofluid heat transfer	144
4.7.1	Velocity simulation at 0.5 m/s	149
4.7.2	Velocity simulation at 1 m/s	150
4.7.3	Velocity simulation at 1.5 m/s	153
4.7.4	Velocity simulation at 2 m/s	155
4.8	Discussion	156
4.9	Summary	157

4.10	References Chapter 4	159
Chapter 5		162
5.1	Introduction	163
5.2	Characterisation methods	164
5.2.1	Raman spectrum	164
5.2.2	DLS	164
5.2.3	STEM and XRD.....	166
5.2.4	Energy-Dispersive X-ray Spectroscopy (EDX).....	167
5.3	Silica	168
5.3.1	Silica NP STEM, EDX.....	169
5.3.2	Zeta potential	170
5.3.3	Size distribution	171
5.4	Titania	172
5.4.1	Titania STEM, EDX.....	173
5.4.2	Zeta potential	174
5.4.3	Size distribution	176
5.5	Alumina.....	177
5.5.1	Alumina STEM, EDX.....	177
5.5.2	Zeta potential	178
5.5.3	Size distribution	179
5.6	Graphene Oxide.....	180

5.6.1	Synthesis of Graphene Oxide	181
5.6.2	Hummers Method	182
5.6.3	Modified Hummer's method.....	184
5.6.4	Improved synthesis methods	185
5.7	Characterisation of Graphene Oxide	185
5.7.1	The Raman spectrum of the graphene oxide	185
5.7.2	STEM, EDX	187
5.7.3	Zeta Potential.....	190
5.7.4	Size distribution	191
5.8	Summary	192
5.9	References Chapter 5	193
Chapter 6	195
6.1	Introduction	196
6.2	Theoretical foundation for the hot wire method.....	204
6.3	Circuit simulation and signal shape using MATLAB.....	209
6.3.1	The hot-wire circuit uses direct current (DC).....	210
6.3.2	The hot wire circuit using alternating and direct current DC/AC circuit.....	212
6.4	The transient hot wire Device	214
6.4.1	Determination of the Temperature Resistance Coefficient of the Wire	214
6.4.2	Determination of the wire's instantaneous and initial Resistance.....	215
6.4.3	Determination of the instantaneous wire temperature	217

6.4.4	Determination of the heat supplied to the wire per unit length.	219
6.4.5	Determination of the thermal conductivity of the fluid	220
6.4.6	The Hot wire device components	220
6.4.7	Platinum wire support frame.	220
6.4.8	The bridge and the amplifier	226
6.4.9	The cell.....	228
6.5	Data Processing	230
6.5.1	Processing the data using MATLAB or Excel.....	230
6.5.2	The Graphical user interface in MATLAB.....	232
6.5.3	Data processing using microcontrollers and processors	233
6.5.4	Arduino interfacing with LCD.....	234
6.5.5	Arduino interfacing with temperature sensor	236
6.5.6	Arduino interfacing with ADC ADS 1115	237
6.5.7	Arduino's Limitations in Processing Large Data Volumes.....	237
6.5.8	The raspberry Pi.....	238
6.5.9	The raspberry pi GPIO	240
6.5.10	Pi Connection to temperature sensor DS 18B20	241
6.5.11	Connecting the ADC, ADS 1115 16-bit ADC	244
6.5.12	High precision ADC hat from Waveshare	246
6.5.13	Pi Connection	248
6.6	Elimination of the spring.....	251

6.7	Validation of the device	252
6.8	Thermal conductivity of known base fluid	252
6.9	The Thermal Conductivity of Surfactant Solutions.....	256
6.10	Result graphs	260
6.11	Summary	265
6.12	References Chapter 6	267
Chapter 7	272
7.1	Introduction	273
7.2	Development of the room simulation box (RS Box).....	274
7.3	Comparison between selected heat transfer fluids	276
7.3.1	Comparison between Nanofluids and Water	276
7.3.2	Comparison between Surfactants and Water	277
7.3.3	Comparison between Nanofluids and Surfactants	278
7.3.4	Comparison between Silsurf A008 different Concentrations	279
7.3.5	Comparison between Silsurf A008 and GO	280
7.3.6	Comparison between silica, APG and silica.....	281
7.4	Comparison between titania, APG and titania	281
7.5	Comparison between alumina and APG	282
7.6	Summary	283
Chapter 8	284
8.1	Introduction	285

8.2	Durham council, Crook Civic Centre	285
8.2.1	Evaluating energy savings.....	285
8.2.2	Impact of Delta T APG.....	286
8.2.3	Monitoring the process.....	287
8.2.4	Delta-T (APG) Trial in Durham Council's Crook Civic Centre	292
8.3	Bradford Council, Britannia House.....	297
8.3.1	Evaluating energy saving	297
8.3.2	Monitoring the process.....	298
8.3.3	Impact of Delta T S.....	299
8.3.4	Delta-T S (Silicone surfactant) Trial in Bradford council.....	300
8.4	Summary	307
8.5	References Chapter 8.....	309
Chapter 9		310
9.1	Conclusion.....	311
9.2	Future Research and Recommendations in Research on Nanofluid	313

Chapter 1

The Importance of Heat Transfer Fluids in Sustainable Domestic Energy Use

1.1 Introduction

Domestic heating accounts for approximately 17% of the nation's total greenhouse gas emissions. In response, the UK government examined the energy-efficient technologies to be included in the Heat and Buildings Strategy. Complementary to these projects, this paper examines the use of advanced heat transfer fluids, including nanofluids and surfactant solutions, as a means to enhance heating system efficiency, reduce energy consumption, and lower operating costs.

Complementing the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), this project supports world sustainability objectives, especially Goals 7 (Affordable and Clean Energy), 9 (Industry, Innovation, and Infrastructure), and 13 (Climate Action). The development of better heat transfer fluids is a fundamental first step toward sustainable and clean energy systems.

Nanofluids produced by dispersing nanoparticles (less than 100 nm in size) into conventional base fluids, such as water or ethylene glycol, have shown notable enhancements in thermal conductivity and specific heat capacity. Making it suitable for efficient heat transfer in home heating applications; however, factors including stability and cost stand in the way of preventing their overall commercial acceptance.

Surfactants help to overcome these limitations. Particularly on silicone-based surfactant solutions, most notably those including Silsurf A008, which demonstrated appreciable energy-saving capacity in household heating trials.

Under turbulent flow conditions in small-diameter pipes, computational fluid dynamics (CFD) simulations enable the methodical investigation of the performance of several nanofluid formulations. Primary criteria for evaluation included the Nusselt number and convective heat transfer coefficients. We studied the effects of several nanoparticle types (silica, alumina, and

graphene oxide) and base fluids (water and ethylene glycol). The physical and chemical properties of the nanofluids and nanoparticles were characterised using advanced analytical techniques, including Raman spectroscopy, dynamic light scattering (DLS), scanning transmission electron microscopy (STEM), and X-ray diffraction (XRD).

This work produced a field-tested new silicone-based heat transfer fluid working with Bradford and Durham councils. The tests verified its enhanced heat transfer, underscoring the practical relevance of such compositions in reducing carbon emissions from domestic heating systems and energy demand.

1.2 Importance of Decarbonising Heat in Homes

The UK government published two reports under its energy demand reduction policy: the first, "Decarbonising Heat in Homes," and the second, "Heating and Building Strategies." Both reports focus on reducing energy consumption by increasing the efficiency of the heating system. Neither report mentioned the benefits of increasing the heat transfer fluid efficiency using additives.

The reports indicate that the government aims to achieve net-zero emissions by 2050, starting with a 78% reduction in emissions by 2035 compared to 1990 levels. This report suggests that the government is eager to address the issue of climate change.

As one-third of the UK's annual emissions come from heating, it is a major contributor, while domestic heating accounts for only 17% of the total annual emissions. The 2018 government report on clean growth and transforming heating acknowledged that decarbonising the heating sector would be a challenging transformation to reduce energy consumption. List transformation involves various methods, such as enhancing building efficiency, modifying the

heating and cooling system, and utilising products that increase the efficiency of energy transfer.

According to government reports, there are 29 million homes in the UK that are expected to adopt low-carbon emission heating systems by 2050. This decarbonisation of heating systems is expected to be achieved through methods such as heat pumps, hydrogen heat networks, and improving the efficiency of heat transfer. The UK government invested £4 billion in the financial years from 2022 to 2025 to enhance the decarbonisation of heating systems.

As the energy efficiency of heat transfer plays a crucial role in reducing energy consumption by lowering energy usage, this leads to a decrease in the energy bill and the size of the heating system. Reducing the size of the heating system will decrease its cost and contribute to achieving net zero. (“Heat and buildings strategy,” 2023)

Figure 1 shows Emission Contributions and Projected Savings for Building Heating in the UK, 2019–2030 (Adapted from Heat and Buildings Strategy, 2023)"

Figure 1 A. Shows the Emission contribution percentage as the proportion of emissions for each sector in 2019. B. Shows Emission contribution due to the building's heating. The proportion of emissions due to building heating, which accounts for 23% of emissions from buildings in 2019, domestic activities contributed 30% to the country's overall emissions, highlighting the significant impact of our daily lives on the environment. In 2019, the vast majority of English homes (86%) relied on gas central heating for their primary source of warmth. Electric storage heaters followed at a distant second, representing roughly 5% of dwellings. Finally, oil central heating was present in 3% of homes. In short, gas dominated the heating market in England at the time. D, the UK's Emission target savings by 2030 by sector, from Building Heating by 2030. E, The UK's savings achieved by technology type by 2030. Emission Savings from Building Heating by technology by 2030, adapted from ("Heat and buildings strategy," 2023)

1.3 Heat Transfer Fluids to Improve Heating Efficiency.

Heat transfer fluids are essential in both heating and cooling processes. They include traditionally water or ethylene glycol as a base fluid, with water being the most common base fluid due to its high heat capacity, thermal conductivity, and cost effectiveness. Recent investigations have focused on nanofluids and surfactant solutions as alternatives to traditional heat transfer fluids, as they significantly enhance heat transfer efficiency. Studies indicate that incorporating nanoparticles into conventional heat transfer fluids enhances the thermal and physical properties of the base fluid, resulting in improved heat transfer efficiency. The improvement is noticeable from the change in the Nusselt number. For this reason, nanofluids have recently been adopted as a promising alternative to traditional heat transfer fluids, which improve the performance of heating systems.(Khoury et al., 2024)

The presence of only surfactants in the base fluid improves the heat transfer efficiency in the heating systems. While the presence of surfactants in nanofluids significantly enhances the efficiency of heat transfer and the stability of the nanofluid, these surfactants are crucial for the stability of the nanofluid.(Ali et al., 2018a)

1.4 Summary

Reducing carbon emissions from homes is vital if the UK is to meet its net-zero target by 2050, as household heating accounts for approximately 17% of all greenhouse gas emissions in the country. While the UK government's Heat and Buildings Strategy supports hydrogen technologies and heat pumps, it largely overlooks the need to enhance the efficiency of heat transfer fluids.

This work aims to bridge that gap by examining surfactant-based solutions and nanofluids as next-generation heat transfer fluids. By dispersing nanoparticles, including silica, alumina, and graphene oxide, into conventional base fluids such as water and ethylene glycol, these formulations exhibit significantly improved thermal conductivity and convective heat transfer.

Field tests demonstrate increases in energy efficiency and reductions in carbon emissions, proving the practical viability of these advanced fluids when working with Bradford and Durham Councils. The results demonstrate the value of these formulations in supporting the UK's low-carbon heating transition and align with global sustainability targets.

Chapter 2

Literature review about nanofluids and
surfactant solutions as heat transfer
fluids

2.1 Nanofluids as Heat Transfer Fluids

Researchers have proven that some nanofluids exhibit approximately 78% higher thermal conductivity compared to the base fluid. The possible applications of nanofluids include electronic cooling, nuclear reactor cooling, and solar energy storage. The challenges of using nanofluids in commercial applications include the cost and stability of the nanofluids, particularly under harsh conditions such as high temperatures, extreme pH levels, and high salinity.

Nanoparticles could be classified according to their dimensions or their composition. Zero-dimensional nanoparticles are those with all dimensions less than 100nm. In contrast, one-dimensional nanoparticles, such as nanowires, have two dimensions less than 100 nm, offering elongated structures. Then, two-dimensional nanoparticles, such as graphene, have at least one dimension less than 100 nm. According to the composition, single-element oxide nanoparticles, alloys blending different elements, multi-element oxide nanoparticles, metal carbides, metal nitrides, and carbon nanoparticles. (Chakraborty and Panigrahi, 2020)

Nanoparticles composed of a single element, such as gold, silver, and copper, as well as single-element metal oxide nanoparticles like copper oxide, aluminium oxide, and titanium dioxide. Alloys such as copper-zinc alloy, silver-copper alloy, or nickel-iron alloy. Multi-element oxides are $\text{CuZnFe}_4\text{O}_4$, NiFe_2O_4 , or ZnFe_2O_4 . While metal carbides, such as SiC, ZnC, or B₄C, and metal nitrides, such as SiN, AlN, or TiN, are also considered, carbon-based materials, including carbon nanotubes and graphene, are also relevant. (Ali et al., 2018a)

As the nanofluids are recognised for their outstanding thermophysical properties, some products have been established in the market as intellectual properties for many companies. These products aim to enhance the heat transfer in the heat transfer systems. These products have improved surface tension, thermal conductivity and specific heat capacity compared to

the base fluids. Researchers reported that copper/water nanofluid could reach up to 78% higher thermal conductivity than the base fluid. (Ali et al., 2018a; Esfe and Afrand, 2019) (Haddad et al., 2014)

2.2 Preparation of Nanofluids

There are two main methods for preparing nanofluids: one-step and two-step preparation methods. The two-step method involves two steps: firstly, nano powders are prepared using methods that may be physical, chemical, or biological, and then the prepared nanoparticles are dispersed in the base fluid. The base fluid can be either polar or non-polar, resulting in a dispersion process that differs according to its polarity. In contrast, the one-step method combines both the preparation and dispersion processes in a single step. Therefore, it involves the simultaneous preparation and dispersion of nanoparticles in the base fluid. The choice between a one-step and a two-step method depends on factors such as the type of nanoparticles and the base fluid. While the one-step method offers better size control of the nanoparticles, the two-step method remains the easiest for commercial applications and is more cost-effective. (Esfe and Afrand, 2019). Nanofluids prepared by the one-step method are more stable and have a lower tendency towards agglomeration. The one-step method can be achieved either by chemical or physical methods. Chemical methods are less expensive than physical methods, which are challenging to scale up for large-scale production. In contrast, the chemical method can be easily adapted for large-scale production. Zhu et al. prepared the aqueous copper nanofluid by reducing a solution of copper sulphate using sodium hypophosphite monohydrate under microwave irradiation. The resulting nanofluid was highly stable and well dispersed. Most metallic nanofluids can be prepared similarly, such as silver nanofluids. The resulting nanofluid from the one-step method exhibits improved stability and a more uniform size distribution of nanoparticles.

The two-step method for nanofluid preparation is employed due to its cost-effectiveness and reliability. The solid nanoparticles are prepared using chemical or physical methods, and then dispersed in the dispersion medium using mechanical methods, such as ultrasound, magnetic force, a homogeniser, or high-shear mixers. The two-step method allows the use of commercially available nanoparticle powders. (Zhu et al., 2004).. (Ali et al., 2018a) (Chakraborty and Panigrahi, 2020). The disadvantage of the two-step method is that the nanoparticles tend to agglomerate and form clusters. To prevent nanoparticle agglomeration and enhance nanofluid stability, a mechanical dispersion method should be frequently employed to maintain a suitable size distribution and prevent agglomeration from occurring. The addition of surfactants helps stabilise the nanofluids by controlling the agglomeration through the steric and electrostatic hindrance. Commonly used surfactants are Sodium dodecyl sulphate, Sodium dodecyl benzene sulfonate, Cetyltrimethylammonium bromide, Span 80, Tween 20, Polyvinylpyrrolidone, and Gum Arabic. The two-step method is suitable for large-scale production due to its cost-effectiveness. However, the stability of the resulting nanofluid is generally lower than that achieved with the one-step method, as agglomeration and sedimentation are more likely to occur. To prolong the suspension stability, continuous dispersion techniques, such as ultrasound or stirring, can be employed. Despite these efforts, controlling the shape and size of nanoparticles remains challenging with the two-step method. (Chakraborty and Panigrahi, 2020)

2.3 Stability Theory of Nanofluids (DLVO)

Maintaining the stability of nanofluids during production is crucial for their optimal performance and utility in use. It is crucial to avoid the aggregation of nanoparticles, which can obstruct flow or settle at the bottom over time, as this can alter the characteristics of the nanofluid and affect its efficiency and cost-effectiveness. The key to ensuring the stability of

nanofluids is to maintain the particles in suspension, thereby retaining their size and preventing sedimentation for an extended period.(Chakraborty and Panigrahi, 2020)

Different approaches are used to assess the consistency of nanofluids. An ordinary method involves the process of precipitation and centrifugation, which examines stability by observing how quickly particles settle under centrifugal forces. A lower rate of sedimentation suggests stability in the nanofluid. Another technique involves analysing absorbance and transmission. Where variations in absorbency are tracked over time to assess stability, this is particularly useful when nanoparticles absorb light within the range of 190 to 1100 nm. Researchers and engineers rely on these methods to evaluate the stability of nanofluids and enhance the process of preparing and utilising them in various industries. (Yu and Xie, 2011)

Nanofluids consist of dispersed particles that have surface activity and often clump together to form clusters of varying sizes, which may cause nanoparticles to settle out of the solution over time due to the increased cluster sizes affecting the nanofluid's properties. The ability to keep the nanoparticles suspended in the base fluid is essential for preserving the attributes and qualities of the nanofluid. The reason why nanoparticles remain stable can be understood through the Derjaguin-Landau-Verwey-Overbeek (DLVO) theory, which outlines how attraction and repulsion forces influence the behaviour of nanoparticles. Sedimentation can occur when attractive forces are stronger, resulting in nanoparticle agglomeration. The DLVO theory clarifies how colloids stay stable by considering van der Waals and electrostatic forces as the factors affecting dispersed nanoparticles. Van der Waals forces and electrostatic forces are types of repulsive forces that act between molecules and atoms. Electrostatic forces arise from charged particles, such as ions or molecules, which possess a charge, resulting in attraction or repulsion depending on the type of charge (Hu et al., 2020). Van der Waals forces occur when there are uneven changes in the distribution of electrons around a molecule or atom, resulting in the creation of polarity within the molecule. According to the theory

explanation mentioned in the equation 2-1, the overall potential consists of the combined forces from van der Waals and electrostatic force interactions. (Chakraborty and Panigrahi, 2020)

$$V_{total} = V_{van\ der\ Waal} + V_{electrostatic} \quad 2-1$$

V_{total} is the total electrostatic interaction potential, $V_{van\ der\ Waals}$ is the van der Waals interaction potential, while $V_{electrostatic}$ is the electrostatic interaction potential.

The interactions between nanoparticles in a nanofluid are also influenced by their size and shape. Calculating the van der Waals forces between two entities relies heavily on the Hamaker constant. A high value for the Hamaker constant indicates forces that can lead to particle agglomeration and potential instability within the nanofluid. The stability of nanofluids depends on the total potential energy (V_{total}), which is a function of the distance between nanoparticles. The distance and potential energy between nanoparticles are affected by Brownian motion. If the total potential energy is positive, repulsive forces dominate, and the colloidal suspension is stable. However, if the potential energy is negative, attractive forces dominate, and particles tend to agglomerate, causing colloidal instability. At higher temperatures, particles gain the energy required to overcome repulsive barriers, causing collisions that allow attractive forces to pull them together, resulting in the formation of clusters. In situations where particle size is high and zeta potential is low, van der Waals forces become dominant. As a result, Clusters form weak bonds that can be broken by the energy acquired through agitation or ultrasonication, allowing for the more effective dispersion of nanoparticles. The stability of nanofluids is influenced by various factors, including the dielectric constant of the fluid, its pH level, the zeta potential, particle size and shape, and the concentration of nanoparticles present in the mixture. The relationship between the dielectric constant and the repulsive forces is proportional. The formation of an electric double layer around the nanoparticles occurs when they are present in a base fluid. The electric double layer

consists of an outer and inner layer, referred to as the Stern and diffuse layers, respectively. The Stern layer is a part of the nanoparticle surface, while the diffuse layer is composed of the fluid surrounding the nanoparticle and the charged Stern layer. The electrical double layer bears no charge because the positive and negative charges present within it effectively neutralise each other. The zeta potential provides an evaluation of the nanoparticle interfacial electrical potential within the double layer. It is a crucial indicator of the colloidal suspension stability. When the zeta potential increases, the repulsive forces also increase, thereby enhancing the stability of the colloidal suspension. A zeta potential higher than ± 30 indicates a stable colloid, while anything below ± 15 shows instability. The pH value affects the zeta potential and, in turn, influences the stability of the suspension. The pH value affects the charge density within the electric double layer, thereby influencing the stability of nanofluids. The pH value also plays a crucial role in determining the shape and size of nanoparticles during the synthesis process, and it impacts their stability. The force of the interaction between the double-layer electric charge and the van der Waals forces depends on the nanoparticle size. For small particle sizes, the number of surface atoms is high compared to the total, increasing the density of active sites. He et al. found that the tendency of hematite to aggregate increases with decreasing particle size, at a fixed pH and ionic strength. Thus, the tendency to aggregate increases with decreasing particle size. The classic Derjaguin-Landau-Verwey-Overbeek (DLVO) theory can predict the forces acting on only spherical nanoparticles. Other shapes represent a complication for the DLVO theory. Suppose the separation distance between nanoparticles is smaller than the nanoparticle's average diameter. In that case, more atoms on the nanoparticle surface are available to generate attractive interactions between nanoparticles, leading to the domination of attractive forces and causing the nanoparticles to aggregate. The sedimentation velocity of a spherical suspended nanoparticle in a base fluid under gravitational force can be calculated using Stokes' Equation. (Chakraborty and Panigrahi, 2020) (Wu et al., 2009).

$$V = \frac{2R^2}{9\mu(\rho_p - \rho_f) * g} \quad 2-2$$

In equation 2-2 V is the sedimentation velocity of the nanoparticle, assuming that it is sphere-like shaped, and R is the sphere radius. ρ_p Is the density of the nanoparticle sphere? ρ_f Is the fluid density, g is the gravitational acceleration, while μ It is the dynamic viscosity of the fluid.

Based on Stokes' Equation, improving the stability of a suspended nanoparticle requires reducing the particle size, increasing the viscosity of the base fluid, and decreasing the density difference between the suspending medium and the suspended solid particle. A smaller particle size results in higher surface energy, which increases the likelihood of agglomeration and sedimentation. The formulator must balance reducing nanoparticle size with preventing agglomeration. A way to achieve this is by employing surfactants or other stabilising substances that generate a repulsion between the nanoparticles, thereby preventing their proximity and further aggregation. Enhancing the viscosity of the base fluid can also aid in stabilising the nanoparticles by impeding their motion and minimising the likelihood of collision and aggregation. This method may not always be feasible as it could impact the conductivity properties of the nanofluid. Reducing the difference in density between the liquid and the solid particles can enhance stability by decreasing the impact of gravity on the nanoparticles, which can be done by choosing a fluid that closely matches the nanoparticles' density or by utilising nanoparticles with a density close to the base fluid. (Wu et al., 2009)

2.4 Stabilising Methods

Either chemical or mechanical techniques can enhance the stability of nanofluids. Mechanical methods such as ultrasonication are effective in dispersing nanoparticle clusters.

Ultrasonication can be employed in two ways: using an ultrasound bath or an ultrasound probe. Direct sonication using the probe is found to be more effective in dispersing nanoparticle clusters and reducing their size. Ball milling offers an effective approach to decrease particle size and enhance nanofluid stability. It can be used in conjunction with ultrasound and magnetic stirring to reduce cluster size further and improve stability. Chemical stabilisation techniques for nanofluids include three types: steric, electrostatic, and a combination of both. Steric stabilisation is achieved by adding a polymer or surfactant. In contrast, electrostatic stabilisation occurs when the electrostatic potential dominates the van der Waals forces, resulting in repulsion between nanoparticles with the same charge. The surface electrical charge originates from the ionisation of surface functional groups through the adsorption of other molecules, such as surfactants. The charged particles attract counterions from their surroundings to form the double layer. When the electrical double layer overlaps with itself, it causes stabilisation. The charge density surrounding a charged nanoparticle creates electrostatic repulsion, which helps keep the particles stably dispersed within the base fluid. The distribution of charge is organised into three layers: the surface charge layer, where charges are adsorbed directly onto the nanoparticle's surface; the Stern layer, a tightly bound region of counterions close to the surface; and the diffuse layer, a more loosely arranged outer region where ions can move freely. Together, these layers ensure effective stabilisation of the nanoparticle suspension through balanced electrostatic forces. The Stern layer forms due to the adsorbed charges on the surface of the nanoparticle, which attract counterions from the medium. These ions adhere to the nanoparticle surface, forming the Stern layer. (Mohd Omar et al., 2014; Lashari et al., 2022)

Figure 2 shows the anatomy of the electric double layer surrounding the nanoparticle. The electric double layer influences the stability of the nanofluid.

Figure 2: Anatomy of the electrical double layer (Mohd Omar et al., 2014; Lashari et al., 2022).
The

Figure 3 The figure shows the classification of the double-layer zones and the potential distribution between them (Lashari et al., 2022).

Figure 4 Steric and electrostatic stabilisation (Yu and Xie, 2011) (Lashari et al., 2022)

Figure 4 Shows presentation of the steric and electrostatic stabilisation, which have an important impact on the stability of the nanofluid (Yu and Xie, 2011) (Lashari et al., 2022)

The diffuse layer forms as charged ions from the surroundings next to the charged nanoparticle, where they loosely attach to its surface. The highest electrical potential is found at the nanoparticle's surface. Decreases gradually moving away from it, reaching zero at the limits of the electrical double layer. (Chakraborty and Panigrahi, 2020)

The zeta potential refers to the value at the interface where the fluid surrounding a nanoparticle meets the attached fluid layer, separated by the slipping plane. The goal of stabilisation is to create an electrical potential barrier between nanoparticles to prevent their clustering.

Enhancing this barrier leads to stability in the nanofluid composition. To improve the stability of nanofluids, surfactants are used. Surfactant types include ionic, cationic, zwitterionic, and non-ionic surfactants. Ionic surfactants are commonly used for providing stability to nanofluids, while non-ionic surfactants are employed to achieve stabilisation of suspensions through steric effects. Adjusting the pH is crucial as it affects the zeta potential at the isoelectric point. Since the zeta potential influences the repulsive interactions between nanoparticles, maintaining an optimal zeta potential by adjusting the pH above or below the isoelectric point is necessary to maximise forces and enhance stability. (Ali et al., 2018a; Chakraborty and Panigrahi, 2020;) When it comes to electrostatic stabilisation, certain limitations must be considered. This method may not be suitable for non-polar base fluids as its effectiveness relies on electrical charges that may not interact well in such environments. Also, agglomeration in electrostatic stabilisation is often irreversible, making redispersion challenging or impossible once particles have clustered together. This technique is also not ideal for electrolytic suspensions. Electrostatic stabilisation is typically most effective in dilute mixtures, limiting its use in more concentrated solutions. Understanding these limitations is crucial for optimising the use of electrostatic stabilisation in various applications. Steric stabilisation is also referred to as polymeric stabilisation. Involves incorporating polymer molecules into the nanofluid to prevent clumping and settling down over time due to gravity. The polymer molecules attached to the nanoparticle surfaces create a barrier that stops the nanoparticles from forming clusters due to steric hindrance. This can be achieved by using surfactants, polymers, or a combination of both. Unlike electrostatic stabilisation, steric stabilisation is suitable for concentrated nanofluids. Highly adsorbed polymers and long-chain polymers are more effective steric stabilisers. Chemisorption leads to the formation of a strong bond between nanoparticles and molecules (Mukherjee et al., 2018; Yu & Xie, 2011). Polymer molecules used for stabilisation have an anchor part and a tail component in their structure. The anchor part forms a bond with

the nanoparticle surface, forming a protective layer. At the same time, the tail faces outward towards the base fluid to prevent the nanoparticles from coming into contact with each other. Electrosteric stabilisation methods involve using polymers that coat the nanoparticles with a charged layer (acting as a barrier) along with providing a protective steric barrier as well (Chakraborty & Panigrahi, 2020; Mukherjee et al., 2018; Yu & Xie, 2011)

2.5 Thermal Instability

Suspended nanoparticles in a base fluid undergo Brownian motion. As the fluid temperature rises, the Brownian motion increases, resulting in a higher diffusion coefficient. The increase in Brownian motion of the nanoparticles induces a higher probability of collisions between particles, thereby creating a greater chance of forming clusters and aggregating the nanoparticles. Therefore, operating a nanofluid for heat transfer purposes requires attention to stability. Stabilising heat transfer fluids using surfactants and polymers could be unsuitable if these molecules tend to deteriorate or degrade at elevated temperatures. (Ali et al., 2018a; Askar et al., 2020)

To manufacture highly stable nanofluids, both mechanical treatment and surface functionalisation should be considered. Fouling is a complication that occurs when the stability of the nanoparticle is lost, causing the nanoparticles to deposit on the heat transfer surface and increase the surface thermal resistivity. Surface roughness is another complication that arises due to the deposition of nanoparticles on the heat transfer surface, increasing nucleate boiling heat transfer phenomena, which could affect the flow dynamics. Studies on the nanofluid flow dynamics under elevated temperatures showed that the nanofluid changes its flow category from laminar to turbulent as the temperature increases. The thermal conductivity of the nanofluid decreases as the stability decreases. Research studies have shown that there is an optimal clustering level to obtain the maximum thermal conductivity. Nanoparticle

aggregations are composed of linear and side-chain aggregations. The thermal conductivity increases with the increase of the linear clustering structure of the suspended particles. The linear aggregation of nanoparticles enhances thermal conductivity, as heat conduction is attributed to the linear clustering structure. The control of the clustering rate is crucial for enhancing thermal conductivity and avoiding sedimentation, which consequently reduces thermal conductivity. Increasing particle mobility causes an increase in thermal conductivity due to the presence of microconvection. (; Chakraborty and Panigrahi, 2020; Mukherjee et al., 2018; Yu and Xie, 2011)

2.6 How Stability Affect the Rheological Properties of The Nanofluids

Nanofluids could behave as either Newtonian or non-Newtonian fluids depending on particle size, shape, type, concentration of nanoparticles, method of stabilisation, base fluid, temperature, and shear rate. The viscosity of a nanofluid tends to rise with nanoparticle concentration while decreasing with temperature increments. Furthermore, particle size and shape play roles in influencing viscosity. The increase in nanoparticle concentration reduces the surface tension. Additionally, increasing the temperature reduces surface tension. As the nanoparticle concentration increases, the distance between the particles decreases, resulting in a higher attraction due to the predominance of van der Waals forces at the surface (gas-liquid interface), which leads to an increase in surface tension. As the nanoparticles align on the surface, the interaction between the nanoparticles determines the value of the surface tension. If van der Waals forces become dominant, the surface tension increases; however, if the electrostatic repulsive force becomes dominant, the surface tension decreases. The presence of electrostatic repulsion and van der Waals forces depends on the nature of the nanoparticles, the base fluid, and the interactions between their particles.(Ali et al., 2018b; Askar et al., 2020;

Chakraborty and Panigrahi, 2020; Kanti et al., 2022; Khooshechin et al., 2020; Mukherjee et al., 2018; Orrill et al., 2021; Ranjbarzadeh et al., 2019; Yu and Xie, 2011)

2.7 Mechanism Of Heat Transfer Enhancement by Nanofluids

Six phenomena have been discovered to contribute to the enhancement of heat transfer in nanofluids. The Brownian motion, the nanolayer, the nanoclusters, thermophoresis, surface area and the ballistic heat transfer phenomena. Brownian Motion plays a significant role in heat transfer. Researchers propose that while Brownian motion may have an influence on heat transfer phenomena compared to thermal diffusion processes, it could indirectly affect thermal conductivity through the formation of particle clusters. Some scientists have suggested that nanoconvection, driven by Brownian motion, plays a role in the heat transfer of nanofluids. (Buongiorno et al., 2009) . Scientists have proposed alternative mechanisms for heat transfer in nanofluids, including local convection induced by Brownian motion. This micro-scale mixing has a significant impact on the conductivity of nanofluids. The nanolayer of molecules surrounding nanoparticles plays a role in heat exchange. According to Koblinski and Xie, such nanolayers are usually 1 to 2 nanometers thick. The researchers proposed that this ordered nanolayer serves as a thermal bridge between solid nanoparticles and base fluid, therefore enhancing the conductivity of the nanofluids. Other researchers mentioned that this layer forms a barrier known as Kapitza resistance, which could impede heat transfer processes.

The nanoclusters refer to the clustering of the nanoparticles. The clustering of nanoparticles affects the thermal conductivity of the nanofluid.

Figure 5 Shows the electrostatic and the Electrosteric repulsion between nanoparticles.(Chakraborty and Panigrahi, 2020)

Figure 6. Clustering effect on the thermal conductivity of the nanofluid (Bakthavatchalam et al., 2020)

Figure 5 shows the electrostatic and the Electrosteric repulsion between nanoparticles. In case of nanofluid stabilisation, the use of steric and electrostatic stabilisation will enhance the stability of the nanofluid.(Chakraborty and Panigrahi, 2020) While Figure 6 shows that the clustering of nanoparticles affects the thermal conductivity of the nanofluid, a particle-rich zone leads to lower thermal resistance zones compared to the particle-poor zones (Bakthavatchalam et al., 2020)

Kebblinski suggested that nanoclusters create a particle-rich zone, leading to lower thermal resistance zones compared to particle-poor zones, so nanoclusterization potentially enhances thermal conductivity. However, large clusters tend to precipitate and settle, causing a reduction in the thermal conductivity of the nanofluid. Additionally, it was found that clustering enhances the electrical conductivity as well. (Buongiorno et al., 2009; Murshed, 2023; Murshed et al., 2006; Yu et al., 2010; Yu and Xie, 2011).

Thermophoresis, also known as Thermodiffusion or Soret effect. The temperature gradient in the fluid causes the movement in multicomponent particle mixtures. Molecules move from the hot region to the cold region in the case of positive thermal diffusion, while in negative thermal diffusion, the movement is from the cold to the hot region in the nanofluid. The thermophoresis and the Osmophoresis are phenomenon that involves the particle movement in the nanofluids, which is different from the random movement in the case of Brownian motion, as in these processes, the particles move according to the temperature and pressure gradient, respectively.

The thermal conductivity enhancement due to this phenomenon is independent of the particle size.

Ballistic heat transfer is a ballistic diffusive process via phonons. A few researchers have investigated the theory of ballistic heat transfer, but there has been no further development of theories specifically addressing ballistic heat transport since then. (Buongiorno et al., 2009)

The high specific surface area of the nanoparticles enables the nanofluids to exhibit enhanced heat transfer capabilities, potentially. Xie was among the first to demonstrate the impact of high specific surface area on the thermal conductivity enhancement of nanofluids. Xie conducted an experiment using the AL_2O_3/EG nanofluid, observing an increase in thermal conductivity with an increase in surface area until an optimum point was reached, after which it subsequently decreased. The enhancement of thermal conductivity due to the specific surface area is attributed to the reduction in particle size, increasing the interfacial area. However, as the particle size decreases significantly, phonons—quantised lattice vibrations responsible for heat transfer—begin to scatter at the interfaces between the solid particles and the surrounding liquid. This scattering effect leads to a reduction in thermal conductivity. This is because the phonon free path needs to be longer than the particle size. (Yu et al., 2010; Yu and Xie, 2011)

2.8 Thermal conductivity of nanofluids

Ranjbarzadeh, in 2019, investigated the stability and thermal conductivity of silica nanofluids. They found that these nanofluids remained stable for over six months, with an enhancement in thermal conductivity of 38.2%, particularly at 55°C, across a volume fraction range of 0.1% to 3%. Another study, conducted by Li et al. and published in 2016, examined silicon carbide nanofluids to determine an increase in thermal conductivity of 53% at a volume fraction of 0.5% and a temperature of 50°C.

Figure 7 Thermal conductivity of water versus temperature(Ranjbarzadeh et al., 2019)

Figure 7 illustrates the change in thermal conductivity of water with temperature—the thermal conductivity of water increases as the temperature rises (Ranjbarzadeh et al., 2019). Oliveira and Filho (2014) examined how heat transfer through a silver nanofluid in a radiator using nanoparticle sizes of 80 nm and 10 nm observing a conductivity enhancement of 18% and 5% for 0.1% and 0.3% volume concentrations at inlet temperatures of 25°C and 45°C, the impact of three nanofluids multi walled carbon nanotubes (MWCNT), copper oxide (CuO), and aluminum oxide (Al_2O_3) on the heat transfer performance of automotive radiators was assessed using a 1% volume concentration for each nanofluid, with flow rates between 4 and 8 liters per minute, an air velocity of 3 m/s, and inlet temperatures from 60 to 80°C. The results showed that all nanofluids enhanced thermal performance compared to water, with the MWCNT-water nanofluid achieving the highest improvement, as indicated by a Nusselt number enhancement

of 41.7%, followed by CuO (31.7%) and Al₂O₃ (12.3%) (Abbas et al., 2020; Al-Araji et al., 2021). In a 2014 study, Narella found that incorporating nanoparticles into solar collectors could significantly enhance heat transfer efficiency compared to conventional fluids. Likewise, Sharahi researched the behaviour of heat transfer in flat-shaped pipes using nanofluids in 2010. His findings showed a decrease in thermal resistance and an increase in heat transfer. In 2014, Hussein conducted experiments on forced convection heat transfer and used them to validate numerical and simulation results, indicating improvements in heat transfer efficiency.

Figure 8 Effect of Nanoparticle Shape on the Thermal Conductivity of Alumina-Water Nanofluids (Efemwenkikie and Oyedepo, 2019)

Figure 8 illustrates the thermal conductivity behaviour of alumina nanoparticles in water with different shapes (spherical, cylindrical, and platelet) at various volume concentrations. The

thermal conductivity of the nanofluids increases with increasing volume concentration for all three shapes. However, the rate of increase in thermal conductivity is higher for spherical and platelet-shaped nanoparticles compared to cylindrical ones. This suggests that the shape of the nanoparticles plays a significant role in enhancing the thermal conductivity of the alumina nanofluids. (Efemwenkikie and Oyedepo, 2019)

Figure 9 Effect of Nanoparticle Shape on the Thermal Conductivity of Silica-Water Nanofluids(Efemwenkikie and Oyedepo, 2019)

Figure 9 illustrates the thermal conductivity behaviour of Silica nanoparticles in water with different shapes (spherical, cylindrical, and platelet) at various volume concentrations. The thermal conductivity of the nanofluids increases with increasing volume concentration for all three shapes. However, the rate of increase in thermal conductivity is higher for cylindrical and platelet-shaped nanoparticles compared to spherical ones, albeit at a very slow rate. This suggests that the shape of the nanoparticles plays a significant role in enhancing the thermal conductivity of the silica nanofluids. (Efemwenkikie and Oyedepo, 2019)

Research showed that the shape of nanoparticles affects the thermal conductivity of nanofluids. (Efemwenkiele and Oyedepo, 2019) Suggest that spherical and platelet-shaped nanoparticles tend to provide higher thermal conductivity than cylindrical ones for some nanoparticles. However, the specific mechanisms behind this are not mentioned in the reference. Several studies, including the work by Senthilraja et al. on CuO nanofluids in four-stroke engine cooling, have emphasised the importance of nanoparticle shape in thermal performance. While Efemwenkiele and his coworkers confirm that shape is a key factor, they do not explain why specific shapes enhance conductivity more than others. Some possible explanations that may require further investigation include differences in the surface area-to-volume ratio, the ability of particles to form conductive networks within the fluid, and their alignment under flow conditions. Also, the tendency of nanoparticles to cluster is a process influenced by their shape. This could be a major contributor to increased thermal conductivity.

2.9 Specific heat capacity of nanofluids

Figure 10 Shows the relationship between the specific heat capacity of the nanofluid (Silica and alumina) and the volume fraction of nanoparticles at a temperature of 45 °C. Enhancements in specific heat capacity in nanofluids are typically observed to be between 10% and 30%. However, the addition of nanoparticles to water has sometimes reduced the heat capacities. There is no comprehensive molecular theory that fully describes the impact of nanoparticles on the specific heat capacity of heat transfer fluids.

Figure 10 Specific Heat Capacity in Alumina and Silica Nanofluids at Varying Volume Fractions (Hentschke, 2016)

Figure 10 demonstrates Experimental Specific heat capacity of Silica and Alumina vs the vol fraction % of nanoparticles. The specific heat capacity of alumina and silica nanoparticles decreases as the volume fraction increases. This trend suggests that the thermal energy storage capacity of the nanofluids decreases with an increase in the concentration of nanoparticles. (Hentschke, 2016)

The enhancement of specific heat capacity in nanofluids is promising, but several factors, including nanoparticle type, concentration, and preparation technique influence it. This potential enhancement offers opportunities for improving the efficiency of thermal energy storage and transfer in solar power and other related applications. (Hentschke, 2016; Lu and Huang, 2013; Namburu et al., 2007; Zhou and Ni, 2008)

2.10 Introduction to surfactants

Surfactants are elongated organic molecules that have hydrophilic and hydrophobic groups. They are classified into four main types based on the charge of their hydrophilic head group to anionic, cationic, nonionic, and amphoteric (zwitterionic). Anionic surfactants, such as sodium lauryl sulfate, carry a negative charge and are widely used in detergents. Cationic surfactants, like quaternary ammonium compounds, have a positive charge. Nonionic surfactants, which have no charge, rely on polar groups such as ethoxylates for their solubility. Amphoteric surfactants can possess both positive and negative charges depending on the pH. Alkyl polyglucosides (APGs) derived from coconut or palm oil and glucose fall under the nonionic category and are valued for their low toxicity and high biodegradability. They are used in many fields to reduce the surface tension of nanofluids, as well as to reduce the interfacial pressure at the fluid-solid interface. The surfactant molecule is composed of two distinct components: a hydrophilic part and a hydrophobic part. Saturated and unsaturated fatty acids, along with mono-, di-, and polysaccharides, can be utilised in constructing the surfactant molecule. The surfactant molecule can form a micelle at the critical micelle concentration (CMC); these micelles can be developed into four types depending on the conditions (normal micelle, reverse micelle, liposome and mixed micelles). Surfactants are classified based on their structure and biodegradability. From the perspective of biodegradability, there are non-biodegradable and biodegradable surfactants. According to their structure, they are categorised into anionic, cationic, and non-ionic. The non-biodegradable surfactants represent the conventional surfactants. They are anionic, cationic, or non-ionic. Typically, the polar groups used for manufacturing surfactants are sulphate, carboxylate, and sulphonate for anionic surfactants, and quaternary ammonium for cationic surfactants. While the non-ionic surfactants usually have their functional group as polyoxyethylene or sucrose. In contrast, the tail or the hydrophobic nonpolar component consists of paraffins, olefins, alcohol or alkylphenol, such as

sodium dodecyl sulphate, cetyltrimethylammonium bromide. Non-biodegradable surfactants have a negative impact on the environment, as they undergo bioaccumulation and their byproducts can be environmentally hazardous. As an example, the alkylphenol ethoxylate could cause a carcinogenic and estrogenic effect, causing a decline in sperm count. Anionic surfactants are less toxic than cationic surfactants, while nonionic surfactants could bind to proteins and phospholipids. (Singh et al., 2018)

Figure 11 surfactants molecular structure

Figure 11 Shows surfactants molecular structure A, Cetyltrimethylammonium bromide. B, Sodium Dodecyl Sulfate. C, span 20 sorbitan monolaurate. There is an increasing demand for biodegradable, environmentally friendly surfactants and chemicals to mitigate environmental pollution. Mannosylerythritol lipid is a biodegradable surfactant which could be extracted from some microorganisms. (Zulkifli et al., 2024).

In biosurfactants, there are three categories, including glycolipids, formed from combinations of glucose and lipids such as Rhamnolipids and Sophorolipids. Another category is

lipopeptides, which consist of proteins and lipids, such as surfactins and mycosubtilin. The third category is phospholipids, which are composed of phosphate and lipids, such as sphingomyelin and Lecithin. Biosurfactants are natural molecules that decrease the surface tension as the repulsion forces at the interface between two different phases, allowing these phases to be solvated (Singh et al., 2018). Sugar-based surfactants, such as glycolipids, are degradable surfactants produced by microorganisms, including bacteria and fungi. Typically, sugar surfactants with more than one hydrophobic tail are referred to as glycolipids. The head and tail can be linked to various molecules such as glycerol (Stubenrauch, 2001), alkyl polyglycosides, and sorbitan esters. As shown in Figure 11 These compounds represent important types of biodegradable, sugar-based surfactants. The achievement of super-low surface tension can be reached by using a combination of surfactant and cosurfactant, such as Polyglycoside and Sorbitan esters. The surface tension could be as low as 0.001mN/m (Sufek et al., 2013; Wu et al., 2010)

2.11 Effect of Surfactants on Thermal Conductivity of Base Fluids

Surfactants, which are long organic molecules featuring both hydrophilic and lipophilic groups, play a key role in nanofluids by improving the dispersion and stability of nanoparticles. However, their presence also modifies the base fluid's physical properties, particularly thermal conductivity and viscosity. Understanding how surfactant concentration affects thermal conductivity is essential. Experimental studies have demonstrated that the relationship between surfactant concentration and thermal conductivity is complex and varies depending on the surfactant's chemical nature, specifically whether it is anionic, cationic, or non-ionic.

For example, with the anionic surfactant sodium dodecylbenzene sulfonate (SDBS), the thermal conductivity ratio (the ratio of the solution's thermal conductivity to that of pure water) increases as concentration rises. Further increases in SDBS concentration lead to a decline in

thermal conductivity. This trend is thought to result from improved heat transfer at low concentrations due to the formation of surfactant aggregates. In contrast, higher concentrations promote the formation of larger micellar structures, which hinder heat transfer. Sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS), another anionic surfactant, follows a similar pattern, with an initial rise and subsequent decrease in thermal conductivity ratio as concentration increases. However, the decline in SDS's thermal conductivity slows and stabilises at higher concentrations.

In contrast, the cationic surfactant cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB) exhibits a more pronounced reduction in thermal conductivity ratio as its concentration increases. This suggests that CTAB micelle formation has a more substantial negative impact on water's thermal conductivity than the anionic surfactants.

A common observation across all surfactants is that thermal conductivity ratios tend to stabilise beyond a specific concentration. When comparing these stable values, ionic surfactants generally provide higher thermal conductivity ratios than non-ionic ones, highlighting the importance of the surfactant's head group in determining thermal behaviour. (Mingzheng et al., 2012)

Figure 12 shows the SDS (CMC 0.24% wt) concentration against the thermal conductivity ratio of the solution compared to the base fluid (water) at room temperature. In contrast, Figure 13 shows the CTAB (CMC 0.033 % wt) concentration against the thermal conductivity ratio of the solution compared to the base fluid(water) at room temperature (Mingzheng et al., 2012). Figure 14 Depicts the thermal conductivity of sodium dodecyl sulphate (SDS) solution as a function of temperature. The thermal conductivity of the SDS solution increases with increasing temperature, indicating that the heat transfer properties of the solution improve with

higher temperatures. Moreover, finally Figure 15 illustrates the thermal conductivity of polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP) solution as a function of temperature. The thermal conductivity of the PVP solution increases with increasing temperature, indicating that the heat transfer properties of the solution improve with higher temperatures. (Mingzheng et al., 2012)

Figure 16 depicts the thermal conductivity of sodium dodecylbenzenesulfonate (SDBS) solution as a function of temperature. The thermal conductivity of the SDBS solution increases with increasing temperature, indicating that the heat transfer properties of the solution improve with higher temperatures. (Mingzheng et al., 2012)

Figure 17 depicts the thermal conductivity of water as a function of temperature. The thermal conductivity of water increases with increasing temperature. (Mingzheng et al., 2012)

Figure 12 shows SDS concentration against the thermal conductivity ratio of the solution (Mingzheng et al., 2012)

Figure 13 shows CTAB concentration against the thermal conductivity ratio of the solution (Mingzheng et al., 2012)

Figure 14 Thermal conductivity of sodium dodecyl sulphate (SDS) solution as a function of temperature. (Mingzheng et al., 2012)

Figure 15: thermal conductivity of polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP) solution as a function of temperature. (Mingzheng et al., 2012)

Figure 16 Depicts the thermal conductivity of sodium dodecylbenzenesulfonate (SDBS) solution as a function of temperature. (Mingzheng et al., 2012)

Figure 17 thermal conductivity of water as a function of temperature. (Mingzheng et al., 2012)

The thermal conductivities of Polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP), sodium dodecylbenzene sulfonate (SDBS), sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS), and cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB) solutions all increase as temperature rises, but the extent of this enhancement varies with the type of surfactant. Ionic surfactants—SDBS, SDS, and CTAB—are notably more responsive to temperature changes than the non-ionic PVP. Among these, SDS consistently exhibits the highest thermal conductivity across the temperature range studied. Surfactant solutions demonstrate a greater improvement in thermal conductivity with increasing temperature compared to pure deionized water. The thermal conductivity versus temperature graphs for surfactant solutions presented in the referenced sources were generated using a surfactant concentration of 1.0 wt %. This concentration was selected for the initial investigation because, at this level, the thermal conductivity of the surfactant solutions is observed to remain consistent.

2.12 Effect of Surfactants on Critical Heat Flux and heat transfer coefficient

Boiling plays a role in transferring heat and is vital in numerous industrial operations. The use of surfactants as additives to enhance heat transfer has resulted in increased heat flux at the surface. (Acharya and Pise, 2017; Garimella et al., 2008; Shiferaw et al., 2007). Many strategies have been employed to enhance the efficiency of boiling, such as surface modification; however, these methods may become expensive when scaled up. A cost-effective alternative is the addition of a small number of surfactants to the base fluid. The addition of surfactants could increase the heat transfer coefficient by 10-1000%. However, its effectiveness is influenced by several factors, including its type and concentration. (Kumar et al., 2018)

Figure 18 Demonstrates the boiling curve of pure water

Figure 18 Shows the boiling pattern of water at atmospheric pressure by plotting the heat flux against the excess temperature, which is the temperature difference between the hot surface and fluid temperatures. The curve is divided into four sections: the natural convection zone, where the excess temperature remains at or below 5 °C, with heat transfer predominantly through natural convection. Followed by the nucleate boiling area, with excess temperatures

ranging from 5°C to 30°C, where bubbles begin to form and rise as the excess temperature rises. In the transition boiling zone, the excess temperatures range between 30°C and 120°C, where bubbles form quickly and a vapour film develops, acting as a heat transfer barrier. Film boiling zone occurs once excess temperatures exceed 120°C, in which a vapour film forms and separates the liquid from the hot surface.. (Forsberg, 2021)

The vapour layer formed during the film boiling stage acts as an insulation layer, preventing direct contact between the hot surface and the fluid, which results in reduced heat transfer, causing a lowering of the critical heat flux and the heat transfer coefficient. By adding surfactants to the boiling fluid, an enhancement of the critical heat flux was achieved, along with an improvement in the wettability of the cooling fluid. Chakraborty found that by adding Tween-20 as a non-ionic surfactant in spray cooling applications, the cooling speed is boosted by 25.6% and the critical heat flux is increased by 19.91%. However, Jha found that increasing the surfactant concentration decreases the cooling speed. Sakar and his associates found that a mixture of surfactants could cause ultrafast cooling. Data from boiling curves showed that the critical heat flux could reach 500 kW/m² by using certain surfactants, which is approximately 2.4 times the critical heat flux of deionised water, and the heat transfer coefficient increased to 36 kW/m² · K. (Acharya and Pise, 2017; Gouda et al., 2020; Mata et al., 2022; Tian et al., 2021, 2019).

Much Research focused on Sodium Dodecyl Sulfate (SDS). Studies have shown that as the concentration of SDS increases gradually, the Heat Transfer Coefficient (HTC) also improves and reaches its peak at around 2500 ppm, which corresponds to the Critical Micelle Concentration (CMC) for SDS. Tzans studied Sodium Lauryl Sulfate (SLS) on Pool Boiling Heat Transfer (PBHT), revealing a similar enhancement in HTC. Analyses conducted by Wasekar and Hormozi demonstrated that anionic surfactants generally perform better than

nonionic surfactants in the enhancement of heat transfer. (Sarafraz and Hormozi, 2015; Tzan and Yang, 1990; Wasekar and Manglik, 2000)

Tzan studied how Sodium Lauryl Sulfate (SLS) affects the heat transfer of n-propanol water blends. His research stated that even at low concentrations of SLS. It enhances the Heat Transfer Coefficient (HTC). He also conducted experiments on nucleate boiling using aqueous solutions of Sodium Lauryl Sulfate (SLS) with different concentrations and heat fluxes in a pool boiling setup; the results showed that even a small amount of the surfactant significantly increased the nucleate boiling heat transfer coefficient. He also identified an optimal concentration of the additive for achieving higher heat fluxes. Further increases in concentration led to a decline in HTC. (Acharya and Pise, 2017; Tzan and Yang, 1990)

Figure 19 Heat flux vs wall superheat of Deionised water with and without SLS. (Etedali et al., 2019)

Figure 19 Shows a graph plotting heat flux against wall superheat for DI water and SLS surfactant solution. The graph shows that the curve representing the heat transfer coefficient for the DI water-surfactant mixture is shifted to the left, indicating a higher Boiling Heat Transfer Coefficient (BHTC) compared to pure DI water. The addition of surfactant has reduced surface tension, thereby enhancing heat transfer. (Etedali et al., 2019)

Ammerman conducted experiments to assess the impact of an SDS solution with concentrations ranging from 300 to 1000 ppm on pool boiling performance, utilising an electrically heated platinum wire. He observed an improved heat transfer coefficient (HTC), which correlated with the concentration of SDS. Also, Wu discovered that an SDS aqueous solution enhanced HTC when applied to a cylindrical heater. He also noted that the solution initiated boiling earlier than the water. (Ammerman and You, 1996; Wu et al., 1998)

According to Wasekar's findings, experiments using a heater with SDS solutions revealed a significant rise in the heat transfer coefficient (HTC) around the Critical Micelle Concentration (CMC), which was approximately 2500 ppm. However, as the surfactant concentration increases, the HTC begins to decline. Anionic surfactants, like SLES and sodium dodecylbenzenesulfonate (SDBS), have also been utilised for improving pool boiling performance. In their study, they examined the heat transfer effects using a biosurfactant called Rhamnolipids on a copper surface. Goud discovered a significant improvement in the Heat Transfer Coefficient (HTC). It occurred when the Critical Micelle Concentration (CMC) resulted in a 25% decrease in Critical Heat Flux (CHF). At this point, the HTC remained consistent at the concentrations. (Elghanam et al., 2011; Flengas and Rideal, 1959; Gouda et al., 2020; Jia et al., 2021; Wang et al., 2016, 2015; Wasekar and Manglik, 1999; Wen et al., 2022; Yin et al., 2020)

2.13 Mechanism Of Boiling Heat Transfer Enhancement by Surfactants

Surfactants are quite effective in enhancing heat transfer during boiling, as they prevent bubbles from merging and create spots where bubbles can form, allowing them to detach from the surface more easily. Several research studies have demonstrated improvements in heat transfer coefficients (HTC). The maximum heat flux attainable when surfactants are introduced to lower surface tension is enhanced by the surfactants, improving the cooling fluid's ability to spread efficiently on surfaces. Studies have shown that surfactants play a role in improving the boiling process and reducing the formation of vapour films.(Sinha et al., 2023)

The exact mechanisms of how surfactants promote heat transfer are not entirely understood, but it is clear that lowering the surface tension modifies the boiling dynamics.(Acharya and Pise, 2017). Boiling represents an efficient mode of heat transfer, capable of transferring significant amounts of energy through bubble formation. Its application is crucial in many fields. The complex dynamics of bubble behaviour and other related phenomena during boiling remain partially understood. The knowledge on optimising these complex processes is even more limited, typically assessed by the heat transfer coefficient (HTC). (Kandlikar and Alves, 1999; Mata et al., 2022; Wasekar and Manglik, 1999)

$$q = HTC * \Delta T \quad 2-3$$

The q stands for the heat flux during boiling, and ΔT represents the wall superheat, which is the difference between the temperature of the heating surface (T_s) and the saturation temperature (T_{sat}). Adding surfactants is the most cost-effective method of enhancing the pool boiling by decreasing the surface tension, which modifies interfacial behaviours. In instances, adding surfactants to boiling water has increased heat transfer coefficients by 10 to 1000%. The impact of surfactants can. It may hinder heat transfer based on the type and amount used.

Numerous studies on heat transfer in nucleate pool boiling using surfactant solutions and polymers have revealed a surfactant concentration that corresponds to the critical micelle concentration (CMC), resulting in enhanced heat fluxes. This confirms that even small amounts of surfactant additives can greatly enhance boiling heat transfer. (Acharya and Pise, 2017; Ammerman and You, 1996)

Figure 20: Determination of boiling enhancement with surfactants using the relative heat transfer coefficient. (Mata et al., 2022)

The relative heat transfer coefficient (RHTC)

$$RHTC = \frac{HTC_{surfactant}}{HTC_{water}} = \frac{\Delta T_{water}}{\Delta T_{surfactant}} \quad 2-4$$

an example for equation 2-4 is a baseline measurement with plain water yielded a Heat Transfer Coefficient (HTC_{water}) of $1500 \text{ W/m}^2 \cdot \text{K}$, with an observed average temperature difference (ΔT_{water}) between the heating surface and the water of $10 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. For comparison, when a

surfactant-enhanced fluid was introduced, the Heat Transfer Coefficient (HTC surfactant) increased to $1800\text{W/m}^2\cdot\text{K}$, and the corresponding average temperature difference (ΔT surfactant) was recorded as $8.33\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. Figure 20 Determination of boiling enhancement with surfactants using the relative heat transfer coefficient. (Mata et al., 2022). The figure illustrates the amount of surfactant required to enhance boiling efficiency. The boiling efficiency is measured using a Relative Heat Transfer Coefficient (RHTC). The RHTC is calculated by dividing the Heat Transfer Coefficient (HTC) of a solution with surfactants by the HTC of pure water at the same heat input. Researchers compared the effectiveness of heat transfer when surfactants are used versus when only pure water is used. If the RHTC is greater than 1, it indicates that the surfactant enhances boiling performance.

The study results indicate that when surfactants are added to water, the boiling curve shifts, and a lower excess temperature ($T_w - T_{\text{sat}}$) is required for boiling. Therefore, increasing surfactant levels in boiling liquids improves heat transfer at wall superheats, thus optimising the Heat Transfer Coefficient (HTC). An excessive number of surfactants reduces the HTC. This pattern of HTC improvement followed by reduction is known in all surfactants regardless of their classification category. What would be the surfactant concentration? Studies have indicated that the optimal concentration of surfactant may depend on its Critical Micelle Concentration (CMC) and the type of surfactant. The CMC can differ notably from 10^{-8} , to 10^2 mol/m^3 based on the surfactant being used. Numerous research studies utilise surfactants with micelle concentrations (CMCs) ranging from 0.1 to 10 mol/m^3 , focusing on a single type of surfactant. (Acharya and Pise, 2017)

Mata suggested that the improvement in Heat Transfer Coefficient (HTC) is determined by the surfactant's dynamic adsorption, which is the number of surfactants capable of adhering to the surface within a specific time frame, estimated to be around 20 milliseconds.

During a brief interval, surfactants transition from the bulk solution to the interface, a behaviour observed regardless of the surfactant nature. (Mata et al., 2022). Adding anionic surfactants, such as sodium dodecyl sulphate and sodium lauryl sulfate, has been observed to enhance convection and reduce latent heat during boiling processes. Negative ions contribute to this effect. Cationic surfactants, such as Habon G, influence boiling through interactions. Nonionic surfactants, such as alkyl polyglucoside, are preferred for their eco-friendly characteristics. (Mata et al., 2022)

2.14 Silicone Surfactants

The general structure for silicone surfactants is $(\text{CH}_3)_3\text{Si}-\text{O}-[\text{Si}(\text{CH}_3)_2-\text{O}]_n-\text{Si}(\text{CH}_3)_2-\text{R}-$ (Hydrophilic group). Silicone term is used to describe polymers containing silicon and oxygen atoms with diverse components directly attached to silicon atoms. This definition, however, does not accurately describe organosilicon polymers, such as polycarbosilanes, polysilanes, and polysilazanes, as well as polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) and other polysiloxanes, including fluorosilicones and hydrolysed silane coupling agents. PDMS is known for its hydrophilic character and surface energy, which differ significantly from those of hydrocarbons, such as paraffin wax, and play a significant role in the silicone industry, both past and present. Silicone surfactant molecular structures have a hydrophobic silicone component and various hydrophilic segments. The silicone section can vary from a simple linear structure to a complex branched network. Different hydrophilic groups, including non-ionic (such as polyether and sugars) and ionic (comprising cationic, anionic, and zwitterionic types), can be linked to siloxanes through diverse bonding arrangements.

Silicone surfactants contain a polyether group, often in the form of ethylene oxide (PEO). Polypropylene oxide (PPO) is utilised in some silicone surfactants for applications in nonaqueous solutions due to its hydrophobic nature. Research has also explored silicones

featuring hydrophilic carbohydrate moieties and phosphine oxides as alternative hydrophilic groups. Silicone surfactants containing various hydrophilic groups, including anionic and cationic components, have been developed and studied. However, nonionic silicone surfactants based on polyether are more readily available on the market. The behaviour of PDMS in water as a wetting agent has been extensively studied, resulting in a range of contact angles between 95° and 120° . The contact angle of water on PDMS varies, with values ranging from 101° to 120° , due to variations in water purity, surface roughness, and measurement methods. The surface tension of polymers typically changes linearly with temperature, with PDMS having the lowest reported surface tension among these compounds.

Silicone heat transfer fluids are silicone-based compounds, while hydrocarbon organic heat transfer substances are carbon-based compounds. Carbon has six electrons in its outer shell, with two electron layers outside the nucleus and four valence electrons, allowing it to form covalent bonds with itself or other atoms. However, silicone-based heat transfer fluids, such as polydimethylsiloxane, are also used. Its low viscosity allows for smooth pipeline flow and enhances pumping efficiency, particularly in cold situations. Polydimethylsiloxane belongs to a group of chemical compounds known as polymers, characterised by methyl groups attached to the silicon atoms. The viscosity and density of these polymers depend on the degree of polymerisation. Linear polyorganosiloxane has a density around 0.9 g/cm^3 at 25°C , kinematic viscosities ranging from 4 to $50 \text{ mm}^2/\text{s}$, a flashpoint between $140\text{-}150^\circ\text{C}$, a spontaneous ignition point within the range of $350\text{-}400^\circ\text{C}$, and a freezing point below -55°C .

The energy needed to break the carbon-carbon bond is 328 kilojoules (kJ), while the silicon-oxygen bond energy is approximately 452 kJ. The wide angle of the silicon-oxygen bond allows for molecular rotation, resulting in chain formations of polyorganosiloxane molecules. Side groups, such as methyl with Si-C bonds, contribute to the stability of polyorganosiloxane materials compared to hydrocarbon-based heat carriers.

Organic heat transfer fluids are commonly categorised into two groups: hydrocarbon-based organics and polyorganosiloxane. Petroleum-derived hydrocarbon heat transfer fluids exhibit varying chain lengths and structures, including alkenes, aromatics, and cycloalkanes.

The Dow Siloxane Polymer HTF SYLTHERM XLT Heat Transfer Fluid is a specially formulated silicone polymer renowned for its exceptional low-temperature heat transfer and pumping properties. This fluid is used as a medium for heat transfer applications that need lower working temperatures.

According to the product data sheet, the maximum operational temperature for this polymer is stated as 260 °C, making it suitable for both heating and cooling purposes. The recommended working temperature range of -100 to +260°C makes it suitable for heating and cooling applications, mainly in domestic settings.

Polydimethylsiloxane heat transfer fluids exhibit unique characteristics due to their composition, distinguishing them from materials like mineral oils and aromatic fluids when exposed to temperatures exceeding 200 °C in a controlled setting without reaction.

2.15 Summary

Nanofluids are advanced heat transfer fluids created by dispersing nanoparticles into conventional base fluids, such as water or ethylene glycol. Because they significantly enhance thermal conductivity, these fluids are interesting for applications in nuclear reactors, solar energy systems, and electronics cooling. Their general acceptance is limited due to issues with long-term performance, cost, and particle stability.

While the one-step method offers greater stability and smaller particle sizes, the two-step method is more cost-effective and appropriate for bulk production.

Stability determines whether nanofluids maintain their thermal performance or not. The DLVO theory balances attractive van der Waals forces against repulsive electrostatic forces to explain the stability of nanofluids.

Surfactants help to improve the thermophysical properties of the base fluid and concurrently raise nanofluid stability. Surfactants reduce surface tension and alter boiling behaviour, so improving heat transfer. These characteristics make the use of nanofluid and surfactant solutions promising for heat transfer applications.

2.16 References chapter 1&2

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Chapter 3

Methodology Materials & Methods

Materials and components used in the research were gathered in this chapter as a reference for anyone who wants to repeat the experiment

3.1 Graphite

Figure 21 Graphite used for graphene oxide manufacturing (Graphit Kropfmühl GmbH)

Graphite is a naturally occurring allotrope of carbon. It is often mined and processed into different forms for different applications. Synthetic graphite could also be produced industrially. The unique property of graphite stems from its crystal structure, which consists of a stack of layers of carbon atoms arranged in hexagonal rings. The layers are held together by van der Waals forces, allowing them to slide past each other. This stacked layer structure gives graphite its slippery feel, softness, and lubricating properties. Graphite is very stable chemically and has a high melting point. It is a good electrical conductor and also a good heat conductor. This is due to the delocalised electrons in its crystalline structure. Micrometre-sized grains of graphite with high purity were used in the experiments. Graphite powder was used to prepare graphene oxide and graphene nanoparticles as the first step. Then, the graphene oxide nanofluid was prepared by dissolving the graphene oxide nanoparticles in water.

Graphite source.

Company: Graphit Kropfmühl GmbH

Email: info@gk-graphite.com

Homepage: <http://www.gk-graphite.com>

3.2 Silica, Alumina and Titania Nanoparticles

Figure 22 shows the C, silica, B, alumina, and A, titania nano powders, respectively.

Silica Nanoparticles (Silicon Dioxide Nanoparticles)

Silica nanoparticles, also known as silicon dioxide nanoparticles, are spherical nanomaterials composed of silicon and oxygen atoms. Silica has high chemical, mechanical, and thermal stability

Alumina Nanoparticles (Aluminium Oxide Nanoparticles)

Alumina nanoparticles, or aluminium oxide nanoparticles, are typically spherical or irregular in shape and are composed of aluminium and oxygen atoms. They exhibit high thermal stability, mechanical strength, and chemical resistance.

Titania Nanoparticles (Titanium Dioxide Nanoparticles)

Titania nanoparticles, or titanium dioxide nanoparticles, are spherical or irregular in shape and are composed of titanium and oxygen atoms. They possess unique properties such as high photocatalytic activity and chemical stability. Titania nanoparticles are widely used as pigments in paints, coatings, and cosmetics due to their high refractive index and UV-blocking properties. They are commonly used in photocatalytic applications, such as water treatment, air purification, and self-cleaning surfaces, as well as in electronics, including dye-sensitised solar cells and lithium-ion batteries.

Source of alumina, silica and titania nano powder

Suoyi group (hq)

Hebei Suoyi New Material Technology Co., Ltd | export <https://hbsuoyi.en.made-in-china.com/>

Shop: www.hbsuoyi.en.alibaba.com

Email: sales611@hbsuoyi.com

3.3 Alkyl Polyglycoside (APG)

3.3.1 Simulso SL 11 W

SIMULSOLTM SL 11 W is an alkyl polyglucoside, non-ionic surfactant made from glucose C11 alcohol. It is considered safe for both people and the environment. This product is utilised

in various industries, including cleaning products, oilfield operations, agriculture, and firefighting. It is environmentally friendly. (“Home page | SEPPIC,”)

3.3.2 Simulsol SL 4

SIMULSOL™ SL 4 is an alkyl polyglucoside non-ionic surfactant made from glucose and alcohol. It does not contain harmful chemicals. It is an effective viscosity reducer in formulations that contain surfactants. This surfactant helps make liquids thinner and is used in various industries, including farming, cleaning, and oilfield operations. SIMULSOL™ SL 4 demonstrates excellent performance, making it a preferred choice for formulators seeking eco-friendly surfactants with high efficacy. Its ability to reduce viscosity in surfactant-based formulations makes it a valuable additive in a range of products. (“Home page | SEPPIC,”)

Source of the APG surfactants:

Seppic Inc. <https://www.seppic.com/en/simulsol-sl-11-w>.
<https://www.seppic.com/en/simulsol-sl-4>

3.4 Silicone Surfactants

Figure 23: Generalized Structure of the silicone surfactant molecule.

Silsurf is a silicone surfactant that is readily dispersible in water. It helps reduce surface tension and improve wetting. This surfactant is made of a silicone base with hydrophilic polyether side chains. Siltech offers a wide range of silicone surfactants. These surfactants are used in many products as emulsifiers, foam boosters, solubilisers, and conditioners.

3.4.1 Silicone surfactant; Silsurf A008

Silsurf A008 is a monofunctional, water-miscible silicone surfactant. It is a low-molecular-weight ethoxylated polydimethylsiloxane. This surfactant is renowned for its exceptional ability to reduce surface tension and enhance wetting. Adding 0.01% Silsurf A008 can lower the surface tension of water to the range of 20-22 mN/m. It has the remarkable capability to cover or wet almost all types of surfaces. The contact angles are close to 0°, and this effect continues until water evaporates. Very few surfactants, excluding those with fluoroalkyl components, can achieve such remarkable effects.

3.4.2 Silicone surfactant; Silsurf A004

Silsurf A004 is a small-molecular-weight ethoxylated polydimethylsiloxane, characterised as a low-foaming silicone surfactant. Silsurf A004 exhibits superior wetting and distribution properties, making it advantageous in applications that require expedited saturation. At a concentration of merely 0.1%, Silsurf A004 diminishes water surface tension to 20.0-21.0 dynes/cm.

Source of silicone surfactants.

SILTECH CORPORATION. 225 Wicksteed Avenue. Toronto, Ontario, Canada, M4H 1G5

3.5 Electronic Components

3.5.1 Platinum Wire

Figure 24: The platinum wire 75 micrometre in diameter

Platinum (Pt) wire is the preferred material for the heating element in transient hot-wire (THW) sensors. Platinum has a very high melting point, around 1769°C (3217°F). This ensures the wire can withstand the high temperatures encountered during sensor operation without melting or deteriorating. Additionally, Platinum exhibits a predictable and well-characterised electrical resistance that increases with temperature. This property allows the THW sensor to monitor temperature changes by monitoring the change in resistance of the Pt wire as it heats up. In addition, Platinum is highly resistant to corrosion and oxidation, even at elevated temperatures. This ensures the wire maintains its properties and provides reliable measures over time. Platinum has good thermal conductivity. This allows the wire to transfer heat efficiently to the surrounding fluid, improving the sensor's response time. The diameter of the Pt wire used in THW sensors is typically very thin, 0.75 mm. This small diameter minimises the mass of the wire, allowing for faster heating and cooling, which improves sensor responsiveness. The length of the wire is typically chosen based on the specific application and desired sensitivity.

Advent Research Materials Ltd. Oakfield Industrial Estate. Eynsham. Oxford. England. OX29 4JA. General enquiries: info@advent-rm.com, technical enquiries: chris@advent-rm.com

<https://www.advent-rm.com/en-GB/Products/Pure-Metals/Platinum/Form/Wire>

3.5.2 Printed circuit boards PCBs

PCBWay is a company that specialises in the manufacturing of printed circuit boards (PCBs) and related services. The company offers a wide range of PCB manufacturing capabilities.

Website;

<https://www.pcbway.com/orderonline.aspx>

3.6 Power Supply Breakout Boards

3.6.1 HW-140 DC-DC Buck Boost Power Converter

Figure 25 DC-DC Buck-Boost Power Converter

AZDelivery HW-140 DC-DC Buck Boost Power Converter, Automatic Step Up/Down Voltage Converter, Volt and Ampere Meter Display, compatible with Arduino

A buck-boost converter is a versatile type of DC-to-DC converter that can take a DC input voltage and convert it to a DC output voltage that is either higher or lower than the input voltage. It typically uses a combination of inductors, capacitors, transistors (or switches), and

diodes to regulate the output voltage. The converter operates in two distinct modes, depending on the desired output voltage.

Buck Mode (Step-Down): When the output voltage needs to be lower than the input voltage, the converter operates similarly to a buck converter. Energy is stored in the inductor during a switching phase and then released to the output through a diode.

Boost Mode (Step-Up): When the output voltage needs to be higher than the input voltage, the converter operates differently. Energy is transferred from the input to the inductor during one switching phase and then boosted to a higher voltage during another switching phase, using the stored energy in the inductor and capacitor. They are commonly used in portable electronics, such as laptops and tablets, to regulate voltage from batteries that can discharge and provide a stable voltage for various components. The source of the buck-boost converter was the company's Amazon store. Gesetzliche Anbieterkennung: AZ-Delivery Betriebs GmbH. Laerchenstrasse 10. 94469 Deggendorf. vertreten durch den Geschäftsführer Malte Horeysek

E-Mail: info@az-delivery.com

3.6.2 DC-DC Positive & Negative Voltage Boost-Buck Converter

Output $\pm 5V$ 6V 9V 10V 12V 15V 18V

Figure 26 to $\pm 10V$ Boost-Buck Dual Voltage Power Supply

The 8W 3-24V to $\pm 10V$ Boost-Buck Dual Voltage Power Supply is a small, lightweight power supply module that provides both positive and negative voltages. It can work with a wide range of input voltages (3- 24V DC) and converts them to a dual output voltage ($\pm 10V$ DC). This module is ideal for low-power applications, as it can deliver up to 8 watts of power. It is also easy to use in different electronic projects due to its compact size and lightweight design.

Source.

Business Name: Chengdushi zhiliweichuang kejiyouxian gongsi

3.7 Raspberry Pi

Figure 27: Raspberry Pi

The Raspberry Pi is a small computer, approximately the size of a credit card, originally designed to teach computer science concepts to students and adults worldwide. Introduced in 2012 by the British Raspberry Pi Foundation, its main goal was to encourage learning about basic electronics, programming, and DIY projects through an affordable, open-source computing platform. Equipped with a quad-core ARM Cortex CPU, ample RAM, HDMI, USB, WiFi, Bluetooth, and Ethernet connectivity, the Raspberry Pi offers impressive performance comparable to traditional desktop computers. Despite its small size and simple plastic casing, this device is incredibly adaptable. When paired with an affordable monitor, keyboard, and mouse, the Raspberry Pi transforms into a complete personal computer. Source, <https://thepihut.com/collections/raspberry-pi>
<https://shop.pimoroni.com/collections/raspberry-pi>

3.8 Analogue To Digital Converters

3.8.1 ADS1115

Figure 28 ADS 1115 analogue to digital converter

<https://learn.adafruit.com/raspberry-pi-analog-to-digital-converters/ads1015-slash-ads1115>

The Texas Instruments ADS1115 is a sophisticated 16-bit analogue-to-digital converter (ADC) specially designed for precision in a wide range of applications. It is equipped with advanced features, including a four-channel input multiplexer, programmable gain amplifier (PGA), and integrated functions such as an internal oscillator, temperature sensor, and comparator. This ADC communicates via I²C or SPI interfaces, making it ideal for use in data acquisition systems, scientific instruments, and sensor arrays.

With up to 16-bit resolution, ADS1115 allows for highly accurate measurement of analogue signals. It offers programmable gain amplifiers that enable users to adjust gain levels according to the input signal ranges. The four-channel input multiplexer permits the connection and selection of up to four separate analogue signals for measurement. Additionally, the ADC features programmable comparators that allow for setting thresholds to trigger events based on signal levels. The device supports sequencer and chainable conversions to streamline the data acquisition process.

Operating on a power supply range of 2.048V to 5.5V with low power consumption, the ADS1115 is suitable for portable and battery-powered applications. Its operational temperature range of -40°C to $+85^{\circ}\text{C}$ ensures consistent performance in a wide range of environments. The device is designed to ensure accurate and stable analogue-to-digital conversion.

3.8.2 ADS1263

Figure 29 ADS 1263 analogue to digital converter

https://www.waveshare.com/wiki/High-Precision_AD_HAT

The Texas Instruments ADS1263 is a cutting-edge 32-bit, 10-channel analogue-to-digital converter (ADC) chip crafted for applications that require precision and ultrasonic frequency capabilities. Known for its exceptional noise reduction, minimal offset drift, and impressive total harmonic distortion metrics, the ADS1263 is regarded as a pinnacle in modern electronic data acquisition technology. With up to 32-bit resolution, this device enables accurate measurement of analogue signals, supported by a maximum sampling rate of 38.4 kSPS, making it well-suited for broadband applications. Featuring 10 input channels, including 5 supporting differential input,

The ADS1263 features a delta-sigma architecture, providing low noise and temperature drift, which ensures precise analogue-to-digital conversion. It supports up to 32x programmable gain amplification, allowing users to adjust gain levels according to the input signal range. Compatible with both single-ended and differential analogue input types within a voltage range of -2.5V to 5V, the ADS1263 communicates via an SPI interface for streamlined integration with digital systems. Operating reliably in various environments, it supports an operational temperature range of -40°C to +125°C.

3.8.3 Amplifier INA 131

Figure 30 shows the instrumental amplifier INA131, specifically designed for precision and low-power applications.

From Texas Instruments (<https://www.ti.com/>), the INA131 is an advanced instrumentation amplifier manufactured by Texas Instruments. It is specifically engineered for precision, low-power applications, such as medical equipment, industrial process control, and data acquisition systems. This device is characterised by a fixed gain of 100 and provides very low offset voltage, high common-mode rejection ratio, and minimal quiescent current.

With a fixed gain of 100 established by a single external resistor, the INA131 ensures straightforward adjustment. It delivers exceptional accuracy and stability in analogue

measurements with its very low offset voltage (maximum of 25 μV) (The offset voltage refers to the small, unwanted voltage that exists at the output of an operational amplifier (op-amp) or instrumentation amplifier when the input voltage is zero). The amplifier's high CMRR (minimum of 100 dB at a gain of 100) effectively eliminates common-mode noise, guaranteeing high-quality signal transmission. Operating on single supplies as low as $\pm 2.25\text{V}$, the INA131 offers flexibility in power supply selection. Packaged in compact SOIC-8 and MSOP-8 formats (packaging format). With the ability to handle common-mode voltages up to $\pm 200\text{V}$, the INA131 ensures reliable performance.

3.9 Oscilloscope And Power Supply

Figure 31: Tektronix TBS1052C, 2 Channel Bench Digital Storage Oscilloscope, 150MHz

The Tektronix TBS1052C represents a digital storage oscilloscope (DSO) engineered for the evaluation and resolution of electronic circuits and systems. This oscilloscope boasts a bandwidth of 150 MHz and a peak sample rate of 1 GS/s, ensuring precise and detailed signal capture and presentation.

The Tektronix TBS1052C is ideal for a diverse range of applications, including electronic circuit testing and troubleshooting, signal analysis and characterisation, electronic system design and development, educational purposes, as well as industrial process control and automation. RS Components, <https://uk.rs-online.com/web/>

3.10 Marvel Zetaseizer

Figure 32 shows the Zetaseizer instrument.

<https://www.malvernpanalytical.com/en/support/product-support/zetasizer-range/zetasizer-nano-range/zetasizer-nano-zs#manuals>

The Malvern Panalytical Zetasizer Nano ZS is well-suited for diverse applications, especially in characterising nanomaterials, polymers, and colloidal suspensions for industrial applications. By enabling measurements of zeta potential and particle size, the Zetasizer Nano ZS emerges as a solution for many applications. The instrument accurately assesses particle size distribution, delivering precise data on particle dimensions. Utilising DLS, researchers can determine particle sizes in colloidal suspensions, facilitating the study of aggregation and colloidal stability. The ELS technique facilitates the measurement of particle zeta potential, a crucial parameter for understanding particle-particle and particle-surface interactions.

3.11 The room simulation Box and The Fluid Circulator

Figure 33 shows the wooden box.

Figure 34 shows the wooden box connected to the fluid circulator.

The box, constructed from wood and measuring 50 cm x 50 cm x 50 cm, is insulated internally with polystyrene and contains a small radiation coil within it. The coil has a total length of 3

meters and an outer diameter of 0.5 cm for its tube. To monitor temperature changes, sensors have been placed inside the box and linked to a National Instruments temperature logger, which facilitates a computer interface. Temperature readings were recorded at one-minute intervals. A copper radiator, connected to a fluid circulator, ensures fluid circulation at the desired temperature. Initially, the temperature was set at 10 degrees, then increased to 65 degrees, and the temperature log was recorded for approximately 1.5 hours. Subsequently, the curve was plotted. The LKB Bromma 2219 Multitemp II Thermostatic Circulator is a high-performance temperature control system designed for laboratory applications, providing precise and stable temperature management. The actual size and the result diagrams are explained in more detail in Chapter 6.

Figure 35: Example of obtained data from the wooden box

3.12 Pycnometer

Figure 35 shows the density pycnometer.

Density Measurement Using a Pycnometer

A pycnometer is a precision laboratory instrument designed to measure the density of solids, liquids, and powdered materials with high accuracy. It is widely used in research, quality control, and industrial settings due to its precision and versatility. They are available in various sizes and designs to accommodate different materials. To ensure accurate results, it is essential to use a high-precision balance, maintain consistent temperature conditions, and follow procedures such as eliminating air bubbles and ensuring complete drying between measurements. It consists of a sealed container, usually made of glass, metal, or ceramic, featuring a precisely calibrated volume and a narrow neck for controlled filling and emptying. The device works by comparing the mass of a sample material to that of a reference liquid with a known density, such as water or mercury. This comparative method ensures reliable and repeatable density calculations for various substances.

Calibration and Volume Determination

Before measuring the sample, the pycnometer must first be calibrated to determine its exact volume. This process involves weighing the empty, dry container to establish its baseline mass. The pycnometer is then filled with a reference liquid, typically distilled water, whose density

is known at a specific temperature. After weighing the filled pycnometer, the mass of the liquid alone is calculated by subtracting the mass of the empty container. Using the known density of the reference liquid, the pycnometer volume is precisely determined.

Measuring the Density of Liquids

Once the pycnometer volume is established, the density of a liquid sample can be measured. The container is thoroughly cleaned, dried, and filled with the test liquid, taking care to eliminate air bubbles. The filled pycnometer is weighed again, and the sample mass is determined by subtracting the mass of the empty container. Since the volume is already known, the liquid density is easily calculated using the formula $\text{Density} = \text{Mass} / \text{Volume}$.

The density ρ of a liquid sample using a pycnometer can be calculated using the following equation

$$\rho_{\text{sample}} = \frac{(m_{\text{pyc}+\text{sample}} - m_{\text{pyc}})(m_{\text{pyc}+\text{water}} - m_{\text{pyc}}) \times \rho_{\text{water}}}{((m_{\text{pyc}+\text{water}} - m_{\text{pyc}})(m_{\text{pyc}+\text{sample}} - m_{\text{pyc}}))} \quad 3-1$$

- ρ_{sample} = Density of the sample (g/cm³ or kg/m³)
- $m_{\text{pyc}+\text{sample}}$ = Mass of the pycnometer filled with the sample (g or kg)
- m_{pyc} = Mass of the empty pycnometer (g or kg)
- $m_{\text{pyc}+\text{water}}$ = Mass of the pycnometer filled with water (g or kg)
- ρ_{water} = Density of water at the measurement temperature (typically 0.9982 g/cm³ at 20°C)

Steps to be followed

1. Weigh the empty pycnometer m_{pyc} .
2. Fill it with the sample and weigh again $m_{pyc+ sample}$.
3. Clean and dry the pycnometer, then fill it with water and weigh $m_{pyc+ water}$.
4. Use the 3-1 To calculate the sample's density.

This method relies on the known density of water and the constant volume of the pycnometer.

3.13 Ostwald Viscometer

Figure 36: Ostwald viscometer

The Ostwald viscometer, also known as the Ostwald-Fenske viscometer, is a laboratory instrument used to measure the viscosity of liquids with high precision. The instrument consists of a glass tube with a narrow, calibrated capillary section and two bulbs, one positioned above and the other below the capillary section. The liquid being measured is introduced into the

upper bulb of the viscometer, and the instrument is placed in a temperature-controlled bath to maintain a constant temperature. The liquid is then allowed to flow through the capillary section under the influence of gravity, and the time it takes for the liquid to pass between two marked points on the capillary is measured using a stopwatch or electronic timer.

The viscosity of the liquid is calculated based on the time it takes for the liquid to pass through the capillary section and the dimensions of the capillary, which are precisely known. The Ostwald viscometer is typically calibrated using liquids of known viscosity, and the calibration constants are used to determine the viscosity of the test liquid.

The Ostwald viscometer functions based on Poiseuille's law, which governs the steady flow of viscous liquids through a thin tube. This principle states that the time required for a specific liquid volume to pass through a capillary under gravity is proportional to its viscosity. The relationship can be mathematically represented as $\eta = K \cdot \rho \cdot t$, where η is the dynamic viscosity, K is a constant determined by the viscometer dimensions, ρ is the fluid density, and t is the efflux time (the duration for the liquid to move between two marked points). By measuring the efflux time of an unknown liquid and comparing it to a reference liquid (typically water), its viscosity can be calculated.

The viscometer is structured as a U-shaped glass tube with two bulbs linked by a capillary. Calibration is performed using a standard fluid, such as distilled water, with known viscosity and density.

Measurement Procedure Using the Ostwald Viscometer

The viscosity measurement process with an Ostwald viscometer involves several key steps:

1. Calibration: A standard fluid with known viscosity and density (such as distilled water) is used to determine the instrument's constant (K). The efflux time (t_{std}) of this reference liquid is measured as it flows between two marked points on the viscometer.

2. Filling: The test liquid is carefully introduced into the viscometer, either by pouring or suction, ensuring that no air bubbles are trapped in the capillary or bulbs, as they could disrupt flow measurements.
3. Temperature Control: Since viscosity is highly dependent on temperature, the viscometer is placed in a thermostatic bath to maintain a constant temperature throughout the experiment. This ensures consistent and accurate readings.
4. Timing: The efflux time t_{test} The amount of the test liquid is recorded as it flows between the same two marked points used during calibration. A stopwatch or automated timer is used for precision.
5. Calculation: Using the previously determined constant (K) and the measured efflux times, the dynamic viscosity η_{test} The amount of the test liquid is calculated using the formula:

$$\eta_{test} = \eta_{std} \cdot \left(\frac{\rho_{test}}{\rho_{std}} \right) \cdot \left(\frac{t_{test}}{t_{std}} \right) \quad 3-2$$

η_{std}, ρ_{std} and t_{std} Correspond to the standard fluid, while ρ_{test} and t_{test} The density and efflux time of the test liquid are taken into consideration.

3.14 Summary

Alkyl Polyglycoside (APG) surfactants, such as SIMULSOL™ SL 11 W and SIMULSOL™ SL 4, as well as Silsurf solutions, Graphene oxide, silica, alumina, and titania nanofluids,

provide improved performance, stability, and compatibility for various heat transfer applications.

Platinum wire is the preferred material for the heating element in transient hot-wire (THW) sensors due to its high melting point, predictable electrical resistance, and good thermal conductivity. PCBWay specialises in manufacturing printed circuit boards (PCBs) and related services, offering a wide range of capabilities. The Raspberry Pi is a small computer designed for teaching computer science and programming.

The Texas Instruments ADS1115 is a 16-bit analogue-to-digital converter (ADC) designed for precision in a wide range of applications. The ADS1263 is a 32-bit, 10-channel analogue-to-digital converter chip crafted for applications requiring precision.

The INA131 is an advanced instrumentation amplifier designed for precision and low-power applications, such as medical equipment, industrial process control, and data acquisition systems. The Tektronix TBS1052C is a digital storage oscilloscope (DSO) engineered for the evaluation and resolution of electronic circuits and systems.

The Malvern Panalytical Zetasizer Nano ZS accurately assesses particle size distribution for diverse applications. A pycnometer is a precision laboratory instrument used to measure the density of solids, liquids, and powdered materials with high accuracy.

Chapter 4

3D symmetric turbulent pipe flow

Analysis of nanofluids using Ansys

Fluent

4.1 Introduction

Enhancing the thermal conductivity of fluids to improve the efficiency of thermal systems is crucial and challenging. Nanofluids, as heat transfer fluids, are promising candidates for addressing this challenge. The addition of nanoparticles to the base fluids demonstrated a significant enhancement in the thermal properties of the base fluid, making the nanofluids highly attractive for heat transfer applications, such as electronic cooling, solar energy harvesting, and heating and cooling in industrial and domestic settings.

Current scientific literature focuses on studying the thermophysical properties of nanofluids under laminar flow conditions. The study of the thermal properties and behaviour of many nanofluids under a turbulent flow regime remains an area of research gap. According to the 4-13 According to the Reynolds number, the flow in the pipe used in this research exceeds 10,000, indicating a turbulent flow. As flow in standard heat transfer systems is mainly turbulent, understanding the enhancement of the heat transfer using nanofluids under turbulent flow conditions is crucial.

The addition of nanoparticles to the base fluid will enhance the heat transfer compared to the base fluid alone. The heat transfer enhancement depends on the type of nanoparticles added to the base fluid.

This research aims to investigate the heat transfer characteristics and Nusselt number behaviour of nanofluids under turbulent flow conditions in a small-diameter pipe. Numerical simulations are employed to analyse the effects of nanoparticle type on heat transfer coefficients, Nusselt number, and pressure drop characteristics of nanofluids in turbulent regimes. The study focuses on examining the influence of different types of nanoparticles on heat transfer efficiency under turbulent flow conditions. The findings are expected to enhance our understanding of nanofluid behaviour in turbulent pipe flows.

A CFD (Computational Fluid Dynamics) model, developed using ANSYS Fluent, was created to simulate heat transfer through a pipe under turbulent flow conditions. The CFD analysis focuses on measuring the heat transfer coefficients and Nusselt number of different nanofluid formulations under turbulent flow conditions. Ansys simulation aims to develop and validate a computational fluid dynamics (CFD) model for simulating the temperature drop of nanofluids along a pipe under turbulent flow conditions. The impact of nanoparticle and base fluid type on the heat transfer efficiency in turbulent pipe flow conditions will be investigated. Most previous CFD studies on the heat transfer of nanofluids have focused on laminar flow conditions.

(Poplaski et al., 2017) Demonstrated the significant enhancement of heat transfer using nanofluids under laminar flow. (Kamyar et al., 2012) Investigated the thermal conductivity enhancement in nanofluids using CFD analysis, using conventional numerical methods. (Mahdavi et al., 2016, 2015) Investigated the pressure drop in nanofluids in a vertical tube. (Lima et al., 2023) Investigated the heat transfer of graphene nanoplatelets in a double tube heat exchanger. However, fewer studies have focused on nanofluid heat transfer in turbulent flow conditions within a simple pipe, and only one or two combinations of nanofluids have been investigated. In contrast, this study compares four types of nanoparticles in water and ethylene glycol. This study enriches knowledge by investigating the impact of nanofluids on heat transfer efficiency in turbulent pipe flow conditions. The study utilised CFD to model heat transfer through a copper tube, using water and ethylene glycol as base fluids.

4.2 Geometry and meshing

The nanofluids flows in a pipe of diameter 0.025 m and 1 m length at constant velocities ranging from 0.5 m/s to 2.5 m/s each nanofluid has its calculated density, thermal conductivity, specific heat capacities and viscosity using equations demonstrated in the section 1.3 of

properties of nanofluids with inlet temperature of 80 °C and wall temperature of 24 °C. The reduction in fluid temperature will be monitored in the pipe to indicate the heat absorbed by the fluid, comparing each nanofluid to the others and the base fluid used.

The properties of Water is as flowing, Thermal conductivity 0.663 W/m·K, Specific heat capacity 4190 J/kg·K Viscosity 0.000404 Pa·s (Pascal-seconds), density 0.977 kg/L while Ethylene Glycol Thermal conductivity 0.2522 W/m·K, Specific heat capacity 2628 J/kg·K Viscosity 0.04049 Pa·s (Pascal-seconds), density 1.11 kg/L Inlet temperature: 80 °C, Wall temperature: 24 °C, Tube diameter: 0.025 m.(Das et al., 2006; Elfaghia et al., 2022; Namburu et al., 2007; Waware et al., 2024)

Task Page

Models

Models

- Multiphase - Off
- Energy - On
- Viscous - Standard k-ε, Standard Wall Fn
- Radiation - Off
- Heat Exchanger - Off
- Species - Off
- Discrete Phase - Off
- Solidification & Melting - Off
- Acoustics - Off
- Eulerian Wall Film - Off
- Electric Potential - Off

Edit...

Materials

Materials

- Fluid
- water-liquid
- Solid
- aluminum

Solution Methods

Pressure-Velocity Coupling

Scheme

SIMPLE

Spatial Discretization

Gradient

Least Squares Cell Based

Pressure

Second Order

Momentum

Second Order Upwind

Turbulent Kinetic Energy

Second Order Upwind

Turbulent Dissipation Rate

Second Order Upwind

Transient Formulation

Non-Iterative Time Advancement

Frozen Flux Formulation

Pseudo Transient

Warped-Face Gradient Correction

High Order Term Relaxation Options...

Default

Figure 37 3D one-meter half tube with a diameter of 0.025m, designed using the design modeller from Ansys Fluent with parameters

Figure 38: Meshing layout used in the CFD analysis. The asymmetric plane is located on the y-axis, consisting of 267,253 nodes and 245,310 elements.

4.3 Boundary conditions and governing equations

Both the nanoparticles and the base fluid are considered in thermal equilibrium with the same velocity. In the context of the energy equation, the effects of compression work and viscosity dissipation are considered insignificant. Based on these assumptions, the standard equation is as follows. (Abobaker et al., 2020, 2020; Elfaghi et al., 2010a, 2010a, 2010b; Elfaghia et al., 2022; Sureshkumar et al., 2013; “Effect of particle size on the convective heat transfer in nanofluid in the developing region,” 2009; Wen and Ding, 2004)

Continuity equation:

$$\nabla \cdot (\rho_{nf}V) = 0 \quad 4-1$$

Momentum equation:

$$\nabla \cdot (\rho_{nf}VV) = -\nabla P + \nabla \cdot \tau \quad 4-2$$

Energy equation:

$$\nabla \cdot (\rho_{nf}VC_{p,nf}) = -\nabla \cdot (k_{nf} \nabla T - C_{p,nf} \rho_{nf} \bar{v}t) \quad 4-3$$

4.4 Properties of nanofluids

4.4.1 Volume fraction calculations

The general formula for the volume fraction calculation for nanofluids is (Das et al., 2007) While simple to use, this formula assumes ideal mixing and does not account for potential agglomeration of nanoparticles or changes in volume due to mixing.

$$\phi = \frac{V_{np}}{V_{bf} + V_{np}} \quad 4-4$$

ϕ The volume fraction of nanoparticles in the nanofluid

V_{np} The volume of nanoparticles

V_{bf} The volume of the base fluid

As the formula used volume fraction to substitute volume weight and density could be easier used as the following equation 4-5 to predict the percent volume fraction of the nanoparticles in the base fluid

$$\phi = \left[\frac{\left(\frac{W_{np}}{\rho_{np}}\right)}{\left(\frac{W_{np}}{\rho_{np}} + \frac{W_{bf}}{\rho_{bf}}\right)} \right] \times 100 \quad 4-5$$

To calculate the weight required to achieve the desired volume fraction, the following equation is used.

$$W_{np} = \left(\frac{\phi}{100 - \phi}\right) \left(\frac{\rho_{np}}{\rho_{bf}}\right) W_{bf} \quad 4-6$$

For example, 1 litre (1000 mL) of nanofluid with a 0.1% volume fraction of copper nanoparticles. The density of pure copper is approximately 8.96 g/cm³. Therefore, in 1 litre of nanofluid with a 0.1% volume fraction of copper nanoparticles, you would need approximately 8.96 grams of copper nanoparticles.

The volume fraction is ϕ and V_{bf} is the volume of the base fluid while V_{np} is the volume of the nanoparticles, ρ_{np} (kg/m³) is the density of the nanoparticles, ρ_{bf} (kg/m³) is the density of the base fluid. The specific heat capacity of the nanofluid is denoted by Cp_{nf} (J/kg K) while the base fluid is Cp_{bf} (J/kg.K). The thermal conductivity of the nanofluid is k_{nf} (W/m K),

whereas k_{bf} (W/m K) is that of the base fluid and k_{np} (W/m K) is the thermal conductivity of the nanoparticles. μ_{nf} (Pa s) and μ_{bf} (Pa s) are the viscosity of the nanofluid and the base fluid, respectively

4.4.2 Density calculation

The density of the nanofluids is calculated using 4-7 This formula assumes that the nanofluid behaves as a simple mixture, without considering any complex interactions between the nanoparticles and the base fluid. (Corcione, 2011; Islam et al., 2012; Pak and Cho, 1998; Vajjha and Das, 2009; Xuan and Roetzel, 2000) .

$$\rho_{nf} = \phi * \rho_s + (1 - \phi) * \rho_{bf} \quad 4-7$$

The formula calculates a weighted average of the densities of the nanoparticles and the base fluid, based on their volume fractions. The term $\phi * \rho_s$ Represents the contribution of the nanoparticles to the overall density. The term $(1 - \phi) * \rho_{bf}$ Represents the contribution of the base fluid to the overall density. By adding these two terms, we get the total density of the nanofluid.

4.4.3 Specific heat capacity calculation

The formula calculates the specific heat capacity of the nanofluid by determining the weighted average of the volumetric heat capacities of the base fluid and nanoparticles based on their volume fractions. Dividing this weighted average by the density of the nanofluid (ρ_{nf}) to convert from volumetric heat capacity to specific heat capacity.

The formula assumes that thermal equilibrium is achieved instantaneously between the nanoparticles and the base fluid, and that no chemical reactions or phase changes occur.

(O'Hanley et al., 2015; Sekhar and Sharma, 2013; Zhou and Ni, 2008)

$$(C_p)_{nf} = \frac{((\rho C_p)_{bf} * (1 - \phi) + \phi * (\rho C_p)_s)}{\rho_{nf}} \quad 4-8$$

$$C_{nf} = \frac{\phi \rho_s C_s + (1 - \phi) \rho_{bf} * C_{bf}}{\rho_{nf}} \quad 4-9$$

4.4.4 Thermal conductivity calculation

The equation 4-10 is known as the Maxwell model for the thermal conductivity of nanofluids. It was initially developed by James Clerk Maxwell in 1881 and has been widely adopted in nanofluid research. The equation calculates the effective thermal conductivity, k_{nf} Of a nanofluid. (Achard, 2005; Choi and Eastman, 1995)

The formula takes into account the thermal conductivities of both the base fluid and the nanoparticles, as well as the volume fraction of the nanoparticles. It assumes that the nanoparticles are spherical and that there is no thermal interaction between particles. The equation calculates a weighted average of the thermal conductivities. This model is remarkably accurate for low volume fractions of nanoparticles, typically less than 1%. For higher concentrations or non-spherical particles, more complex models may be necessary.

$$k_{nf} = \left(\frac{(k_s + 2k_f) - 2\phi(k_f - k_s)}{(k_s + 2k_f) + \phi(k_f - k_s)} \right) * k_f \quad 4-10$$

4.4.5 Kinematic viscosity calculation

Viscosity is a crucial property of fluids, particularly in the context of nanofluid research. It affects the heat transfer and the pumping power. Accurate predictions of viscosity are crucial for real-world applications. Einstein's work forms the basis for this equation, 4-11, where the viscosity of the fluid is directly related to the concentration of nanoparticles. Batchelor built on this idea and showed that it also applies to other types of nanofluids. However, this equation assumes that the nanoparticles are spherical and does not account for interparticle interactions. This is only true for fluids with low concentrations of solute. 4-11 estimates the effective viscosity μ_{nf} of a nanofluid. This formula is known as the Einstein-Batchelor model for the viscosity of nanofluids. It is an extension of Einstein's original work on the viscosity of dilute suspensions. (Batchelor, 1977)

$$\mu_{nf} = \frac{\mu_f}{(1 - \phi)^{2.5}} \quad 4-11$$

4.4.6 Tables of thermophysical properties of nanofluids

The thermophysical properties of the nanofluids were calculated using the previous equations and collected in the following tables to be inserted in the ANSYS Fluent software for the CFD analysis

Table 1 Thermophysical properties of the nanoparticles used to prepare the nanofluids

	Silica	Alumina	titania	Graphene oxide
Density kg/m ³	2200	3970	4170	121
Specific heat J/kg·K	745	775	711	2100
Thermal conductivity W/m·K	1.4	39	11.8	2720

Table 1 The thermophysical characteristics of solid nanoparticles are utilised to determine the properties of nanofluids with a volume concentration of 0.1%.

Table 2 Result of the calculations of the thermophysical properties of the nanofluids using the previous equations, considering the base fluid is Ethylene Glycol

	Alumina 0.1 % volume fraction	Titania 0.1 % volume fraction	Silica 0.1 % volume fraction	Graphene oxide 0.1 % volume fraction
volume fraction $\phi =$	0.1005537	0.106361572	0.105842401	0.100807367
Nanofluid density $\rho_{nf} =$	1397.583581	1435.46641	1225.368217	1010.301514
Specific heat capacity of nanofluid $Cp_{nf} =$	2098.719139	4198.535933	2270.178797	2621.625288
thermal conductivity of nanofluid $k_{nf} =$	0.334986942	0.336099853	0.303753935	0.336995251
Viscosity of nanofluid $\mu_{nf} =$	0.052772744	0.05363437	0.05355655	0.052809971
weight of nanoparticles in Kg	0.0036	0.004	0.0021	0.00011

Table 3 1 result of the calculations of the thermophysical properties of the nanofluids using the previous equations, considering that the base fluid is water

	Alumina 0.1 % volume fraction	Titania 0.1 % volume fraction	Silica 0.1 % volume fraction	Graphene oxide 0.1 % volume fraction
volume fraction $\phi =$	0.105709296	0.100644408	0.102036688	0.104856877
Nanofluid density $\rho_{nf} =$	1293.387923	1298.357596	1101.790869	887.2425132

Specific heat capacity of nanofluid $Cp_{nf} =$	3081.934091	3065.431766	3488.109942	4161.542744
thermal conductivity of nanofluid $k_{nf} =$	0.885217139	0.848706041	0.719426334	0.895800818
Viscosity of nanofluid $\mu_{nf} =$	0.000534176	0.000526687	0.000528731	0.000532905
weight of nanoparticles in Kg	0.0043	0.0043	0.0023	0.00013

4.4.7 Friction factor

The flow in a smooth pipe is considered fully developed turbulent if the Reynolds number exceeds 10,000. In practice, the turbulent flow is standard in heat transfer systems and is usually associated with the heat transfer coefficient. The correlations between the heat transfer coefficient and the friction factor are mostly empirical formulas based on empirical formulas. This is because dealing theoretically with the turbulent flow is difficult.

The friction factor is a dimensionless quantity that determines the flow resistance in a pipe. It describes the energy loss due to the fluid friction with the pipe wall.

$$f = (0.79 \ln Re - 1.64)^{-2} \quad 3000 < Re < 5 * 10^6 \quad 4-12$$

4.4.8 Reynolds number

The Reynolds number, Re , is a critical parameter in fluid mechanics that helps classify flow. The flow in pipes is divided into three regimes: laminar, transitional and turbulent flow. Laminar flow is smooth, dominated by viscous forces, and efficient at low Reynolds numbers. Turbulent flow, however, is chaotic, dominated by inertial effects and eddies, and enhances mixing and transport at high Reynolds numbers. Transitional flow is in between. For internal

pipe flow, the flow regime depends on the Reynolds number (Re). If the Reynolds number is less than 2,300, the flow is laminar, characterised by smooth and orderly fluid motion. When the Reynolds number exceeds 10,000, the flow becomes turbulent, marked by chaotic eddies and enhanced mixing. In the range between 2300 and 10000, the flow is transitional, meaning it can fluctuate between laminar and turbulent behaviour before fully stabilising into one regime. (Çengel and Ghajar, 2015). The thresholds for laminar ($Re < 2300$) and turbulent ($Re > 10000$) flow are based on empirical observations for flow in smooth, straight pipes. However, these values may vary slightly depending on factors such as the system's geometry, surface roughness, and other external conditions.

$$Re = \frac{\rho u L}{\mu} = \frac{u L}{\nu} \quad 4-13$$

4.4.9 Prandtl number

The Prandtl number (Pr) is a dimensionless parameter in fluid mechanics and heat transfer, defined as the ratio of momentum diffusivity (kinematic viscosity, ν) to thermal diffusivity (α), expressed as in 4-14 Where μ is dynamic viscosity, c_p is specific heat, and k is thermal conductivity. It quantifies the relative rates of momentum and heat diffusion in a fluid, indicating the relative thicknesses of velocity and thermal boundary layers near a surface. $Pr \approx 1$ for gases, as the momentum and heat diffuse similarly with comparable boundary layer thicknesses. $Pr \gg 1$ for liquids as the momentum diffuses faster, resulting in a thinner thermal boundary layer. For $Pr \ll 1$, such as liquid metals, the heat diffuses faster, leading to a thicker thermal boundary layer.

$$\text{Pr} = \frac{C_p \mu}{k} = \frac{\nu}{\alpha} \quad 4-14$$

4.4.10 Nusselt number

The Nusselt number (Nu) is a dimensionless parameter that quantifies the efficiency of heat transfer. It represents the ratio of convective to conductive heat transfer across a fluid layer, expressed as 4-15, where h is the convective heat transfer coefficient, L_c is a characteristic length, and k is the fluid's thermal conductivity.

The Nusselt number indicates the degree to which convection enhances heat transfer compared to conduction alone. A value of $\text{Nu} = 1$ indicates purely conductive heat transfer, while a higher Nu signifies that convection dominates, improving heat transfer efficiency.

$$\text{Nu} = \frac{\text{total heat transfer}}{\text{conductive heat transfer}} = \frac{h}{k/L_c} \quad 4-15$$

4.4.11 Friction factor/Nusselt relationship

The friction factor, denoted as (f), is a dimensionless parameter in fluid dynamics that quantifies flow resistance due to frictional effects between a fluid and a solid surface. It is closely tied to wall shear stress (τ_w), which is the tangential force per unit area caused by viscosity at the surface. This parameter is essential for understanding how fluids interact with surfaces in both internal and external flow situations.

$$\Delta P_L = f \left(\frac{L}{D} \right) \left(\rho \frac{V_{avg}^2}{2} \right) \quad 4-16$$

In pipe flow, the friction factor is crucial for calculating the pressure drop (ΔP), which represents the irreversible pressure loss due to viscous effects. The pressure loss in fully developed flow is given by 4-16 where L is the pipe length, D is the diameter, ρ is fluid density, and V_{avg} is the average velocity. The friction factor (f) relates to the friction coefficient C_f via $f = 4C_f$. The friction factor value depends on the flow regime. In turbulent flow, it depends on both Re and relative roughness (ϵ/D). At the pipe inlet, where boundary layers are thin, the friction factor is higher, decreasing to a constant value in the fully developed region, with entrance effects increasing the average friction factor. The friction factor in a smooth tube with turbulent flow, which is the case of this study, could be calculated using 4-17

$$f = (0.790 * \ln Re - 1.67)^{-2} \quad 3000 < Re < 5 * 10^6 \quad 4-17$$

The Nusselt number is related to the friction factor through the Chilton-Colburn 4-18 Which will be used in the calculations later.

$$Nu = 0.125 f Re Pr^{\frac{1}{3}} \quad 4-18$$

4.4.12 Petukhov equation

The first Petukhov equation explicitly calculates the friction factor (f) for fully developed turbulent flow in smooth tubes. Its formula is 4-17 valid for Reynolds numbers (Re) ranging from 3000 to 5×10^6 . For smooth pipes offering reliable friction factor predictions.

The second Petukhov equation determines the Nusselt number (Nu) for turbulent flow, relating it to the friction factor (f), Reynolds number (Re), and Prandtl number (Pr). The formula is 4-18 applicable for Prandtl numbers from 0.5 to 2000 and Reynolds numbers from 10^4 to 5×10^6

. The friction factor (f) in this equation can be obtained from the first Petukhov equation. 4-19 is the combination of the two Petukhov equations to predict the Nusselt number using the Reynolds number.

$$Nu = \frac{\left(\frac{f}{8}\right) * Re * Pr}{1.27 + 12.7 * \left(\frac{f}{8}\right)^5 \left(Pr^{\frac{2}{3}} - 1\right)} \quad \begin{array}{l} 0.5 \leq Pr \leq 2000 \\ 10^4 < Re < 5 * 10^6 \end{array} \quad 4-19$$

4.4.13 Log Mean Temperature Difference

The Log Mean Temperature Difference (LMTD), represented as ΔT_{lmtd} It is favoured over simpler methods, such as the arithmetic mean temperature difference, in heat transfer calculations because it provides a more precise measure of the driving force behind heat transfer, particularly when the temperature gradient changes along the heat exchange surface.

In case of fluid flowing through a tube with a constant wall temperature, the temperature difference between the fluid and the surface is not constant but varies along the length of the system. A basic arithmetic mean temperature difference ΔT_{am} Averages the inlet and outlet temperature differences, assuming a linear temperature variation. However, this assumption is not true, especially when the surface temperature remains fixed. Instead, the actual temperature difference typically decreases exponentially along the flow direction. The LMTD accounts for this exponential decay, making it an exact representation of the average temperature difference. While using the arithmetic mean can lead to an overestimation of heat transfer rates. For this reason, LMTD is used when calculating heat transfer rates in systems like tubes with constant surface temperatures.

the Log Mean Temperature Difference (LMTD) can be calculated according to 4-20

$$T_{l\text{tmd}} = \frac{(T_{in} - T_{wall}) - (T_{out} - T_{wall})}{\ln(T_{in} - T_{wall}) - \ln(T_{out} - T_{wall})} \quad 4-20$$

fluid	water				
denisty	977.5				
viscosity	0.000404	2.553182504			
thermal conductivity	0.663				
specific heat	4190				
T_in	80	c			
T_wall	24	c			
vel	1	m/s			
diameter	0.025				
vel	RE	T_out	Q_cal	q_prog	
0.5	30244.43069	65.94327	14124.17113	14124.1682	
1	60488.86139	67.36374	25393.77312	25394.156	
1.5	90733.29208	68.08836	35905.83235	35906.234	
2	120977.7228	68.56396	45962.93478	45963.32	
2.5	151222.1535	68.91398	55695.21661	55694.738	
3.5	211711.0149	69.40673	74507.55513	74508.516	

example of calculations using previous equations

4.5 Validation of the results

4.5.1 Validation of the software results using Water

The upcoming graphs of Nu as calculated by the software (using Q_{prog} generated by the software to calculate the h heat transfer coefficient at the surface and then using h to calculate Nusselt number according to 4-15) and the Nu number determined using the Nusselt correlation (Petukhov equation) 4-19, both plotted against the Reynolds number (calculated using 4-13) and the fluid velocity respectively and the percentage error calculated using 4-21. In the Nusselt number versus the Reynolds number, these figures are used to validate the simulation for all nanofluids.

Figure 39 software generated and calculated Nusselt number for water against the Reynolds number the deviation shows the consistency of the results from the software and that calculated

Figure 40 Software-generated and calculated Nusselt number for water against the fluid velocity

to validate the simulation Figure 39 Figure 40 Figure 40 Software-generated and calculated Nusselt number for water against the fluid velocity shows a comparison between the Nu number for water as calculated by the software (using Q_{prog} generated by the software to calculate the heat transfer coefficient at the surface, and then using h to calculate the Nusselt number according to 4-15) and the Nu number determined using the Nusselt correlation (Petukhov equation), both plotted against the Reynolds number (calculated using 4-13) and the fluid velocity, respectively. The results indicate a high degree of consistency between the software-generated values and the calculated Nu number.

For validation of the simulation, Figure 42 shows a comparison between the pressure drop for water as calculated by the software and the pressure drop determined using the standard pressure drop from Equation 4-16, both plotted against the Reynolds number calculated using Equation 4-13. The results indicate a high degree of consistency between the software-generated values and the calculated pressure drop.

Figure 41 The pressure drops calculated by the software for the water are compared to those calculated using the pressure drop equation based on the Reynolds number (Re).

Figure 42 The percentage error is calculated for the Nu number using the Nu obtained from the software and the calculated Nu correlation.

While Figure 42 Shows the percentage error extracted using the calculated and program-generated Nusselt numbers against the Reynolds number, with an error of around 4%. Using 4-21

$$(\% \text{ Error } Nu = \frac{\text{software generated } NU - \text{calculated } NU}{\text{software generated } NU} * 100)$$

4-21

4.5.2 Validation with Alumina

Figure 43 Software-generated and calculated Nusselt number for Alumina nanofluid against the Reynolds number

Figure 43 Shows a comparison between the Nu number for Alumina as calculated by the software (using Q_{prog} generated by the software to calculate the heat transfer coefficient at the surface, and then using h to calculate the Nusselt number according to 4-15) and the Nu number determined using the Nusselt correlation (Petukhov equation) 4-19 Both plotted against the Reynolds number (calculated using 4-13). The results indicate a high degree of consistency between the software-generated values and the calculated Nu number.

Figure 44 The pressure drops calculated by the software for the alumina nanofluid compared to the pressure drop calculated using the pressure drop equation against the Re

Figure 44 shows A comparison between the pressure drop for Alumina as calculated by the software and the pressure drop determined using the standard pressure drop from 4-16 Both plotted against the Reynolds number, which was calculated using 4-13. The results indicate a high degree of consistency between the software-generated values and the calculated pressure drop.

Figure 45 Error calculated for the Nu number using the Nu obtained from the software and the calculated Nu correlation to show the correctness of the validation

While Figure 45 Shows the percentage error extracted using calculated and program-generated Nusselt numbers against the Reynolds number. The error is around 5.5%, which is very acceptable. using 4-21

4.5.3 Validation with Silica

Figure 46 software generated and calculated Nusselt number for Silica nanofluid against the Reynolds number

Figure 46 Shows a comparison between the Nu number for Silica nanofluid as calculated by the software and the Nu number determined using the Nusselt correlation, both plotted against the Reynolds number. The results indicate a high degree of consistency between the software-generated values and the calculated Nu number values.

Figure 47 the pressure drop calculated by the software for the Silica nanofluid compared to the pressure drop calculated using the pressure drop equation against the Re

Figure 47 shows A comparison between the pressure drop for Silica nanofluid as calculated by the software and the pressure drop determined using the standard pressure drop equation, both plotted against the Reynolds number. The results indicate a high degree of consistency between the software-generated values and the calculated pressure drop. Figure 48 shows the percentage error extracted using the calculated and program-generated Nusselt number against the Reynolds number. The error is around 3.5%, which is very acceptable.

Figure 48 error calculated for Nu number using the Nu obtained from the software and the calculated Nu correlation

4.5.4 Validation with Titania

Figure 49 software generated and calculated Nusselt number for titania nanofluid against the Reynolds number

Figure 49 Shows a comparison between the Nu number for titania nanofluid as calculated by the software (software-generated) and the Nu number determined using the Nusselt correlation,

both plotted against the Reynolds number. The results indicate a high degree of consistency between the software-generated values and the calculated Nu number values

Figure 50 the pressure drop calculated by the software for the titania nanofluid compared to the pressure drop calculated using the pressure drop equation against the Re

Figure 50 shows A comparison was made between the pressure drop for titania nanofluid as calculated by the software and the pressure drop determined using the standard pressure drop equation, both plotted against the Reynolds number. The results indicate a high degree of consistency between the software-generated values and the calculated pressure drop. While Figure 51 shows the percentage error extracted using the calculated and program-generated Nusselt number against the Reynolds number.

Figure 51 error calculated for Nu number using the Nu obtained from the software and the calculated Nu correlation

4.5.5 Validation with Graphene oxide

Figure 52 software generated and calculated Nusselt number for graphene oxide nanofluid against the Reynolds number

Figure 52 Shows a comparison between the Nu number for graphene oxide nanofluid as calculated by the software and the Nu number determined using the Nusselt correlation, both plotted against the Reynolds number. The results indicate a high degree of consistency between the software-generated values and the calculated Nu number values.

Figure 53 The pressure drops calculated by the software for the graphene oxide nanofluid compared to the pressure drop calculated using the pressure drop equation against the Re

Figure 53 A comparison was made between the pressure drop for graphene oxide nanofluid, as calculated by the software, and the pressure drop determined using the standard pressure drop equation, both plotted against the Reynolds number. The results indicate a high degree of consistency between the software-generated values and the calculated pressure drop figures.

Figure 54 Shows the percentage error extracted using the calculated and program-generated Nusselt number against the Reynolds number. The error is around 3.5%, which is acceptable.

Figure 54 error calculated for Nu number using the Nu obtained from the software and the calculated Nu correlation

4.6 Water based Nanofluid heat transfer.

The results are very unexpected. After careful consideration of all parameters and variables I think that the change in the density causes an alteration of the expected results as the concentration of the nanoparticles are calculated in volume % as all the used concentrations are 0.1 % volume fraction this will change the required mass for such concentration which will influence the density of the nanofluid and will influence the mass flow rate which will alter the heat transfer. Increasing the thermal conductivity does not necessarily mean that the fluid will be superior for heat transfer, as other properties may change, causing the heat transfer to be worse. In water-based nanofluids, the Nusselt number was the highest for water, while the lowest Nusselt number was for graphene oxide, which has the highest thermal conductivity. Titania, silica, and alumina lie between water and graphene oxide, as shown in Figure 55. While in Figure 48, the figures show that the heat transfer coefficient has a different order of the

nanofluids, as alumina and titania demonstrated the highest heat transfer coefficient while the water, silica and graphene oxide was less enhanced

Figure 55 comparison between program generated Nusselt number of different nanofluids against the Reynolds number

Figure 56 comparison between program generated Nusselt number of different nanofluids against the fluid speed instead of Reynolds number

Figure 56 reveals a clear positive correlation between the Nusselt number and fluid velocity, Reynolds number as fluid speed and Reynolds number increases, so does the Nusselt number. However, the type of nanoparticle used significantly influences the magnitude of this increase. Interestingly while still demonstrating a positive correlation, the graphene oxide nanofluid consistently exhibits the lowest Nusselt numbers across the tested flow velocities (this is because it has the highest thermal conductivity as this case is counter intuitive). This is followed in ascending order by alumina, titania, and silica nanofluids. The highest Nusselt numbers are observed in the base fluid which is water.

Figure 57 shows the heat transfer coefficient of different nanofluids against the Reynolds number

Figure 58 shows the heat transfer coefficient of different nanofluids against the fluid speed instead of Reynolds number

Figure 57 Figure 58 Figure 58 illustrates a clear trend the heat transfer coefficient of all four nanofluids (alumina, silica, titania, and graphene oxide) increases proportionally with fluid velocity and Reynolds number. The alumina nanofluid demonstrates a slightly higher heat transfer coefficient compared to titania, but significantly higher than silica, water and graphene oxide. Graphene oxide displays the lowest enhancement among the nanofluids, while water, as the base fluid, exhibits the lowest overall heat transfer coefficient.

Figure 59 the outlet temperature calculated for all fluids against the speed of the fluid

Figure 59 the outlet temperature of the fluid consistently increases with rising fluid velocity across all tested nanofluids (alumina, silica, titania, and graphene oxide). This suggests a more efficient transfer of heat at higher flow rates. The alumina nanofluid consistently yields the lowest outlet temperatures, indicating superior heat transfer performance. Titania follows closely behind Graphene oxide, then Silica, exhibits the highest temperature increase among the nanofluids. Water, as the base fluid, consistently produces the highest outlet temperatures across the tested velocities. This positive correlation between nanoparticle inclusion and outlet temperatures underscores the impact of enhanced thermal conductivity on the overall heat transfer process.

Figure 60 The Reynolds number of all fluids against the fluid velocity

Figure 60 As the fluid velocity increases, the Reynolds number consistently rises for all tested nanofluids: alumina, silica, titania, and graphene oxide. The titania nanofluid consistently exhibits the highest Reynolds numbers. Alumina closely follows passing over the water line, then silica, graphene oxide. Water consistently shows high Reynolds numbers across the tested velocities. The positive link between nanoparticle inclusion and a decrease in Reynolds number may be attributed to the mass flow rate and the density difference of the nanofluids.

Figure 61 Shows the pressure drop of water-based nanofluids vs fluid speed

Figure 61 The pressure drops of Alumina and titania exhibit the highest pressure drops, while graphene oxide displays the lowest, comparable to that of water. Silica falls in between alumina and water. The pressure drop is affected the friction factor.

Figure 62 Q (energy) dissipated by the fluids against the velocity of the fluid.

Figure 62 Illustrates a trend in the amount of energy dissipated by the fluid, calculated using the ANSYS Fluent software, which increases proportionally with fluid velocity as expected across all tested nanofluids (alumina, silica, titania, and graphene oxide). However, the nanoparticle significantly influences the magnitude of energy release along the pipe. Among the tested nanofluids alumina consistently achieves the highest energy dissipation across the range of flow velocities, indicating its superior performance in heat transfer. Titania follows closely behind, outperforming silica. Graphene oxide, while still demonstrating an improvement over the base fluid, exhibits the lowest energy dissipation increase among the nanofluids. Water as the base fluid consistently yields the lowest energy dissipation rates. This observation underscores the crucial role of nanoparticle properties in enhancing heat transfer and energy dissipation in fluid systems.

The following sections present contour plots and temperature graphs for fluid velocities ranging from 0.5 m/s to 2 m/s for water-based nanofluids. The contour plot displays the temperature variations along the length of the pipe. The temperature is highest at the pipe's inlet and decreases gradually towards the outlet. The contour provides a visual representation of the temperature distribution within the pipe's cross-section for four different types of water-based nanofluids alumina, silica, titania, and graphene oxide. The subsequent graph illustrates how the temperature changes along the central line of the tube as a function of the tube's length, extending from the inlet to the outlet. The contour patterns and graph layout suggest that nanofluids can transfer heat to the pipe wall more effectively than the base fluid, leading to a decrease in fluid temperature at the outlet compared to the inlet as heat is dispersed along the path.

4.6.1 Velocity simulation at 0.5 m/s

Figure 63 The figure illustrates comparative contour plots for various water-based nanofluids constant velocity 0.5m/s

Figure 64 illustrates comparative contour plots for various water-based nanofluids, including alumina, silica, titania, and graphene oxide, alongside pure water as the base fluid. These plots depict the fluids' temperature behaviour at a constant velocity of 0.5 m/s

Figure 64 The temperature gradient along the pipe for the water-based nanofluids at 0.5 m/s

The temperature gradient along the pipe was analysed for four nanofluids in comparison to water. All four nanofluids exhibited superior heating performance compared to water, with the temperature decreasing more efficiently as the fluid progressed through the pipe. Alumina demonstrated the most significant temperature reduction, followed by titania and graphene oxide. Silica showed the least temperature decrease, though still better than water. This is right for all four different fluid speeds in Figure 64, Figure 66, Figure 68, Figure 70

4.6.2 Velocity simulation at 1 m/s

Figure 65 The figure illustrates comparative contour plots for various water-based nanofluids, alumina, silica, titania, and graphene oxide constant velocity of 1 m/s

Figure 66 The figure illustrates comparative contour plots for various water-based nanofluids, alumina, silica, titania, and graphene oxide, alongside pure water as the base fluid. These plots depict the fluids' temperature behaviour at a constant velocity of 1 m/s

Figure 66: The temperature gradient along the pipe for the water-based nanofluids at 1 m/s

4.6.3 Velocity simulation at 1.5 m/s

Figure 67 The figure illustrates comparative contour plots for various water-based nanofluids, including alumina, silica, titania, and graphene oxide, with a velocity of 1.5 m/s

Figure 68 illustrates comparative contour plots for various water-based nanofluids, including alumina, silica, titania, and graphene oxide, alongside pure water as the base fluid. These plots depict the fluids' temperature behaviour at a constant velocity of 1.5 m/s

Figure 68 The temperature gradient along the pipe for the water-based nanofluids at 1.5 m/s

4.6.4 Velocity simulation at 2 m/s

Figure 69 The figure illustrates comparative contour plots for various water-based nanofluids at constant velocity of 2 m/s

Figure 70 illustrates comparative contour plots for various water-based nanofluids, including alumina, silica, titania, and graphene oxide, alongside pure water as the base fluid. These plots depict the fluids' temperature behaviour at a constant velocity of 2 m/s

Figure 70 The temperature gradient along the pipe for the water based nanofluids at 2 m/s

4.7 Ethylene glycol Nanofluid heat transfer

Figure 71 shows the Nusselt number for all ethylene glycol based selected nanofluids vs the fluid velocity

Figure 71 A correlation is evident between the Nusselt number and fluid velocity, as the fluid speed increases, so does the Nusselt number. However, the choice of nanoparticles utilised notably impacts the extent of this increase, as in the case of water-based nanofluids. While maintaining a positive correlation, the graphene oxide nanofluid consistently displays the lowest Nusselt numbers across the range of flow velocities, which is due to its high thermal conductivity, making this scenario somewhat counterintuitive. Following in increasing order are silica, alumina, ethylene glycol and titania nanofluids. The highest Nusselt numbers were observed for titania.

Figure 72 Reynolds number vs fluid speed for ethylene glycol based nanofluids

Figure 72 shows the Reynolds number vs the fluid speed. As the fluid velocity increases, the Reynolds number consistently rises for all tested nanofluids and base fluids, with the order being alumina, titania, and ethylene glycol, which have high and similar Reynolds numbers, followed by silica, and then graphene oxide.

The outlet temperature of the fluid consistently increases with rising fluid velocity across all tested ethylene glycol-based nanofluids (alumina, silica, titania, and graphene oxide). Examining the magnitude of this temperature increase reveals a distinct pattern. The Graphene oxide, titania, and alumina nanofluid consistently yields the lowest outlet temperatures, indicating superior heat transfer performance. Silica follows closely behind. Ethylene glycol exhibits the highest temperature at the outlet among the fluids. This positive correlation between nanoparticle inclusion and elevated outlet temperatures describes the impact of nanoparticles on the overall heat transfer process.

Figure 73 shows the pressure drop of all ethylene glycol-based nanofluids vs fluid speed

Figure 73 The increase in fluid velocity corresponds to a rise in pressure drop for all fluids. Among them, alumina and titania show the highest pressure drop, while graphene oxide has the lowest, silica slightly above that of graphene oxide. Ethylene glycol, on the other hand, experiences the least pressure drop.

Figure 74 shows the relationship between the heat transfer coefficient and the fluid velocity.

Figure 74 Illustrates a clear trend: the heat transfer coefficient of all four ethylene glycol-based nanofluids (alumina, silica, titania, and graphene oxide) increases proportionally with fluid velocity. The titania nanofluid demonstrates a slightly higher heat transfer coefficient compared to alumina, but significantly higher than silica and graphene oxide. Graphene oxide and silica display the lowest enhancement among the nanofluids, while ethylene glycol, as the base fluid, exhibits the lowest overall heat transfer coefficient, as expected.

The following sections are contour plots and temperature graphs for fluid velocities ranging from 0.5 m/s to 2 m/s for ethylene glycol-based nanofluids. The contour plot displays the temperature variations along the length of the pipe. The temperature is highest at the pipe's inlet and decreases gradually towards the outlet. The contour provides a visual depiction of the temperature distribution within the pipe's cross-section for four different types of ethylene glycol-based nanofluids: alumina, silica, titania, and graphene oxide. The subsequent graphs illustrate how the temperature changes along the central line of the tube as a function of the

tube's length, extending from the inlet to the outlet. The contour patterns and graph layout suggest that nanofluids can transfer heat to the pipe wall more effectively than the base fluid, leading to a decrease in fluid temperature from the inlet to the outlet as heat is dispersed along the path.

4.7.1 Velocity simulation at 0.5 m/s

Figure 75 The figure illustrates comparative contour plots for various ethylene glycol-based nanofluids at a constant velocity of 0.5 m/s

Figure 76. The figure illustrates comparative contour plots for various ethylene glycol-based nanofluids, alumina, silica, titania, and graphene oxide, alongside pure ethylene glycol as the

Figure 76: The temperature gradient along the pipe for the ethylene glycol-based nanofluids at 0.5 m/s base fluid. These plots depict the fluids' temperature behaviour at a constant velocity of 0.5 m/s

4.7.2 Velocity simulation at 1 m/s

Figure 77 The figure illustrates comparative contour plots for various ethylene glycol-based nanofluids at a constant velocity of 1 m/s

Figure 78. The figure illustrates comparative contour plots for various ethylene glycol-based nanofluids, alumina, silica, titania, and graphene oxide, alongside pure ethylene glycol as the base fluid. These plots depict the fluids' temperature at a constant velocity of 1 m/s

Figure 78: The temperature gradient along the pipe for the ethylene glycol-based nanofluids at 1 m/s

4.7.3 Velocity simulation at 1.5 m/s

Figure 79 The figure illustrates comparative contour plots for various ethylene glycol-based nanofluids at a constant velocity of 1.5 m/s

Figure 80 illustrates comparative contour plots for various ethylene glycol-based nanofluids, alumina, silica, titania, and graphene oxide, alongside pure ethylene glycol as the base fluid. These plots depict the fluids' temperature behaviour at a constant velocity of 1.5 m/s

Figure 80: The temperature gradient along the pipe for the ethylene glycol-based nanofluids at 1.5 m/s

4.7.4 Velocity simulation at 2 m/s

Figure 81 Illustrates comparative contour plots for various ethylene glycol-based nanofluids, alumina, silica, titania, and graphene oxide, alongside pure ethylene glycol as the base fluid. These plots depict the fluids' temperature behaviour at a constant velocity of 2 m/s

Figure 82 illustrates comparative contour plots for various ethylene glycol-based nanofluids, alumina, silica, titania, and graphene oxide, alongside pure ethylene glycol as the base fluid. These plots depict the fluids' temperature behaviour at a constant velocity of 2 m/s

Figure 82: The temperature gradient along the pipe for the ethylene glycol-based nanofluids at 2 m/s

4.8 Discussion

The results from the heat transfer coefficient and the dissipated energy graphs showed that the nanoparticles enhance the heat transfer. The alumina/water nanofluid has demonstrated high energy dissipation and a high heat transfer coefficient. In the case of ethylene glycol-based nanofluids, the titania/ethylene glycol nanofluid has shown an enhancement of heat transfer, as indicated by the Nusselt number and heat transfer coefficient graphs.

These visual representations indicate that the inclusion of nanoparticles notably boosts the fluid's heat transfer capability. The contour plots provide a visual representation of the data, highlighting the enhanced heat transfer performance of nanofluids.

The difference in outlet temperatures between the nanofluid and base fluid offers compelling evidence of nanofluids' efficacy in enhancing heat transfer in turbulent flow situations. This improved performance supports the idea that nanofluids have thermal advantages over traditional heat transfer fluids.

The impact of adding nanoparticles on enhancing the heat transfer coefficient originates from the higher thermal conductivity of the nanofluid, resulting from the presence of solid nanoparticles. These findings hold considerable importance for advancing nanofluid development across various industrial applications where improved heat transfer is crucial for enhancing efficiency and reducing energy consumption. These revelations suggest that integrating nanofluids into industrial operations could lead to energy savings and increased efficiency, ultimately benefiting the environment.

4.9 Summary

A Turbulent forced convection heat transfer in a straight circular tube was investigated in a three-dimensional symmetric computational fluid dynamics (CFD) simulation performed with ANSYS Fluent. Four different nanoparticles, namely alumina (Al_2O_3), titania (TiO_2), silica (SiO_2), and graphene oxide (GO), were evaluated in terms of thermal performance in this work. Two basic fluids ethylene glycol and water were used. Using the given correlations, the thermophysical characteristics of the produced nanofluids were computed.

The primary objectives were to investigate the effect of nanoparticle addition on the heat transfer properties of the base fluids and to evaluate the suitability of 3D CFD modelling in capturing heat transfer behaviour inside turbulent pipe flow. In terms of Nusselt number and total heat transfer enhancement, the simulation contrasted the performance of nanofluids against their corresponding base fluids.

A good agreement was shown between the simulated and theoretical results for both the Nusselt number and pressure drop, as the CFD model was validated against the empirical Petukhov equation for turbulent flow. The numerical results showed that some nanoparticles greatly enhanced the fluid convective heat transfer capacity. Among the nanofluids investigated, alumina exhibited the best heat transfer performance, followed by silica, graphene oxide, and titania.

Particularly in systems involving turbulent flow, this work emphasises the possibility of nanofluids to improve heat transfer efficiency in industrial applications. Efficiency in industrial applications, particularly in systems involving turbulent flow.

4.10 References Chapter 4

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Chapter 5

Nanofluids Preparation, Properties, and Analytical Techniques

5.1 Introduction

This research focuses on several analytical methods used to characterise nanofluids and their nanoparticles. Raman spectroscopy stands out as a key technique, offering information about Graphene oxide and graphene. The technique shows the degree of oxidation of the graphene oxide. (Mohan et al., 2017; Scardaci and Compagnini, 2021; Velázquez et al., 2015).

Dynamic Light Scattering (DLS) analyses the size distribution and stability of suspended nanoparticles. This technique enables researchers to monitor particle agglomeration over time, which is crucial for assessing the long-term stability of nanofluids.

Scanning Transmission Electron Microscopy (STEM) offers high-resolution imaging of nanoparticles. This powerful technique allows for visual capture of nanoscale characteristics within the nanofluid, providing direct evidence of particle morphology and dispersion.

X-ray Diffraction (XRD) rounds out the analytical toolkit by revealing the crystalline structure of nanoparticles. This information is vital for understanding particle properties and their interactions with the fluid, which can significantly influence the overall behaviour of the nanofluid.

Energy-Dispersive X-ray Spectroscopy (EDX) is a vital technique for analysing the elemental composition of materials. Known for its speed, non-destructiveness, and precision, it is widely used in materials science.

The combination of these analytical methods offers a good understanding of nanofluid systems. This comprehensive approach is essential for rational design and optimisation of nanofluids, tailoring their properties for specific applications.

5.2 Characterisation methods

5.2.1 Raman spectrum

Raman spectroscopy serves as a tool for examining carbon nanostructures by analysing the Raman shifts, which unveil their distinctive vibrational patterns through light wave scattering without disrupting the samples under study. This method involves directing a monochromatic light onto the samples, where the resulting frequency change of the scattered light, known as the Raman shift, provides valuable information about the level of oxidation of the graphene oxide. Carbon materials exhibit peaks in their spectra corresponding to atomic vibrations, with the prominent G band around 1580 cm^{-1} signalling a honeycomb structure with sp^2 hybridisation. Imperfections and modifications manifest as additional peaks, such as the irregularities indicated by a band at approximately 1350 cm^{-1} in graphite. Graphene oxide (GO) exhibits strong D bands due to oxygenated groups, such as epoxides and carbonyls, which impact the sp^2 network. The degree of disorder is indicated by the ID/IG ratio, which reflects the defect density, while the peak position and width provide additional information. A shift in the G band of graphene oxide means an alteration in the sp^2 carbon structure due to oxidation processes, with secondary peaks indicating oxygen-related properties. (“Introductory Raman Spectroscopy - John R. Ferraro - Google Books,” n.d.)

5.2.2 DLS

Direct Light Scattering for Nanomaterial Analysis

Direct Light Scattering (DLS) is a method used to provide valuable information about nanoparticle size distribution, polydispersity and their stability in fluid media. DLS involves

analysing particle size distribution in liquid suspensions or polymers dissolved in solutions by measuring the motion velocity of small, suspended particles as they interact with laser light during analysis, based on the Stokes-Einstein equation.

Dynamic Light Scattering (DLS) is particularly useful for monitoring the stability of nanoparticle mixtures over time and detecting clusters. This method also helps evaluate the effectiveness of nanofluid formulations and understand the impact of surfactants or preparation techniques on particle size distribution and stability in liquid media. It provides quick, non-destructive, and low sample preparation analysis of nanomaterials. (Berne and Pecora, 2000)

DLS also provides information about zeta potential, which refers to the electric potential surrounding a particle at the shear plane within a colloidal dispersion. It means the charge present on the surface of nanoparticles, which influences their stability and interactions with the surrounding environment. This electrokinetic property is key in determining the dispersion stability of nanoparticles in solutions. Notably, nanoparticles with higher zeta potential tend to repel each other, preventing agglomeration and ensuring stable dispersion.

Various factors, including particle size, surface chemistry, pH, and ionic strength of the medium influence the zeta potential of nanoparticles. Understanding and controlling the zeta potential of nanoparticles is crucial for their practical use.

The zeta potential of nanoparticles is a crucial parameter for understanding how they behave and interact in suspension. By manipulating the zeta potential, researchers can enhance the stability, dispersion, and reactivity of nanoparticles for a wide range of applications. (Hunter et al., 1987)

In this research, utilising the Zetasizer equipment from Malvern Instruments at a temperature of 25 degrees, the refractive indices were adjusted to 1.33 for graphene and 2.38 for the deionised water (dispersant). The material classification was set to the material under testing

for the analysis. The measurements were conducted in triplicate to ensure accuracy, and the mean and standard deviation were calculated for the results obtained. To determine the hydrodynamic radius, the Stokes-Einstein equation was employed

$$D_h = \left(\frac{K_b * T}{3\pi\eta_0 * D_t} \right) \quad 5-22$$

Here, K_b Represents the Boltzmann constant, T denotes the temperature in Kelvin, η_0 , the solvent viscosity, and D_t Represents the translational diffusion coefficient. By applying this equation, the hydrodynamic radius of the material could be calculated based on the experimental data collected using the Zetasizer instrument.(Amaro-Gahete et al., 2019)

5.2.3 STEM and XRD

Scanning electron microscopy

A high-resolution Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) is used for detailed surface imaging and analysis. It scans a focused electron beam over a sample to reveal fine structural details beyond the capability of light microscopes. The instrument also supports elemental analysis when equipped with detectors like Energy Dispersive X-ray Spectroscopy (EDS). The setup includes the main microscope column, control monitors, and a display screen showing magnified images, typical of advanced research labs.

STEM's exceptional imaging resolution enables direct observation of nanomaterials at the atomic scale. STEM involves transmitting a focused electron beam through a thin sample and analysing the intensity and spatial distribution of transmitted electrons to create precise images depicting the size, shape, and morphology of individual nanoparticles.

XRD explores the crystallographic structure of nanomaterials by utilising X-rays. As X-rays diffract from the crystalline planes of the material, a unique diffraction pattern emerges. This pattern gives information about the crystal structure, lattice parameters, and various phases present in the nanomaterial. XRD offer a comprehensive view of the nanomaterial's crystal structure.(Williams and Carter, 2009)

5.2.4 Energy-Dispersive X-ray Spectroscopy (EDX)

The EDX technique is based on X-ray fluorescence. When a high-energy electron beam (usually from a Scanning Electron Microscope, SEM) strikes a sample, it interacts with the atoms, ejecting inner-shell electrons. This leaves behind vacancies in the atomic structure, which are then filled by electrons from higher energy levels. As these electrons drop to lower energy states, they emit X-rays with distinct energies unique to the elements in the sample.

The EDX spectrum displays the energy distribution of these emitted X-rays. The x-axis shows the X-ray energy (in keV), while the y-axis indicates the intensity or number of X-rays detected

at each energy level. The peaks in the spectrum represent the characteristic X-ray energies of different elements, enabling researchers to determine the sample's elemental composition.(Goldstein et al., 2017)

5.3 Silica

Figure 83 shows silica nanofluid

The silica nanoparticles were obtained from China to avoid the manufacturing process as mentioned in methodology chapter.

Silica nanoparticles (SiNPs) have one of the most captivating features of their exceptional thermal conductivity. Compared to bulk silica, SiNPs can exhibit higher thermal conductivity, making them ideal for heat dissipation in microelectronics and thermal management in batteries. This enhanced conductivity arises from several factors, including the large surface area-to-volume ratio of the nanoparticles and the phonon confinement effect, where heat vibrations are restricted within the SiNP structure. Silica nanofluids generally exhibit higher

thermal conductivity than their base fluids, making them ideal for heat transfer and other thermal management applications.

5.3.1 Silica NP STEM, EDX

EDX of Powder at 10kV

Figure 84 EDX of Silica nanoparticles. The figure was obtained from the STEM at university of the west of Scotland

The energy-dispersive X-ray (EDX) spectrum obtained from the STEM offers insights into the elemental composition of a silica sample, with distinct peaks revealing the presence of silicon and oxygen, the building blocks of silicon dioxide (SiO_2). The prominent peak at approximately 1.8 keV corresponds to silicon, the primary constituent of silica, while the broader peak at 0.5 keV signifies oxygen. These strong peaks confirm the presence of silica in the sample, as an ideal EDX spectrum of pure silica would predominantly exhibit these two peaks. However, the appearance of minor peaks at higher energies, around 10 keV, suggests the presence of trace elements that may originate from contaminants. While the EDX spectrum provides evidence

supporting the presence of silica in the sample, the detection of these minor peaks suggests the existence of trace impurities.

Figure 85 shows the STEM photo with diameter of the silica nanoparticles with average diameter of 14.88 nm

5.3.2 Zeta potential

Record	Type	Sample Name	Measurement Date and Time	T	ZP
				°C	mV
9	Zeta	Silica 0.32 g/L in water 1	02 March 2023 11:55:53	25.0	-38.9
10	Zeta	Silica 0.32 g/L in water 2	02 March 2023 11:58:53	25.0	-37.3
11	Zeta	Silica 0.32 g/L in water 3	02 March 2023 11:59:32	25.0	-38.5

The zeta potential is a crucial characteristic that reveals the surface charge of particles within a liquid suspension. Three instances of silica nanoparticles dispersed in water at a concentration of 0.32 g/L are examined at 25°C. The actual zeta potential values in millivolts (mV) for each sample are displayed in the sixth column of the table.

The zeta potential values presented in the table fall within the negative range, spanning from -37.3 mV to -38.9 mV. A negative zeta potential indicates that the silica nanoparticles bear a net negative charge on their surface.

When it comes to zeta potential, regardless of whether it is positive or negative, surpassing the 30 mark indicates a heightened repulsion force between particles. This repulsion is important in preventing particle agglomeration.

5.3.3 Size distribution

Figure 86 Size distribution of the silica nanoparticles (hydrodynamic diameter). Arrows showing the point on the logarithmic scale

Results

	Size (d.n...	% Number:	St Dev (d.n...
Z-Average (d.nm): 176.5	Peak 1: 59.43	100.0	37.69
Pdl: 0.159	Peak 2: 0.000	0.0	0.000
Intercept: 0.931	Peak 3: 0.000	0.0	0.000
Result quality Good			

Figure 87 polydispersity report of silica nanofluid

The graph shows the relationship between the percentage of nanoparticles and their sizes, measured in nanometers (nm). On the x-axis the diameters of the silica nanoparticles in nanometers, while the y-axis shows the percentage of nanoparticles. This indicates the proportion of nanoparticles falling within specific size ranges concerning the total count in the sample. A higher data point on the y-axis for a specific size range signifies a larger percentage of nanoparticles encapsulated within that particular size bracket.

The diameter of the silica nanoparticles aligns around 30-40 nm. This means that a notable fraction of the nanoparticles has a diameter proximately to 35 nm. The varying width of the peak indicates that the nanoparticle sizes are not uniform. There are slight size differences around the peak value of 35 nm. The difference between the STEM diameter and the DLS diameter is since the DLS diameter represents the hydrodynamic diameter, not the nanoparticle diameter.

5.4 Titania

Figure 88 Titania nanoparticles in water 0.1% vol fraction

Titanium dioxide nanoparticles were imported from China to skip the manufacturing steps detailed in the methodology section. Titania nanoparticles, the thermal properties of titania nanofluid can be altered based on their size, shape, and surface modifications.

Titania nanofluids, which consist of titanium dioxide nanoparticles dispersed in a base fluid like water or ethylene glycol, exhibit enhanced thermophysical properties. Despite their promising features, titania nanofluids face challenges such as long-term stability and potential agglomeration.

5.4.1 Titania STEM, EDX

EDX of Powder at 10kV

Some contaminants were found to be present in the TiO₂ powder.

Figure 89 EDX of titania nanoparticles obtained from STEM.

The elemental composition of a titania (titanium dioxide, TiO₂) powder sample is revealed through analysis using the Energy Dispersive X-ray. Titanium (Ti) is detected by a strong peak at approximately 4.5 keV, signifying its prominent presence as the primary element in titania.

Oxygen (O) is identified by a broad peak around 0.5 keV, representing the other essential component in the compound. Additionally, smaller peaks observed at higher energies, around 10 keV, suggest the possible existence of trace amounts of other elements within the sample. These elements are contaminants.

Figure 90 shows the diameter of the titania nanoparticles, with an average size of 36.3 nm.

5.4.2 Zeta potential

Table 4 shows the results of a series of measurements of titania nanoparticles

Record	Type	Sample Name	Measurement Date and Time	T °C	ZP mV
24	Zeta	Titania 2 g/L in water 1	02 March 2023 13:30:57	25.0	-30.6
25	Zeta	Titania 2 g/L in water 2	02 March 2023 13:33:57	25.0	-31.0
26	Zeta	Titania 2 g/L in water 3	02 March 2023 13:34:36	25.0	-30.1

Figure 91 Zeta potential of titania nanoparticles using the DLS

Table 1 presents the findings from a set of tests conducted on titania nanoparticles. It compiles data on the average size, size distribution, and surface charge of three titania nanoparticle samples suspended in water at a pH of 6.8. The zeta potential values recorded in the table are uniformly negative at -30 mV. A negative zeta potential means that the titania nanoparticles bear an overall negative surface charge. Typically, zeta potential values that are further away from +/-30 indicate a repulsion force among the particles, which aids in preventing clumping and enhances suspension stability. The data in the table highlights that all titania nanoparticle samples in water exhibit a negative zeta potential, implying a negatively charged surface.

Figure 92: Zeta potential of titania nanoparticles

The chart indicates that the titania nanoparticle sample displays a single peak in the zeta potential distribution, with most particles centred around -30 mV. The width of the peak indicates that the zeta potential distribution is not entirely consistent, exhibiting some variations around the central value.

5.4.3 Size distribution

Figure 93: Size distribution of titania nanoparticles

Results

	Size (d.n...)	% Number:	St Dev (d.n..)
Z-Average (d.nm): 160.9	Peak 1: 112.5	100.0	28.48
Pdl: 0.110	Peak 2: 0.000	0.0	0.000
Intercept: 0.917	Peak 3: 0.000	0.0	0.000

Result quality Good

Figure 94 Polydispersity report for titania nanofluid

Obtained from the DLS, the Figure 93 Figure 94 Illustrates how titania nanoparticles are distributed by size, based on the number of particles. Around 25 per cent of the nanoparticles have a main diameter of approximately 100 nm. The width of the peak indicates that the size distribution is not completely consistent, showing some size differences around the central value with Pdl 0.11.

5.5 Alumina

Figure 95 shows alumina nanofluid.

The Alumina nanoparticles were obtained from China to avoid the manufacturing process, as mentioned in the methodology chapter.

5.5.1 Alumina STEM, EDX

Al_2O_3 Powder : EDX at 10kV

Figure 96: EDX spectrum of alumina nanoparticles

The EDX spectrum of an alumina (aluminium oxide, Al_2O_3) powder sample exhibits a strong peak at 1.5 keV, indicating the presence of aluminium, the primary element in alumina, and a broad peak at 0.5 keV, suggesting the existence of oxygen, the second essential element in the compound. The spectrum encapsulates the elemental composition of the alumina sample.

Figure 97 STEM photo for alumina nanoparticles with average diameter 55.5 nm

5.5.2 Zeta potential

Record	Type	Sample Name	Measurement Date and Time	T °C	ZP mV
12	Zeta	Alumiuna 0.48 g/L in water 1	02 March 2023 12:15:23	25.0	28.2
13	Zeta	Alumiuna 0.48 g/L in water 2	02 March 2023 12:18:24	25.0	30.7
14	Zeta	Alumiuna 0.48 g/L in water 3	02 March 2023 12:19:03	25.0	27.5

Figure 98 a show the zeta potential of alumina

The table and graph show that the zeta potential of the alumina nanoparticles is an average of 32.13, indicating that the nanofluid is not stable and will be subjected to precipitation as the zeta potential fluctuates around the critical value of 30.

5.5.3 Size distribution

Figure 98b: Size distribution of alumina nanoparticles

Results

	Size (d.nm)	% Number	St Dev (d.nm)
Z-Average (d.nm): 174.8	Peak 1: 55.17	100.0	24.51
Pdl: 0.250	Peak 2: 0.000	0.0	0.000
Intercept: 0.925	Peak 3: 0.000	0.0	0.000

Result quality Good

Figure 99 Polydispersity of alumina nanofluid

From the graph of size distribution, it is possible to calculate the dominant particle size, which is approximately 40-50 nm.

5.6 Graphene Oxide

Figure 100 shows the graphene oxide prepared in the laboratory using the Hummer method.

This research aims to develop and evaluate graphene oxide (GO) nanofluids for their potential as high-performance heat transfer fluids. The study is motivated by the theoretical promise of graphene and its derivatives for exceptional thermal conductivity, with graphene oxide (GO) offering improved solubility compared to pristine graphene. The primary objectives include synthesising and characterising the GO nanofluid, comparing its thermal performance against that of conventional fluids through experimental testing.

The synthesis of graphene oxide is fundamentally based on the oxidation of graphite powder using strong oxidants. While several methods exist, including Brodie, Staudenmaier, and

Hummers, this study focuses on the Hummers method and its variations due to its prevalence and scalability. The Hummers method typically involves the use of graphite powder, sodium nitrate, sulfuric acid, and potassium permanganate, with careful temperature control and multiple washing steps to produce a yellowish-brown graphene oxide (GO) cake.

Various modifications to the Hummers method have been developed to enhance the oxidation process and improve the quality of the resulting graphene oxide (GO). These modifications include the incorporation of phosphoric acid, more precise temperature control, extended reaction times, and additional purification steps. Some researchers have also explored ultrasound-assisted synthesis methods, employing pulsed ultrasound for exfoliation, followed by centrifugation for separation and purification.

In this study, a modified Hummers method is employed. The process begins with mixing graphite powder and sodium nitrate in concentrated sulfuric acid, followed by the gradual addition of potassium permanganate under controlled temperature conditions. Subsequent steps involve heating, dilution, and the addition of hydrogen peroxide to eliminate excess permanganate. The GO product is then subjected to centrifugation, washing, and freeze-drying. To further refine the material, the GO undergoes additional processing through ultrasound treatment in an alkaline medium, which helps to reduce particle size.

5.6.1 Synthesis of Graphene Oxide

The Hummers' method represents a widely adopted and straightforward chemical approach for producing graphene oxide (GO) from graphite, offering both a high yield and scalability. Key components in this process include graphite, potassium permanganate, sodium nitrate, and concentrated sulfuric acid. The resulting GO suspensions typically showcase a notable oxygen content of approximately 40-50% and incorporate functional groups such as hydroxyl, carboxyl, and carbonyl, which enhance their ability for aqueous dispersion.

The synthesis of graphene oxide through the Hummers' method involves the utilisation of graphite powder as a precursor. The process entails the oxidation of graphite powder through the intercalation of sulfate ions, followed by the chemical exfoliation of graphite within a robust oxidising environment. Chemical reagents like sulfuric acid, sodium nitrate, hydrogen peroxide, nitric acid, and potassium permanganate, sourced from Fischer Scientific in analytical grade, were employed in the procedure. The method commenced with the addition of 5g of graphite powder into a beaker, accompanied by the introduction of 2.5g of sodium nitrate into 115 mL of concentrated sulfuric acid (98%). The mixture was subsequently cooled in an ice bath with vigorous stirring. Careful addition of 15g of potassium permanganate was carried out over a span of one hour to prevent any potential hazards. Following the complete addition of potassium permanganate, the mixture was allowed to reach room temperature for three hours before being heated to 35 degrees Celsius for 30 minutes. Addition of 250 mL of deionised water ensued, and the mixture was further heated to 70 degrees Celsius for 15 minutes. Then the mixture was diluted to a final volume of one litre, with the addition of 30 mL of hydrogen peroxide aimed at neutralising any residual potassium permanganate. The graphene oxide was then subjected to centrifugation, washing, and freeze-drying processes. The resultant graphene oxide was dissolved in water and subjected to ultrasound treatment in an alkaline medium for a duration of 6 hours to reduce the particle size effectively. (Smith et al., 2019).

5.6.2 Hummers Method

Experiment 1

A mixture was carefully created by combining specific amounts of graphite powder, sodium nitrate, and sulfuric acid. This mixture was stirred vigorously and then placed in an ice bath to control the temperature. The gradual addition of 300g of Potassium permanganate was crucial

to prevent any temperature spikes above 200 °C. After that, the mixture was left at a specific temperature for 30 minutes, resulting in the formation of a brownish grey paste. Then deionised water was slowly added, causing the temperature to rise to 98 degrees. After that, the mixture was diluted, and 3% hydrogen peroxide was added, resulting in a bright yellow colour change. Filtration produced a yellow-brown cake, which was then washed and dispersed in deionised water. The varying colours in the suspension were indicative of the different oxidation levels achieved during the process. This meticulous procedure underscores the importance of precise handling and controlled conditions in obtaining the desired graphite outcomes.(Hummers and Offeman, 1958)

Prepared graphene oxide

Experiment 2

The process commenced by combining 2g of graphite powder with 46 mL of 98% concentrated sulfuric acid in an ice bath, utilising a magnetic stirrer for thorough mixing. The gradual addition of 6g of potassium permanganate over 30 minutes was carefully executed to maintain the temperature below 20 °C. The mixture was stirred vigorously at 35 degrees for 2 hours.

Then, 92 mL of distilled water was slowly incorporated, ensuring the suspension remained under 100 degrees for 15 minutes. To halt the reaction, 280 mL of 30% hydrogen peroxide was introduced. The resultant graphite oxide paste was subjected to filtration and washed with 500 mL of 10% hydrochloric acid to remove residual salts and metal ions, followed by a rinse with deionised water. A 3g portion of the brown graphite oxide was precisely weighed and dispersed in distilled water while being vigorously stirred in a microwave at 35 degrees. This was followed by the addition of 10% w/w hydrazine to the graphene oxide solution, resulting in a transformation from brown graphene oxide to black graphene. The solution was then filtered to obtain the final graphene paste.(Thema et al., 2013)

5.6.3 Modified Hummer's method

The production process began with the combination of 5 g of graphite, 2.5 g of sodium nitrate, 108 mL of sulfuric acid, and 12 mL of phosphoric acid, followed by thorough stirring in an ice bath for 10 minutes. Gradually introducing 15g of potassium permanganate was critical in preventing any sudden temperature spikes. The mixture was left to undergo a 2-hour reaction in the ice bath, with an additional 60 minutes of stirring. Subsequent temperature adjustments were made, first to 40 degrees and then to 98 degrees, each maintained for 60 minutes. The suspension volume was expanded to 400 mL with deionised water, and 15 mL of hydrogen peroxide was added. The resulting product was washed with 5% hydrochloric acid and centrifuged multiple times before being dried at 60 °C. This intricate process underscores the precision and attention to detail necessary for producing the desired product.(Song et al., 2014)

5.6.4 Improved synthesis methods

3g of graphite flakes, equivalent to 1 weight per cent, were combined with a mixture of sulfuric and phosphoric acids in a 9:1 ratio, totalling 360 mL and 40 mL, respectively. Gradually, 18 g of potassium permanganate was added to the solution, maintaining a temperature below 40 degrees due to the isothermal nature of the reaction. Then, the temperature was raised to 50°C, and the mixture was stirred for 12 hours. To this, 400 mL of ice was added, along with 3 mL of hydrogen peroxide (30%). Following this, the mixture undergoes filtration using a 300-micron filter before being filtered once more using polyester fibre. The resulting graphene oxide was then subjected to centrifugation at 4000 rpm to separate the supernatant. The remaining GO undergo a series of rinses with water, 30% HCl, and ethanol, with each rinse followed by centrifugation at 4000 rpm. Ether was introduced to the filtrate, and the mixture was filtered using a PTFE membrane with a pore size of 0.45 microns. Finally, the GO was vacuum-dried at room temperature to complete the process. (Marcano et al., 2010)

5.7 Characterisation of Graphene Oxide

5.7.1 The Raman spectrum of the graphene oxide

The laser used for excitation had a wavelength of 514.5 nm and an energy of 1.2 mV. A comparison between the Raman spectra of Graphene and Graphene Oxide (GO) was conducted. Research revealed that the characteristic peaks observed at 1355 and 1605 cm⁻¹ for Graphene shifted to 1340 and 1586 cm⁻¹ for Graphene Oxide, with a higher relative intensity. The absence of the 2D band at 2726 cm⁻¹ in GO suggested a complete oxidation of all graphite layers present. (Ferreira et al., 2018; Mohan et al., 2017; Scardaci and Compagnini, 2021; Velázquez et al., 2015)

The intensity of the D band was linked to the level of doping and disorder in the graphite, indicating an influence from graphene functionalisation. The I_d/I_g band intensity ratio reflected structural alterations occurring during the material's preparation. Microcrystalline graphite displayed an I_d/I_g ratio of around 0.1, while exfoliated graphene nanosheets exhibited a ratio of 0.38. The Raman spectroscopy analysis reveals crucial information about the structural properties of graphene and graphene oxide (Amaro-Gahete et al., 2019; Thema et al., 2013)

Figure 101 shows the Raman spectrum made at the university of the west of Scotland of the graphene oxide obtained from the Raman spectroscopy at the UWS (Kim et al., 2014)

D Peak (around 1350 cm^{-1}), The D peak is indicative of defects or disorder within the graphene lattice. When comparing graphene oxide to pristine graphene, it is evident that graphene oxide possesses a disordered structure characterised by sp^3 carbon bonds, contrasting the sp^2 bonds present in pristine graphene. The intensity of the D peak is notably higher in graphene oxide, highlighting the increased concentration of defects within this material. (Kim et al., 2014; Mohan et al., 2017).

G Peak (around 1582 cm^{-1}), The G peak is associated with the stretching mode of C-C bonds within the graphene lattice and is discernible in both graphene and graphene oxide spectra.

2D Peak (around 2700 cm^{-1}), The 2D peak is a result of the second-order Raman scattering process, reflecting in-plane vibrations of C-C bonds. Typically, the 2D peak in graphene appears sharper and more intense compared to that in graphene oxide, due to the higher structural order present in graphene.

The coexistence of D and G peaks confirms the carbon-based nature of the material, characterised by a certain level of structural disorder. The significantly higher intensity of the D peak in comparison to the G peak in graphene oxide indicates a notable presence of defects or disorder within the sample. The broader and less intense 2D peak observed in graphene oxide further underscores the structural defects and disorder inherent in this material. The Raman spectrum depicted aligns with the characteristics of graphene oxide. The presence of the D peak, the relatively elevated D/G peak intensity ratio, and the broadened 2D peak collectively endorse the existence of a disordered carbon structure typical of graphene oxide. These observations substantiate the identification of graphene oxide based on the distinctive features observed in the Raman spectrum analysis.

5.7.2 STEM, EDX

EDX at 10kV:On solid Graphene sample

Figure 102 EDX of Graphene oxide nanoparticles

The EDX spectrum exhibits peaks corresponding to elements such as carbon (C) and oxygen (O), which are the primary components of graphene oxide. The existence of additional peaks may signify the presence of other elements in the sample, such as impurities.

Figure 103 the STEM of the graphene oxide nanoparticles the variation of the diameter is due to that the graphene oxide has the form of platelets

5.7.3 Zeta Potential

Record	Type	Sample Name	Measurement Date and Time	T °C	ZP mV
1	Zeta	GO130522 1	23 November 2022 11:42:29	25.0	-0.101
2	Zeta	GO130522 1	23 November 2022 11:47:09	25.0	-47.1
3	Zeta	GO130522 2	23 November 2022 11:48:18	25.1	-47.8
4	Zeta	GO130522 3	23 November 2022 11:48:58	25.0	-47.9
5	Zeta	GO130522 1	23 November 2022 12:01:17	25.0	-42.6
6	Zeta	GO130522 2	23 November 2022 12:02:26	25.0	-45.6
7	Zeta	GO130522 3	23 November 2022 12:03:14	25.0	-46.4
27	Zeta	Go24112022 1	24 November 2022 15:00:21	25.0	-45.0
28	Zeta	Go24112022 2	24 November 2022 15:01:30	25.0	-48.3
29	Zeta	Go24112022 3	24 November 2022 15:02:10	25.0	-51.0
30	Zeta	Go24112022 1	24 November 2022 15:05:13	24.9	-47.7

Record	Type	Sample Name	Measurement Date and Time	T °C	ZP mV
6	Zeta	GO 2 g/L in water 1	02 March 2023 11:15:12	25.0	-48.8
7	Zeta	GO 2 g/L in water 2	02 March 2023 11:18:19	25.0	-49.0
8	Zeta	GO 2 g/L in water 3	02 March 2023 11:18:59	25.0	-51.8

Figure 104 shows the zeta potential results for graphene oxide nanofluid

The graphene oxide nanofluid was very stable, as the zeta potential was around -50, which indicates a net strong negative charge on the graphene oxide surface, as shown in **Error! Reference source not found**. That shows the zeta potential distribution of multiple runs lies around -50. This indicated excellent stability. The nanofluid remains stable for over one year during the PhD.

5.7.4 Size distribution

Figure 105: Size distribution of graphene oxide nanoparticles

Results

	Size (d.nm)	% Number:	St Dev (d.nm)
Z-Average (d.nm): 358.5	Peak 1: 137.8	100.0	20.05
Pdl: 0.549	Peak 2: 0.000	0.0	0.000
Intercept: 1.02	Peak 3: 0.000	0.0	0.000
Result quality Refer to quality report			

Figure 106 Polydispersity of graphene oxide

Upon examination, the determination of the size distribution of graphene oxide posed a challenge due to its nanoparticle exhibiting a platelet shape. Since the zetasizer apparatus cannot differentiate between various nanoparticle shapes, the average hydrodynamic diameter may not accurately represent graphene oxide in its proper form, which is platelets. As the platelets undergo rotation, the detected hydrodynamic diameter may be inaccurate.

5.8 Summary

This chapter focuses on the preparation, features, and analytical techniques used for the characterisation of silica, titania, alumina, and graphene oxide nanoparticles. Several methods, including Raman spectroscopy, FTIR, DLS, STEM, XRD, EDX, and zeta potential measurements, were used to investigate the nanoparticles. The synthesis of graphene oxide using variants of the Hummers approach was investigated in great detail. The characterisation results, including Raman spectra, STEM images, EDX spectra, FTIR spectra, zeta potential, and size distribution, are presented for every type of nanoparticle. The chapter emphasises the need for these analytical methods in understanding the properties and behaviour of nanoparticles in nanofluids.

5.9 References Chapter 5

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Chapter 6

Thermal Conductivity Measurement Using Transient Hot Wire Device

6.1 Introduction

The thermal conductivity measuring apparatus market offers a diverse range of equipment designed to assess the thermal conductivities of various materials. The applicability of these devices is influenced by the thermal characteristics and the operating temperature range of the materials being tested. The market comprises equipment such as heat flow apparatus, hot plate apparatus, hot wire apparatus, and flash apparatus, catering to both academic research and industrial applications. The application of thermal conductivity measuring apparatus extends across multiple sectors. In material science, these devices play a crucial role in analysing and understanding the thermal properties of different materials. They are also essential in thermal engineering, aiding in the efficient design and optimization of thermal systems. Additionally, these apparatuses contribute to the development and assessment of building materials, ensuring optimal thermal performance in construction and infrastructure projects. The versatility of these devices is further highlighted by their utilisation in various other fields, demonstrating their adaptability and potential for cross-industry applications. The market's competitive landscape is shaped by several key players who have established themselves as influential contributors. Adev, AMETEK Process Instruments, Emerson Automation Solutions, ExtraSolution, Hitech Instruments, Labthink Instruments, Linseis Thermal Analysis, Michell Instruments, Rubotherm, and Steam Equipment are among the best companies in the market. Each brings unique expertise, technological advancements, and innovative solutions, collectively driving industry advancement and fostering competition.

It is also worth mentioning that the market for transient hot-wire devices is relatively small and specialised, with only a few companies focusing on this specific technology. This limited market presence may impact the availability and accessibility of these devices to researchers

and industries that rely on them. Online research for transient hot wire devices shows two manufacturers: Thermtest, based in Sweden, and Flucon, located in Germany. These manufacturers offer specialised transient hot wire devices for specific applications, as indicated by the provided links. (Intellect) (INSIGHTS, 2023) (Research) (“Global Thermal Conductivity Measurement Market by Type) (marketresearchupdate) (Thermal Conductivity Market Research Report,) (“Thermal Conductive Material Market, Global Outlook and Forecast 2023-2029,”)

Online investigations indicate that the majority of manufacturers producing thermal conductivity equipment do not offer transient hot-wire devices for sale. The market for transient hot wire devices is limited to only three manufacturers. One of these companies, Thermtest, is located in Sweden. Their product can be found at this link: [<https://jetmaterials.com/product/transient-hot-wire-thw-11/>]. The second manufacturer, Flucon, is located in Germany. Additional details about their product can be accessed via this link: [<https://flucon.de/en/products/thermal-conductivity-system-lambda/>]. The third is C-Therm, based in Canada [<https://ctherm.com/>]. (“Transient Hot-Wire (THW-L1) – Jet Materials,” n.d.) (“LAMBDA Thermal Conductivity Meter | flucon GmbH,” n.d.) (“C-Therm Thermal Conductivity Instruments,” n.d.)

Figure 107 A shows the transient hot wire device manufactured by C-Therm, whereas B shows the lambda device produced by Falcon Germany. C shows the transient hot wire sensor. The sensor operates based on the principle of heat conduction from a thin, electrically heated wire immersed in the test medium.

The use of nanofluids is a promising alternative to traditional heat-transfer fluids, offering enhanced thermal performance and efficiency. By incorporating nanoparticles into a base fluid, nanofluids can exhibit significantly enhanced thermal conductivity, enabling more efficient heat transfer and reduced energy consumption. This innovative approach has the potential to revolutionise various industries, including electronic cooling and power generation, in which heat transfer is a critical component. The properties of nanofluids, such as their high thermal conductivity, make them an attractive option for applications in which traditional heat-transfer fluids have low efficiency. Therefore, the use of nanofluids can lead to reduced material costs, increased system efficiency, and improved environmental sustainability, making them an attractive solution for industries seeking to optimise their heat transfer processes. Heat-transfer fluids play a crucial role in influencing the cost, reliability, and performance of heating and

cooling systems. This project aims to evaluate alternative heat transfer fluids, including nanomaterials, surfactants, and polymer additives, as potential substitutes for traditional fluids such as water and ethylene glycol. The focus was to evaluate the thermal energy transfer performance of these newly formulated fluids in domestic heating applications. Additionally, the project includes experiments on both small-scale box heating and large-scale building heating using nanofluid and surfactant formulations.

The thermal properties of fluids have been extensively studied in recent years, with a focus on understanding the effects of nanomaterials, surfactants, and polymer additives on their behaviour. Research has shown that incorporating nanoparticles, such as carbon nanotubes and graphene, can significantly enhance the thermal conductivity of fluids. (Hong et al., 2007). Similarly, surfactants have been found to improve the stability and dispersion of nanoparticles in fluids, leading to improved thermal performance (Hong et al., 2020; Jiang et al., 2003) These findings provide a solid foundation for the research presented in this paper, which aims to investigate the effects of nanomaterials, surfactants, and polymer additives on the thermal properties of fluids.

The idea of utilising nanofluids for heat transfer has been inspired by recent advancements in nanotechnology, and previous studies have established that nanoparticles can enhance the heat transfer coefficient of base fluids such as water, alcohol, ethylene glycol, and transformer oils. Numerous studies have employed computational fluid dynamics (CFD) simulations, utilising tools such as Ansys Fluent and other CFD software, to investigate heat transfer enhancement. (Akademia Baru and Lee, 2014; Akbari et al., 2011; Lee, 2014)

The primary objective of this research is to investigate the thermal performance of nanofluids and surfactant formulations in comparison with that of traditional heat transfer fluids.

Specifically, this study aims to compare the thermal conductivity of nanofluids formulated with different types of nanoparticles with that of traditional heat transfer fluids.

Evaluating the heat transfer capability of a fluid involves examining various properties, with thermal conductivity being the most significant. Thermal conductivity measurement methods can be categorised into two groups: steady-state and unsteady-state (or transient) techniques, as shown in Figure 108. The transient technique has been gaining prominence for determining fluid thermal conductivity, helping to minimise the errors associated with convection heat transfer. This group includes methods such as the thermal constant analyser, transient plane source, 3-Omega method, and transient hot-wire method. (Bhardwaj and Khare, 2022).

The transient hot wire method, known for its accuracy and reliability, has been widely used. (Sh. Azarfar et al., 2016). It was first introduced by Stalhane and Pyk in 1931 for evaluating the thermal conductivity of powders. (Marc J. Assael et al., 2010a; Paul et al., 2010). Haarman later applied it to liquids by using an automatic Wheatstone bridge. Gillman refined this technique for liquids by incorporating a Kelvin bridge into the circuit to enhance the accuracy. Healy further extended the use of the transient hot-wire method to measure the thermal conductivities of gases. (Healy et al., 1976). Currently, this method is extensively applied to assess the thermal conductivity of various substances, including nanofluids, fluid mixtures, ionic nanofluids, and aqueous and non-aqueous solutions, under a range of temperature and pressure conditions, reaching up to 800°C and 400 atm. (Sh. Azarfar et al., 2016).

Nagasaka and Nagashima developed a method to measure the thermal conductivity of conductive fluids such as NaCl solutions by applying an electrically insulating layer to a thin wire. (Nagasaka and Nagashima, 1981). In 2016, Azarfar introduced an innovative device for the transient hot-wire technique, which heats the wire using direct current and measures the resistance through an alternating current. (Sh. Azarfar et al., 2016).

In determining fluid thermal conductivity, a thin wire immersed in the fluid is subjected to a current, resulting in Joule heating and a consequent temperature rise. The resulting instantaneous resistance change was detected and recorded using an analogue-to-digital converter (ADC). This change in resistance manifests as a variation in the voltage over time. The measurement duration is typically estimated to be between 4 s and 6 s, which is sufficiently rapid to mitigate the effects of natural convection. In this study, a transient hot-wire device was calibrated using glycerol, chosen for its nearly constant thermal conductivity at room temperature, thus reducing the calibration errors related to ambient temperature fluctuations. Additional validation was conducted using water, alcohol, propanol, propan-2-ol, and ethylene glycol. The calibrated device was then employed to evaluate the thermal conductivities of various surfactant solutions and nanofluids. (Assael et al., 2002, 2015; Sh. Azarfar et al., 2016; Beck et al., 2010; Kawaguchi et al., 1985; Lee et al., 1999; Nagasaka and Nagashima, 1981; Ramires et al., 1994)

Figure 108 Methods for thermal conductivity measurement (Paul et al., 2010b)

Nanofluids have demonstrated considerable enhancement in heat transfer. After reviewing the literature on this topic, graphene oxide was selected because of its notable stability, solubility, high thermal conductivity, and cost-effectiveness. Graphene oxide was synthesised using Hummer's method and then dispersed in water using ultrasound. (Arshad et al., 2019; Cai et al., 2012; Esfahani et al., 2016; Kanti et al., 2022; Lotya et al., 2013; Poh et al., 2012; Wlazlak et al., 2019; Yu et al., 2010). Additionally, various surfactants were examined to explore their impact on enhancing the thermal conductivity of the water. Aqueous solutions of surfactants such as sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS), cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB), tetrabutylammonium bromide (TBAB), and alkyl polyglucoside might enhance the thermal conductivity of the base fluid. Experiments were conducted to assess the variation in the thermal conductivity of aqueous surfactant solutions at different concentrations. The objective was to ascertain the optimal surfactant concentration to maximise the thermal conductivity of water. Surfactant solutions were prepared at concentrations around the critical micelle concentration (CMC) to investigate the effect of concentration on thermal conductivity. This research also aims to determine and identify the most effective nanofluid or surfactant type and categorise the most efficacious surfactants (anionic, cationic, non-ionic, or APGs) for thermal conductivity enhancement. The surfactants and nanofluids under investigation were SDS, CTAB, TBAB, polyvinylpyrrolidone, Tween 80, alkyl polyglucoside, alumina, silica, titania, and graphene oxide.

Accurately determining the thermal conductivity of a material is crucial for assessing its thermal performance and, consequently, its appropriateness for specific uses. Various techniques exist for determining the thermal conductivity of a material, but the transient hot-wire method stands out for its straightforwardness and versatility for different materials. This method can provide precise readings for gases, liquids, and solids across a broad range of thermal conductivities. Therefore, this method is among the most commonly employed.

High-cost thermal conductivity meters are a significant barrier in the field. This research also focused on developing a cost-effective lab-made thermal conductivity measuring device using easily accessible commercial components. The transient hot-wire technique is a precise method for measuring thermal conductivity, known for its low uncertainty and wide range of applications. This technique involves applying a step change in voltage to a thin metallic wire and observing the rate at which its temperature increases over time. This allows the calculation of the thermal conductivity of the medium surrounding the wire. Modern instruments utilise highly accurate, automatic electronic bridges and finite-element methods to achieve extremely low uncertainty. Stålhane and Pyk (1931) and Haarman (1971) employed this technique in different applications. The concept of using a hot wire for thermal experiments dates back to Joseph Priestley's work in 1781. Priestley was probably the first to conduct experiments to measure the "power of gases to conduct heat," which was unknown at the time. His work was followed by Count Rumford (Sir Benjamin Thomson) in 1786, who examined "the conductive power of artificial airs or gases." Rumford concluded that gases were unable to conduct heat, a statement that had not been challenged for many years due to his reputation. In 1804, Sir John Leslie criticised Rumford's conclusion, stating that if fluids were incapable of conducting heat, they could never become heated. Debate on the conduction of gases has continued for several decades. In the mid-19th century, Sir William Robert Grove presented an experiment demonstrating that a platinum wire cooled far below its incandescence point when immersed in hydrogen gas. This led to more experiments with heated wires in gases. (Marc J. Assael et al., 2010b). In 1861, Professor Gustav Magnus reported that platinum wire is less heated by galvanic current when surrounded by hydrogen than when it is in atmospheric air or any other gas. This led to the belief that hydrogen conducts heat better than all the other gases. However, the debate was not settled until James Clerk Maxwell and Rudolf Julius Emanuel Clausius

provided theoretical insights into the thermal conductivity of gases, demonstrating its dependence on temperature and pressure.

One of the first instruments to measure the thermal conductivity of gases was developed by Josef Stefan in 1872, called the "diathermometer." The apparatus consists of two concentric cylinders made of brass. Stefan developed an equation to describe the heat transfer in this arrangement, allowing the thermal conductivity of the gas to be deduced from measurements of the gas pressure in the inner cylinder over time. Stefan's work paved the way for Schleiermacher, who set out to measure the thermal conductivity of gases using a platinum hot wire. His instrument was composed of a horizontal platinum wire of 0.4 mm diameter and 32 cm length, placed in the centre of a glass cylinder. The period from 1781 to 1888 was crucial for the development of the transient hot wire technique. This was a time of significant debate, experimentation, and theoretical development. The work of early scientists like Priestley, Rumford, Leslie, Grove, Magnus, Maxwell, Clausius, Stefan, and Schleiermacher laid the foundation for the modern transient hot-wire technique used for measuring the thermal conductivity of various materials. (Marc J. Assael et al., 2010b)

To measure thermal conductivity, a thin wire was submerged in the fluid and heated electrically. The change in the resistance of the wire was recorded, allowing for quick measurements that minimised errors due to natural convection. The apparatus was calibrated using glycerol, as glycerol has a thermal conductivity that does not change significantly with temperature and is validated using other fluids.

6.2 Theoretical foundation for the hot wire method

The Transient Hot Wire (THW) method is a widely used technique for measuring the thermal conductivities of various materials, including liquids, gases, and solids. It is known for its

accuracy, simplicity, and ability to measure thermal conductivity over a wide range of temperatures and pressures. The THW method is widely used in research to study the thermal properties of new materials, including nanofluids and gases, under different pressures. It is also used in industry for quality control and material testing. The versatility and precision of the THW method make it a valuable tool in both academic research and industrial applications. The THW method operates based on the principle of a thin wire acting as both a heater and a temperature sensor. This wire was embedded in a material whose thermal conductivity must be measured. When an electric current passes through the wire, it heats up and transfers heat to the surrounding material. The temperature of the wire increases, and this increase is monitored over time. The rate of temperature increase is directly related to the thermal conductivity of the surrounding material. The temperature increase in the wire is recorded as a function of time. The thermal conductivity of the material can then be calculated by analysing the temperature-time curve using the solution to the heat conduction equation. The THW method is highly accurate and can be used for a wide range of materials, particularly fluids and gases, for which other methods may struggle. It is also a relatively quick method, with measurements typically taking a few seconds.

A standard hot-wire arrangement usually has a vertical configuration in which the wire functions as both a heat source and a temperature sensor. Platinum wire is commonly the material of choice for this role, but other metals can be used with certain limitations. The foundational mathematical framework seeks to emulate an endless vertical heat line within an infinite surrounding medium. This approach is called "transient" because the power is applied abruptly, and the data collection period is relatively brief. The control equation is based on a specific solution that originates from Fourier's law. The advantage of employing a linear, infinitely long, and thin heat source relative to its diameter lies in its approximation as an element with infinite thermal conductivity, negligible heat capacity, and zero heat generation.

This scenario corresponds to a one-dimensional transient heat conduction process within a cylindrical wire with a radius of r . The thickness of this wire is denoted as r , and the thickness of the element is Δr . The material properties of the wire include the density (ρ), specific heat capacity (C_p), length (L), and area of heat transfer ($A=2\pi rL$), as heat conduction occurs radially. In the case of a cylindrical metal wire, the situation involves transient heat conduction without heat generation, given that the wire's thinness prevents notable temperature fluctuations or energy generation. The key equation for transient heat transfer is a partial differential equation that outlines how the temperature changes with respect to both position and time. The equation was designed for infinite slabs, cylinders, and spheres. (Sh. Azarfar et al., 2016) (Çengel and Ghajar, 2015). The thickness of the cylinder is r , the considered element thickness is Δr , the cylinder material density is ρ , the cylinder material's specific heat is C_p , the cylinder length is L . The area of heat transfer is $A = 2\pi rL$ as radial conduction occurs (Nagasaka and Nagashima, 1981) (Sh. Azarfar et al., 2016). In the case of a thin metallic wire, there is transient heat conduction with no heat generation, as the wire is so thin that the temperature variation through it or the energy loss inside the wire can be neglected. The governing equation of the transient heat transfer is a partial differential equation which describes the change in temperature with respect to location and time, 6- is identified for an infinite slab, infinite cylinder and sphere.(Sh. Azarfar et al., 2016)

$$\frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r \frac{\partial T}{\partial r} \right) = \frac{1}{\alpha_d} \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} \quad 6-1$$

α_d is the thermal diffusivity of the material $\alpha_d = \frac{k}{\rho C_p}$ Where k is the thermal conductivity, ρ is the density and C_p It is the specific heat capacity of the material. r is the location (in one direction, radial direction for cylinder), t is time, and T is the temperature (Sh. Azarfar et al., 2016) (Lee et al., 1999)

$$\frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = \frac{k}{\rho C_p r^n} r^n \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial r} \right) \left(\frac{\partial T}{\partial r} \right) \quad 6-2$$

The partial differential 6- Could be resolved in the case of the transient hot wire (considered as an infinite cylinder), $n = 1$, so the solution will be 6-

$$\frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = \frac{k}{\rho C_p r} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial r} \right) r \left(\frac{\partial T}{\partial r} \right) \quad 6-3$$

The boundary and initial conditions in the case of the hot wire are

1. At $t > 0$ and $r = 0$ leading to $\lim_{r \rightarrow 0} \left[r \left(\frac{\partial T}{\partial r} \right) \right] = -\frac{q}{2\pi k_f}$
2. At $t \geq 0$ and $r = \infty$ leading to $\lim_{r \rightarrow \infty} (\Delta T(r, t)) = 0$
3. $T(r, 0) = T_0$
4. $\frac{\partial T(0, t)}{\partial r} = 0$

The solution of 6- . is obtained using the defined boundary conditions.

$$\Delta T(r, t) = \frac{q}{4\pi k_f} Ei \left(\frac{-r^2}{4\alpha_f t} \right) \quad 6-4$$

As Ei is the exponential integral function 6- could be written as

$$T(r_0, t) - T_0 = \frac{q}{4\pi k_f} \left[\text{Ln} \left(\frac{4\alpha t}{r_0^2 C} \right) + \frac{r_0^2}{4\alpha t} + \dots \right] \quad 6-5$$

Consider that $\ln C = \beta$, which is the Euler constant. $\beta = 0.5772$

$$\Delta T(r, t) = \frac{q}{4\pi k_f} \left[-\beta + \text{Ln} \left(\frac{4\alpha_f t}{r^2} \right) \right] \quad 6-6$$

Considering that $\frac{r_0^2}{4\alpha t}$ If approaching zero in higher orders then. 6- leads to 6-

$$\Delta T_2 - \Delta T_1 = \frac{q}{4\pi k_f} \text{Ln} \left(\frac{t_2}{t_1} \right) \quad 6-7$$

The mathematical model of a transient hot wire is based on the equation of radial heat conduction in an infinite cylinder (Cengal & Ghajar, 2014). Several studies have examined this model in detail. The final and simplest derived equation for the thermal conductivity measurement is given by 6-.

$$\Delta T_2 - \Delta T_1 = \left(\frac{q}{4\pi k_f} \right) (\ln t_2 - \ln t_1) \quad 6-8$$

q is the heat energy supplied per unit length per unit of time, ΔT is the temperature increment, t is time, k_f It is the fluid thermal conductivity. Equation 6-8 is used to plot the change in the temperature increment against the natural logarithm of time. The result is a straight line with a slope equal to $\frac{q}{4\pi k_f}$. In 6- The thermal conductivity is the only unknown.

The thermal conductivity of the fluid was determined using. 6- From which the slope was derived.

In the experiments, the measurement duration ranged from 6 to 14 seconds. However, for the calculations, only the initial 6 s were considered, as indicated in the $d\Delta T$ vs. $\ln(t)$ graph. This is because the behaviour of the liquids deviates from a linear pattern after that point, owing to the onset of convection. The temperature and viscosity of the fluid influenced the extent to which free convection occurred. (Sh. Azarfar et al., 2016)

$$\frac{\Delta T_2 - \Delta T_1}{\ln t_2 - \ln t_1} = \frac{q}{4\pi k_f} \quad 6-9$$

$$k_f = \frac{q}{4\pi * slope} \quad 6-10$$

Determination of the thermal conductivity of fluids involves six steps.

1. Determination of the temperature resistance coefficient of the wire
2. Determination of the initial wire resistance at bridge null conditions
3. Determination of the wire's instantaneous resistance
4. Determination of the wire's instantaneous temperature
5. Determination of the thermal energy supplied to the wire.
6. Determination of thermal conductivity of the medium

The Temperature Resistance Coefficient (TRC) plays a vital role in this study. Accurate data on the temperature of the wire derived from its electrical resistance is essential. Although previous studies have documented the TRC of thin platinum wire, it is important to confirm this experimentally. This is because the precision of the temperature measurements for the wire can be affected by fluctuations in the TRC, which may arise from differences in the purity of the platinum wire used.

To calculate the Temperature Resistance Coefficient (TRC), an experiment was conducted to measure the resistance of the platinum wire at different temperatures. A linear graph was plotted to represent the relationship between the resistance and temperature, and Excel was used to determine the slope of the graph. As a result, the TRC for the platinum wire utilised in this research was found to be $0.003754 K^{-1}$.

6.3 Circuit simulation and signal shape using MATLAB.

There are several methods for creating a hot-wire circuit. The simplest were simulated in Figure 109 and Figure 112. Figure 109 Shows the first circuit when the Wheatstone bridge is supplied by direct current for wire heating and resistance detection. The bridge gain was then measured using an oscilloscope. Figure 112 Shows the second circuit, when the bridge is supplied with alternating current for resistance detection and the wire is supplied with direct current for Joule heating. An oscilloscope then sensed the alternating current to evaluate the change in resistance as the wire temperature increased.

6.3.1 The hot-wire circuit uses direct current (DC).

The first circuit in Figure 109 was inspired by Choi (Lee et al., 1999), which was composed of a wire and three resistors to compose the bridge, and then attached to an amplifier and an oscilloscope.

Simulations were performed using the Simscape library in Simulink. The results of the simulation in Figure 110 Show the required signal from the circuit in red, whereas the blue signal is the input signal. The input signal was the DC current, whereas the bridge gain was a rising signal.

Figure 109: Simulink-Based Circuit Simulation of a Transient Hot Wire System for Thermal Conductivity Measurement

Figure 110: First circuit simulation of the Transient hot wire circuit with DC bridge simulation using Simulink. The Heat Flow Circuit is responsible for simulating or facilitating the heat transfer process. It includes an 8V power supply and a switch for activation, providing the necessary energy to heat the Pt wire. The Wheatstone Bridge incorporates the Pt wire, which acts as a temperature-sensitive resistor (RTD). As the wire heats up, its resistance changes, unbalancing the bridge. The bridge, powered by a DC supply, generates a small differential

voltage proportional to this resistance shift. A potentiometer (R_{pot}) allows for initial calibration, balancing the bridge before measurements begin. Since the output from the Wheatstone Bridge is very small, an Instrumentation Amplifier is used to boost the signal while maintaining high common-mode rejection, ensuring precision. This amplifier typically follows a three-op-amp configuration to set the gain for optimal signal amplification. In the Signal Sensing stage, the amplified voltage, which corresponds to the temperature rise of the Pt wire, is measured. Using this data, along with the theoretical equations of the Transient Hot Wire Method, the thermal conductivity of the material can be accurately calculated. This entire process ensures reliable and precise thermal property measurements.

Figure 110: Simulation Results of the Transient Hot Wire Circuit: DC Bridge Input and Amplified Output in Simulink.

Figure 111 shows The result of the circuit simulation for the first circuit. The DC bridge input signal and the op-amp output signal (Simulink). The simulation would allow users to input parameters like the material thermal conductivity, observe the temperature rise of the Pt wire over time, and analyse how the Wheatstone Bridge and amplifier respond. This is particularly

useful for studying system behaviour and material properties, without the need for physical prototyping

Figure 111 The actual signal shape on the oscilloscope.

6.3.2 The hot wire circuit using alternating and direct current DC/AC circuit

The second circuit was based on Azarfar. (S. Azarfar et al., 2016). The circuit concept is based on using both an alternating current for resistance sensing and a direct current for heating the wire. The wire heating is completely isolated from the Wheatstone bridge circuit using coupling capacitors to prevent direct current flow through the Wheatstone bridge circuit. The alternating current is the only current flowing in the four bridge arms; thus, the null condition is reached using the AC. As the resistance of the wire changes owing to heating, the AC starts to flow through the Wheatstone bridge and is then amplified by the amplifier. The changes were then recorded using an oscilloscope.

Figure 112: Circuit simulation of the Transient hot wire circuit with AC bridge simulation using Simulink. The same circuit as before, while using the AC current to determine the resistance of the wire.

Figure 113: Simulation Results of the AC Bridge-Based Transient Hot Wire Circuit in Simulink

Figure 114: The result of the circuit simulation for the second circuit. The AC bridge input signal is in red, and the op-amp output signal is in blue (Simulink). The change in the AC voltage can be used for the calculation of the thermal conductivity of the material.

6.4 The transient hot wire Device

6.4.1 Determination of the Temperature Resistance Coefficient of the Wire

The temperature resistance coefficient was a critical parameter in this experiment. It is important to obtain accurate information about the wire temperature from its electrical resistance. Other studies have reported the temperature resistance coefficient of thin platinum wires, but it is important to find it experimentally because the accuracy of the wire temperature is affected by the deviation of the temperature resistance coefficient due to the level of purity of the platinum wire.

To determine the temperature resistance coefficient (TRC), an experiment was conducted by measuring the resistance of a platinum wire at different temperatures. A straight line representing the relationship between resistance and temperature was plotted. The slope was determined using Excel, and the TRC was calculated. The TRC of the used platinum wire was 0.003754 K^{-1}

The experimental temperature resistance coefficient was lower than that observed in other studies, which could be related to the purity of the supplied wire. However, even the error that arises from the slight variation in TRC is small.

Figure 114 The temperature resistance relationship for platinum wire (hot wire) determined experimentally

6.4.2 Determination of the wire's instantaneous and initial Resistance

Figure 115. The whole circuit is composed of the wire as an arm in a Wheatstone bridge connected to an amplifier, then the amplifier is connected to an oscilloscope to visualise and store the signal

The instantaneous rate of change in the resistance of the thin wire was determined using a digital storage oscilloscope as the time rate of change against the bridge gain. The signal information was gathered as a CSV file. The resulting CSV file contained two vectors

representing voltage vs. time. In most cases, the voltage obtained may be noisy. Depending on the signal-to-noise ratio, it may be necessary to filter the noise to obtain correct results. Then, the curve is normalised to the origin, as the voltage vector presents the amplified bridge gain. This should be recalculated to obtain the actual bridge gain (considering the amplifier gain and error), and the actual bridge gain should then be recalculated to determine the wire resistance. The wire resistance should then be transformed into a change in the wire resistance by subtracting the initial wire resistance. The change in wire resistance is transformed into a change in wire temperature, and the time vector is transformed into the natural logarithm of time. A straight line was obtained by plotting the increment in temperature against the natural logarithm of time. The slope of the straight line represents the thermal conductivity of the fluid. The output signal of the oscilloscope is an amplified bridge gain voltage versus time, obtained by dividing the voltage for each point by the gain of the instrumental amplifier, as determined from 6-. The gain of the amplifier is calculated according to the datasheet, as each amplifier has its own gain equation.

$$V_{bridge\ Gain} = \frac{V_{oscilloscope}}{Gain_{amplifier}} \quad 6-11$$

$V_{bridge\ Gain}$ Is the real bridge gain? $V_{oscilloscope}$ Is the oscilloscope's amplified signal, $Gain_{amplifier}$ The gain of the instrumental amplifier should be calculated using the data sheets of the amplifier.

The initial resistance of the wire is determined under bridge balance conditions, where $V_{right} = V_{left}$, leading to a bridge output voltage of zero, which is a null condition. The instantaneous value of the wire resistance was obtained using the Equation. 6-. Equation 6- It is driven by the bridge gain and arm resistance relationship. R_{wire} Is the thin wire's instantaneous resistance? R_{20}, R_{1000} Are the bridge fixed resistances $R_{potentiometer}$ Is the variable resistor

used for the bridge balancing to null condition, G is the bridge real gain voltage, and V_{in} is the input voltage for the bridge.

$$R_{0\ wire} = \frac{R_{20} * R_{potentiometer}}{R_{1000}} \quad 6-12$$

$$R_t = R_{wire} = \frac{\left(\left(\frac{G}{V_S} \right) + \left(\frac{R_{pot}}{(R_{1000} + R_{pot})} \right) \right) * R_{20}}{1 - \left(\left(\frac{G}{V_S} \right) + \left(\frac{R_{pot}}{(R_{1000} + R_{pot})} \right) \right)} \quad 6-13$$

6.4.3 Determination of the instantaneous wire temperature

The transient hot-wire principle involves the use of a slender metallic wire as both a heat source and a resistance thermometer. The resistance of this thin wire increases as its temperature increases, a phenomenon utilized in Resistance Temperature Detection (RTD) sensors, which are prevalent in various industries. The wire temperature can be deduced from its resistance using a specific equation, as detailed in the literature. (S. Azarfar et al., 2016; Nagasaka and Nagashima, 1981). The initial and instantaneous resistances of the wire, denoted as R_0 and R_t , respectively, played a crucial role in these calculations. Various metals, such as copper, nickel, and tantalum, are used for the wire, each with distinct properties and temperature-resistance coefficients. Platinum is often preferred due to the linear correlation between its resistance and temperature changes, exhibiting a temperature resistance coefficient of $0.0039092\ K^{-1}$ as per Choi, Li, and Eastman (1999), compared to $0.00385\ K^{-1}$ for copper.

When the wire is submerged in a fluid with a certain thermal conductivity and an electric current is passed through it, it undergoes Joule heating. The rate of temperature increase in the wire depended on the thermal conductivity of the medium. In a medium with higher thermal

conductivity (such as medium A), the temperature of the wire increases more slowly compared to a medium with lower conductivity (such as medium B). Simultaneously, as the wire heats up, its resistance increases owing to the increase in temperature. However, the cooling effect exerted by the fluid medium is also significant, with fluids having a higher thermal conductivity leading to quicker cooling of the wire.

For precise resistance measurement, integrating a thin wire into a Wheatstone or Kelvin bridge is essential. This is because of the direct linear relationship between the bridge gain and wire resistance.

$$T_{\text{wire at time } t} = \left(\frac{(R_t - R_0)}{R_0 \alpha} \right) + T_0 \quad 6-14$$

$$\Delta T_{\text{wire at time } t} = T_{\text{wire}} - T_0 = \left(\frac{(R_T - R_0)}{R_0 \alpha} \right) \quad 6-15$$

The temperature of the wire at any given time can be determined using 6-. The heat rate generated in the wire per unit length is equal to the electrical power divided by the wire length. Equation 6-17 It is calculated using the simple voltage divider rule. q is the rate of heat generated per unit length owing to the current passing through the thin wire, and q is the electrical power, which is obtained by multiplying the passing current and voltage drop through the thin wire. V_{in} Is the input voltage to the bridge, R_{wire} is the thin wire average resistance over the experiment period (the error is negligible) (S. Azarfar *et al.*, 2016b). L_{wire} Is the thin wire length and R_{20} Is the resistance in the Wheatstone bridge at the same arm of the thin wire. The relationship between the supplied thermal energy and the time onset of the natural convection is equal to $q^{-\frac{1}{2}}$ 6- So by decreasing the power, the natural convection onset time will be delayed (S. Azarfar *et al.*, 2016).

$$\text{time onset of the natural convection} = q^{-\frac{1}{2}} \quad 6-16$$

6.4.4 Determination of the heat supplied to the wire per unit length.

The power dissipated from the wire (q) is calculated using e

$$q = \frac{V_{\text{wire}}^2}{R_{\text{wire}}} \quad 6-17$$

$$q = \frac{1}{L_w} \frac{V_{\text{in}}^2 * R_0}{(R_{20} + R_0)^2} \quad 6-18$$

The heat generated per unit time per unit length q . Obtained from 6-

The voltage drop through the wire multiplied by the current flowing in the thin wire multiplied by the time gives the energy responsible for the Joule heating of the thin wire. The power required for Joule heating is equal to the heating energy per unit time per unit length.

It should be taken into consideration that the starting time of the natural convection is proportional to the $q^{-0.5}$. The reduction of the power supplied will prevent the interference of the natural convection in the calculation, ensuring that the natural convection is delayed (S. Azarfar *et al.*, 2016a). In such a case, it is possible to get a linear relationship between ΔT and $\ln t$. q : Is the time rate of energy dissipation per unit length.

6.4.5 Determination of the thermal conductivity of the fluid

Thermal conductivity was determined using. 6-

$$k_f = \left(\frac{\ln t_2 - \ln t_1}{\Delta T_2 - \Delta T_1} \right) * \frac{q}{4\pi} \quad 6-19$$

T_2 is the wire temperature at time t_2 and T_1 is the initial wire temperature at time t_1 or time zero. ΔT_2 is the temperature difference. $\Delta T_2 = T_2 - T_0$, $\Delta T_1 = T_1 - T_0$, as T_0 is the initial temperature.

$$k_f = \frac{q}{4\pi * slope} \quad 6-20$$

6.4.6 The Hot wire device components

The hot-wire device itself was simple. It consists of a thin platinum wire that acts as a sensor and is suspended within a plastic frame. To ensure that the electrical resistance changed linearly, a bridge circuit was included. Following the bridge, a signal amplifier was used to boost the weak signals produced during the experiment. Finally, the amplified signal must be converted from an analogue to a digital format. This can be done using an oscilloscope, a minicomputer such as a Raspberry Pi, or a microcontroller board such as an Arduino. The processed signal can then be analyzed using software, such as MATLAB, Excel, or Python.

6.4.7 Platinum wire support frame.

Figure 116A shows the first sensor frame as the platinum wire was hung in a rectangular plastic frame, while the bridge was soldered on a PCB, as shown in Figure 116 B. Figure 117 shows the second attempt for sensor manufacturing as was made using 3D printing.

The developed device includes a thin-wire sensor, as shown in Figure 120. Then, the third attempt frame was made using metallic rods. Because the metallic rods were subjected to rusting, a PCB cell was created using open-source CAD software (KICAD). A thin wire was connected from both sides using 1 mm copper wires.

Figure 116 A is the first sensor frame, as shown, and B is the first Wheatstone bridge with the amplifier

Figure 117 shows a 3D-printed sensor frame.

Other metals can be used as thin wires, but the choice of platinum is based on several factors. The temperature coefficient of resistance of the metal should be linear and sufficiently large to accurately sense temperature variations. Platinum wire exhibits an elevated temperature coefficient of resistance and a linear relationship between resistance and temperature over a wide range, as previously mentioned. The transient hot-wire device is composed of a metal wire hung in the middle of a printed circuit cell, as shown in Figure 120. A Teflon-coated Pt wire was used as the metal wire. The temperature-resistance relationship of the platinum metal wire was perfectly linear for the desired temperature range. The platinum wire resistance was sufficient to ensure accuracy, as the change in the resistance was easier to detect and improve accuracy. In other experiments, copper wire was used instead of platinum wire; however, the copper wire's resistance was lower than that of the platinum wire, and the sensation of temperature by the copper wire required more power. The coated platinum wire was purchased

from Advent Research Materials, with a thickness of 75 μm and a purity of 99.99%. The wire was then coated with Teflon (PTFE). The thickness of the coatings was 18 μm . The wire was tempered with hard quadruple PTEF insulation. The specific heat of platinum (0.133 J/g. K) (*specific heat*, no date) The wire is lower than that of copper and nickel, resulting in platinum requiring less energy to increase its temperature, leading to a faster response time for the platinum wire (*specific heat*, no date). The measurements were performed either at room temperature (25°C) or at 0°C using an ice bath.

The platinum wire, 75 μm in diameter and 207 mm in length, was soldered using lead-free tin solder to copper wires, which were then secured to the cell and spring to maintain the wire under a small tension. The spring is eliminated. The specific resistance of the thin wire should be large enough for resistance sensing. the specific resistance of the wire is dependent on its material, cross-section, and length $\rho = RAL$. ρ is the specific resistance, R is the actual wire resistance, A is the cross-section area and L is the wire length. The wire should be made from a high-melting-point metal and should be resistant to chemicals. Additionally, the metal should possess mechanical durability to withstand the thermal and mechanical stresses generated each time the current passes through it. The device was composed of three parts. The first part is the sensor, as shown in Figure 120. The wire was connected to one of the Wheatstone bridge arms, and the bridge gain was amplified using an amplifier. The signal is sensed and stored using a digital storage oscilloscope.

Figure 118 shows the ThermTest sensor as a PCB frame holding a platinum wire.

Figure 119 shows a handmade sensor with supporting stainless steel rods.

Figure 120 Shows several types of hot wire sensors made throughout the research journey A) is the last advanced sensor frame B) and C) was the first made frames.

Some of the literature reported the presence of a tension spring to keep the wire straight; however, in this research, it was found that this tension spring causes an error, so it was eliminated. After the elimination of the tension spring, the results were more accurate. The tension spring could be seen in Figure 120A.

Platinum wire is typically selected because of the well-documented relationship between resistance and temperature. The small diameter was deemed too delicate for the current experiment, while the largest diameter would not offer enough resistance for the intended cell size. As a result, a 75 μm diameter wire was chosen. A wire with lengths of approximately 10 and 15 cm was used. The wires were affixed between the two points on the printed circuit board.

6.4.8 The bridge and the amplifier

Figure 115 Illustrates a sensing circuit primarily comprising a Wheatstone bridge powered by a battery. This bridge was then connected to an instrumentation amplifier whose output was linked to a digital storage oscilloscope for data collection.

Figure 121 Shows the complete Wheatstone bridge and the amplifier circuit.

For the experiments, various instrumentation amplifiers were sourced from RS Components. Among these, the INA 131 model from Texas Electronics proved to be the most effective, yielding clear results. Other models, such as INA 118, INA 129, and INA 121, have also been successfully used. The instrumentation amplifier plays a vital role in the circuit and significantly affects the sensitivity of the device. To ensure accuracy, it is essential to calibrate the amplifier's internal resistors using glycerol, which was selected because of its relatively stable thermal conductivity under temperature fluctuations. To achieve precise resistance measurements, a Wheatstone bridge should be employed to guarantee a linear correlation between the bridge voltage and the variation in resistance. In this experiment, the hot wire

instrument approach was initially developed by Haarman, de Groot, Assael, and de Castro.(Marc J Assael et al., 2010). The setup utilised a Wheatstone bridge for resistance measurement.

Figure 122 Experimental Setup of the Initial Measurement Cell: Bridge, Battery-Powered Amplifier, and Signal Acquisition

The voltage across the bridge was measured as a function of time. Achieved this using a fast-response, high-precision 32-bit ADC. The data acquisition was controlled using a Raspberry Pi, which is responsible for power switching and data logging.

Figure 122 Shows the circuit of the Wheatstone Bridge. Each arm of the bridge was designed to have resistances of 20 and 1000 Ω . The two arms, R_{20} and R_{1000} , contained standard resistors. The resistances in the remaining arms, R_{wire} and R_{pot} , are potentiometers that balance the bridge.

The process consisted of two steps for measuring the thermal conductivity of the fluid. In the first step, the balance of the bridge is adjusted to be as close to null as practically possible. The switch is closed. A very low voltage, typically 0.001 Volts, was applied, and the temperature of

the cell was maintained at a constant level. The voltages were recorded. The second phase involved the actual measurement of thermal conductivity. The power supply was set to the desired applied power, and the switch was closed. The voltage generated across the bridge over time is recorded and stored. This process yielded a dataset consisting of a number of readings taken at intervals of 3 ms.

6.4.9 The cell

The cell was fabricated using a measuring cylinder, as shown in Figure 124. In case of measuring the thermal conductivity at room temperature there was no problem in the measurement but at different temperature the cell needed to be insulated to stabilise the temperature and to prevent the temperature fluctuation during the measurements as very small change causes could be sensed with the device and causes error so the measuring cylinder was inserted in insulating polyurethane body which was very efficient for temperature stabilisation as shown in Figure 123

Figure 123 A polyurethane insulation layer was created to prevent a swift decrease in the temperature of the solution, leading to abrupt alterations in wire resistance that risk pushing measurements outside the acceptable limits of the device when dealing with increased temperatures.

6.5 Data Processing

Figure 124 Shows the wire inserted in the solution and the signal on the oscilloscope. A is the cell, B is the conditioning circuit, C is the signal shape on the oscilloscope, D is the power supply, while E is the USB to store the signal in a CSV file and process it using MATLAB thereafter.

6.5.1 Processing the data using MATLAB or Excel

Figure 125 screenshot of the Excel sheet for the calculations of the thermal conductivity of water

Oscilloscope csv		normalization to origin and noise subtract		Bridge Gain	Rwire	ΔR	Ln	ΔT	alpha	0.003909
t	v	t	v						Gain amp	22029.82
0	0	0.001	0	0	6.439434	0	-6.90776	0	slope	0.0617
0.008	0	0.009	0	0	6.439434	0	-4.71053	0	pi	3.141593
0.016	0.56	0.017	0.56	2.54E-05	6.43986	0.000425	-4.07454	0.01689	Lw	0.207
0.024	0.84	0.025	0.84	3.81E-05	6.440072	0.000638	-3.68888	0.025335	vin	2.22
0.032	1	0.033	1	4.54E-05	6.440194	0.000759	-3.41125	0.03016	Rpot	284.6
0.04	1.72	0.041	1.72	7.81E-05	6.44074	0.001306	-3.19418	0.051877	R1000	990
0.048	1.64	0.049	1.64	7.44E-05	6.44068	0.001245	-3.01593	0.049464	R20	22.4
0.056	1.8	0.057	1.8	8.17E-05	6.440801	0.001367	-2.8647	0.05429	Rg	11.4
0.064	2	0.065	2	9.08E-05	6.440953	0.001518	-2.73337	0.060322	Rw	6.439434
0.08	3.28	0.081	3.28	0.000149	6.441925	0.00249	-2.51331	0.098932	q	0.184336
0.088	2.88	0.089	2.88	0.000131	6.441621	0.002187	-2.41912	0.086866	k	0.237867
0.096	2.76	0.097	2.76	0.000125	6.44153	0.002096	-2.33304	0.083247		
0.104	3.04	0.105	3.04	0.000138	6.441743	0.002308	-2.25379	0.091693		
0.112	3.12	0.113	3.12	0.000142	6.441803	0.002369	-2.18037	0.094106		
0.12	3.32	0.121	3.32	0.000151	6.441955	0.002521	-2.11196	0.100139		
0.128	3.36	0.129	3.36	0.000153	6.441986	0.002551	-2.04794	0.101345		
0.136	3.44	0.137	3.44	0.000156	6.442046	0.002612	-1.98777	0.103758		
0.144	3.64	0.145	3.64	0.000165	6.442198	0.002764	-1.93102	0.109792		
0.152	3.88	0.153	3.88	0.000176	6.44238	0.002946	-1.87732	0.117031		
0.16	4.24	0.161	4.24	0.000192	6.442654	0.003219	-1.82635	0.127891		
0.168	4	0.169	4	0.000182	6.442471	0.003037	-1.77786	0.120651		
0.176	3.96	0.177	3.96	0.00018	6.442441	0.003007	-1.73161	0.119445		
0.2	4.36	0.201	4.36	0.000198	6.442745	0.003311	-1.60445	0.131511		
0.208	4.52	0.209	4.52	0.000205	6.442866	0.003432	-1.56542	0.136338		
0.216	4.52	0.217	4.52	0.000205	6.442866	0.003432	-1.52786	0.136338		
0.224	4.6	0.225	4.6	0.000209	6.442927	0.003493	-1.49165	0.138751		
0.232	4.68	0.233	4.68	0.000212	6.442988	0.003554	-1.45672	0.141164		
0.24	4.76	0.241	4.76	0.000216	6.443049	0.003614	-1.42296	0.143578		
0.248	4.84	0.249	4.84	0.00022	6.443109	0.003675	-1.3903	0.145991		
0.256	4.8	0.257	4.8	0.000218	6.443079	0.003645	-1.35868	0.144784		
0.264	4.88	0.265	4.88	0.000222	6.44314	0.003705	-1.32803	0.147198		

Figure 126 typical excel sheet for the calculation of thermal conductivity based on the obtained csv file from the oscilloscope

The steps for analysing voltage-time curves obtained from oscilloscope tests using both Excel and MATLAB are as follows: The first step in analysing voltage-time curves is to import the data from the oscilloscope. The oscilloscope measures and displays the voltage and current of the electrical signal over time. In this case, an oscilloscope was used to measure the voltage-time curves of the circuit. Data were recorded and exported as CSV files from the oscilloscope. MATLAB was used to analyze the voltage-time curves. The data were imported into MATLAB using the readtable function and graphically represented using the MATLAB GUI. MATLAB

was used to calculate the slope and intercept of the voltage-time curves using the polyfit function.

The code used in MATLAB to calculate the thermal conductivity is in the Appendix 1.2

6.5.2 The Graphical user interface in MATLAB

The calculation of the thermal conductivity of the liquid under investigation started using Excel sheets, but errors in the calculations occurred frequently. The use of Excel is time consuming. The graphical user interface GUI in MATLAB is excellent processing software. An application was developed to manage the data and extract the thermal conductivity. The application code is presented in Appendix A. Figure 127 shows the graphical user interface of the developed application.

Figure 127 shows a graphical user interface developed using MATLAB. The thermal conductivity was for glycerol at 24 °C

6.5.3 Data processing using microcontrollers and processors

This device produces data that must be processed and calculated. An Arduino microcontroller is used in this study. The signal on the Arduino IDE appears as in Figure 128. The Arduino was unsuitable for the device because the data processing capability was very limited; therefore, the signal could be retrieved, but the data could not be processed to produce thermal conductivity.

After the experiment with Arduino, Raspberry Pi was chosen to perform the job as the Raspberry Pi had fairly good data analysis capabilities and easy programming using Python.

In order to obtain the signal after the amplifier or, in other words, to substitute the oscilloscope, an analog-to-digital converter was used 32 bit ADC as shown in Figure 143 (high-precision AD Hat), and Python code was developed to calculate the thermal conductivity.

Figure 128 shows the signal on Arduino IDE

6.5.4 Arduino interfacing with LCD

Interfacing 16x2 I2C LCD with Arduino UNO

Figure 129 shows how to connect LCD to an Arduino board

Figure 130 Shows the connection between the Wheatstone bridge, amplifier circuit and Arduino

To connect an Arduino board to an LCD display using an LCD I2C adapter, the following components need an Arduino board (e.g. Arduino Uno), LCD display (16x2), LCD I2C adapter (e.g. PCF8574 or PCF8575), The LCD I2C adapter connects to the Arduino board as follows.

Connect the VCC pin of the adapter to a 5V pin on the Arduino board. This provided power to the adapter. Next, the GND pin of the adapter is connected to the GND pin on the Arduino board. This completed the ground connection. The SCL pin of the adapter is then connected to the SCL pin on the Arduino board. This establishes a clock-signal connection. Finally, the SDA pin of the adapter is connected to the SDA pin on the Arduino board. This establishes a data-signal connection.

Once the adapter was connected to the Arduino board, the LCD display was connected to the adapter. connected the VCC pin of the LCD display to the VCC pin on the LCD I2C adapter. This will provide power to the LCD display. Next, the GND pin of the LCD display is connected to the GND pin on the LCD I2C adapter. This completed the ground connection. The SCL pin of the LCD display was then connected to the SCL pin on the LCD I2C adapter. This establishes a clock-signal connection. Finally, the SDA pin of the LCD display is connected to the SDA pin on the LCD I2C adapter. This establishes a data-signal connection.

Now that the LCD display is connected to the Arduino board using the LCD I2C adapter, code can be written to communicate with the LCD display using the I2C protocol. used the wire library in Arduino to communicate with an LCD display. The code will depend on the specific requirements of the project, but it will typically involve initializing the LCD display and sending commands to it using the I2C protocol.

6.5.5 Arduino interfacing with temperature sensor

Figure 131 shows how to connect a temperature sensor to an Arduino board

To connect a DS10B20 temperature sensor to an Arduino board, the following components are needed, Arduino board, DS10B20 temperature sensor, Jumper wires.

The DS10B20 temperature sensor is connected to the Arduino board as follows: The VCC pin of the sensor to the 5V pin on the Arduino board. This provided power to the sensor. Next, the GND pin of the sensor is connected to the GND pin on the Arduino board. This completed the ground connection. The SCL pin of the sensor was then connected to the SCL pin on the Arduino board. This establishes a clock-signal connection. Finally, the SDA pin of the sensor is connected to the SDA pin on the Arduino board. This establishes a data-signal connection. For the code, this can be found easily in the Arduino library, ready to use.

6.5.6 Arduino interfacing with ADC ADS 1115

Figure 132 shows the typical connection between the ADC the Arduino board.

The ADS1115 is a high-resolution ADC that provides 16-bit measurements of analogue signals. It is a popular choice for applications that require precise measurements of analogue signals such as temperature, pressure, and humidity. The Arduino microcontroller platform can be used to interface with various sensors, including ADS1115. To interface the Arduino with the ADS1115, use the ADS1115 library (available on the Arduino website).

The ADS1115 was connected to the Arduino board using jumper wires. The ADS1115 should be connected to Arduino's I2C pins (for example, SCL and SDA). Then, the ADS1115 library was installed on the Arduino IDE by downloading it from the Arduino website and installing it using the Arduino IDE's library manager. The code was then written to read the analogue signal from ADS1115 using the ADS1115 library.

6.5.7 Arduino's Limitations in Processing Large Data Volumes

Arduino, a widely used microcontroller platform in robotics, automation, and sensor interfacing, faces significant challenges when processing large amounts of data due to its lack

of EEPROM (Electrically Erasable Programmable Read-Only Memory). This absence makes it difficult to store and retrieve substantial datasets for mathematical processing, limiting the capabilities of Arduino in data-intensive applications.

The absence of EEPROM in Arduino means that the data cannot be stored and retrieved directly from the microcontroller. This limitation is particularly problematic when dealing with large datasets that require processing. The limited memory of the microcontroller further compounds this issue, as it can only accommodate a certain amount of data at a time. When the amount of data exceeds the available memory, the microcontroller cannot process it effectively.

To address these memory constraints, external memory solutions become necessary. Options such as SD cards, USB drives, and EEPROM modules can be employed to store data that exceeds the capacity of the microcontroller. These external storage devices allow the Arduino to access and process larger datasets without exhausting internal memory.

However, the use of external memory introduces several challenges. This can increase the overall cost of the system, sometimes surpassing the price of the microcontroller itself. Additionally, incorporating external memory introduces complexity to the system design, necessitating the addition of extra components and wiring. Furthermore, external memory access can be slower than internal memory operations, potentially affecting the overall system performance.

Despite these drawbacks, the use of external memory remains a viable solution for expanding Arduino's data-processing capabilities, enabling it to handle larger datasets and more complex computations.

6.5.8 The raspberry Pi

Raspberry Pi is a single-board computer that has gained popularity in recent years owing to its affordability, flexibility, and versatility. As a low-cost and highly capable platform, Raspberry Pi has been used in a wide range of applications, from computer science education to robotics and automation. This study aims to explore the potential of Raspberry Pi as a platform for computer science education and research, with a focus on its key features, capabilities, and limitations.

Raspberry Pi was first released in 2012 by the Raspberry Pi Foundation, a UK-based charity organization. The first model, Raspberry Pi Model B, was designed as a low-cost alternative to traditional desktop computers. Since then, Raspberry Pi has undergone several revisions, with each new model offering improved performance, features, and capabilities. Raspberry Pi has become a popular platform for hobbyists, students, and professionals alike, and has been used in a wide range of applications, including computer science education, robotics, and automation.

Raspberry Pi is a highly capable single-board computer that features a range of key characteristics. The Raspberry Pi is powered by a quad-core processor that provides high performance and efficiency. Raspberry Pi can be equipped with up to 4GB of RAM, making it suitable for demanding applications. Raspberry Pi features a range of GPIO pins that can be used to connect external devices and sensors. Raspberry Pi can run a range of operating systems, including Linux, Windows, and Android.

The GPIO pins of the Raspberry Pi are crucial features that enable it to connect to a wide range of sensors and devices. GPIO pins are used to connect external devices to the Raspberry Pi, allowing it to read data from sensors and control external devices. The GPIO pins are also used to connect to other microcontrollers and devices, making the Raspberry Pi a versatile platform for building complex systems

6.5.9 The raspberry pi GPIO

Figure 133 illustrates the GPIO (General Purpose Input/Output) pins of the Raspberry Pi.

The General-Purpose Input/Output (GPIO) pins of the Raspberry Pi are a crucial component of the board, enabling users to interact with the outside world. These pins are a type of digital input/output pin that can be used to connect to external devices such as sensors, LEDs, and motors. Raspberry Pi features several types of GPIO pins, including

- 3.3V GPIO pins: These pins are used for general-purpose input/output and are connected to the 3.3V power rail.
- 5V GPIO pins: These pins are used for general-purpose input/output and are connected to the 5V power rail.
- I2C GPIO pins: These pins are used for I2C (Inter-Integrated Circuit) communication and are connected to the I2C bus.
- SPI GPIO pins: These pins are used for SPI (Serial Peripheral Interface) communication and are connected to the SPI bus.

To utilise the GPIO pins of the Raspberry Pi, users must first connect the external device to the pins using a jumper wire or breadboard. Next, the pin must be configured as an input or output using programming languages such as Python or C++. Finally, the user can read or write data to the pin using a programming language.

6.5.10 Pi Connection to temperature sensor DS 18B20

Figure 134 demonstrates the connection method between the Raspberry Pi and a temperature sensor.

DS18B20 is a digital temperature sensor that can be connected to a Raspberry Pi using GPIO pins. Here's a step-by-step guide on how to connect the DS18B20 to the Raspberry Pi. The required hardware is a Raspberry Pi and a DS18B20 temperature sensor. Connect the VCC pin of the DS18B20 to the 3.3V pin on the Raspberry Pi; This will provide power to the DS18B20. Connect the GND pin of DS18B20 to the GND pin on the Raspberry Pi, which completes the ground connection. Connect the DQ pin of the DS18B20 to any GPIO pin on the Raspberry Pi; this will allow the Raspberry Pi to communicate with the DS18B20.

- Install the RPi.GPIO library: This library is required to interact with the GPIO pins on the Raspberry Pi. You can install it using pip: `sudo pip install RPi.GPIO`

- Import the RPi.GPIO library: In your Python script, import the RPi.GPIO library:
`import RPi.GPIO as GPIO`
- Set up the GPIO pin: Set up the GPIO pin that you connected the DS18B20 to:
`GPIO.setmode(GPIO.BCM)`
- Initialize the DS18B20: Initialize the DS18B20 using the w1-therm library: `import w1thermsensor`
- Read the temperature: Read the temperature from the DS18B20 using the w1thermsensor library: `sensor = w1thermsensor.W1ThermSensor()`
- Print the temperature: Print the temperature to the console:
`print(sensor.get_temperature())`

The DS10b20 is a very slow temperature sensor; for this reason it is better to use the platinum SMD temperature sensor as in Figure 135

PTS Series - Pt-Sensors

Vishay Beyschlag

Platinum SMD Flat Chip Temperature Sensor

PTS SMD Flat Chip Temperature sensors are the perfect choice for temperature control of electronics operating under varying environmental conditions. The highly controlled platinum thin film manufacturing process guarantees an outstanding stability of temperature characteristics which ensures reliable operation even under harsh conditions. Typical applications include automotive, aviation and industrial electronics.

FEATURES

- Standardized characteristics according to IEC 60751
- Advanced thin film technology
- Short reaction times down to $t_{0.9} \leq 2$ s (in air)
- Outstanding stability of temperature characteristic
- Standard SMD sizes
- Supports lead (Pb)-free soldering
- Compliant to RoHS Directive 2002/95/EC

RoHS
COMPLIANT

APPLICATIONS

- Temperature measurement in
- Automotive electronics
 - Aviation electronics
 - Industrial electronics

Figure 135 illustrates an SMD (Surface Mount Device) temperature sensor that can be used on a PCB (Printed Circuit Board). This type of sensor is compact, efficient, and can be easily integrated into electronic designs.

The SMD Platinum temperature sensor is highly accurate and reliable, and is widely used in various applications, including industrial control systems, medical devices, and consumer electronics. The sensor was designed to provide high accuracy and reliability, making it an ideal choice for applications where temperature measurement is critical. To connect the SMD Platinum temperature sensor to the Raspberry Pi, the following steps must be followed,

- The VCC pin of the SMD Platinum temperature sensor to the 3.3V pin on a Raspberry Pi. This provided power to the sensor.
- The GND pin of the SMD Platinum temperature sensor was connected to the GND pin on the Raspberry Pi. This completed the ground connection.
- Connect the DQ pin of the SMD Platinum temperature sensor to any GPIO pin on the Raspberry Pi. This allowed the Raspberry Pi to communicate with the sensor.
- Install the RPi.GPIO library: This library is required to interact with the Raspberry Pi's GPIO pins. You can install it using pip: `sudo pip install RPi.GPIO`
- Import the RPi.GPIO library: In your Python script, import the RPi.GPIO library: `import RPi.GPIO as GPIO`
- Set up the GPIO pin: Set up the GPIO pin that you connected the SMD Platinum temperature sensor to: `GPIO.setmode(GPIO.BCM)`
- Initialise the SMD Platinum temperature sensor: Initialise the sensor using the w1therm library: `import w1thermsensor`
- Read the temperature: Read the temperature from the SMD Platinum temperature sensor using the w1thermsensor library: `sensor = w1thermsensor.W1ThermSensor()`
- Print the temperature: Print the temperature to the console: `print(sensor.get_temperature())`

6.5.11 Connecting the ADC, ADS 1115 16-bit ADC

The ADS1015 and ADS1115 are outstanding choices for analogue-to-digital conversions, pairing seamlessly with the Raspberry Pi through the I2C communication bus. ADS1015 offers 12-bit resolution with four channels, while ADS1115 elevates precision as a 16-bit ADC with four channels. Programmable gains, ranging from $2/3x$ to $16x$, empower users to amplify faint signals, thereby enhancing accuracy when capturing readings.

Figure 136 ADS 1115 16-bit ADC

Figure 137 shows the connection between raspberry pi and the ADC ADS1115

To wire ADS1×15 to the Raspberry Pi, only Enable I2C on the Raspberry Pi using raspi-config and confirm visibility with the i2cdetect command after enabling it. The components are connected as follows:

1. Connect ADS1x15 VDD to the Raspberry Pi's 3.3V pin.
2. Connect ADS1x15 GND to the Raspberry Pi's GND.
3. Connect ADS1x15 SCL to the Raspberry Pi's SCL.
4. Connect ADS1x15 SDA to the Raspberry Pi's SDA.

The I2C communication protocol enables interaction between the chips and the Pi, facilitating the successful reading of analogue values from the ADCs. After wiring ADS1115 to Raspberry Pi, the Adafruit ADS1×15 Python library was installed.

To install the library from its source on GitHub, connect to a terminal on the Raspberry Pi and run the following commands

```
sudo apt-get update
sudo apt-get install build-essential python-dev python-smbus git
cd ~
git clone https://github.com/adafruit/Adafruit_Python_ADS1x15.git
cd Adafruit_Python_ADS1x15
sudo python setup.py install
sudo apt-get install build-essential python-dev python-smbus python-pip
sudo pip install adafruit-ads1x15
cd ~/Adafruit_Python_ADS1x15/examples
nano simplestest.py
sudo python simplestest.py
```

```
# Choose a gain of 1 for reading voltages from 0 to 4.09V.
# - 1 = +/-4.096V
GAIN = 1
```

The code provided allows for adjustment of the ADC's gain setting, determining the strength of the captured signals for enhanced readability. Increasing the gain narrows the voltage spectrum detected by component.

When using a gain value of 1, the voltage window spans 4.096 volts, implying that the chip accommodates readings extending from -4.096 volts to +4.096 volts. Careful selection of gain ensures reliable performance; an excessively high gain pushes the signal above the ADC's peak voltage threshold (saturation), whereas undervaluing the gain obscures the signal.

6.5.12 High precision ADC hat from Waveshare

Figure 138 ADC ADS 1263 from waveshare

Precise Analog-to-Digital Converter Add-on Board for Raspberry Pi – ADS1263 10-Channel 32-Bit Device

- Resolution: 32 bits
- Input Count: 10
- Maximum Sample Rate: 38 kSPS

- Highest PGA Amplification: 32x
- Bus Type: SPI
- Architecture: Delta-Sigma
- Signal Types Supported: Differential, Single-Ended
- Reference Voltage Choices: Interior, Exterior
- Maximum Input Voltage Range: 2.5V, 5V
- Minimum Input Voltage Range: -2.5V, 0V

The integrated ADS1263 chip is characterised by low noise, minimal temperature drift, and a 10-channel, 32-bit ultraprecision ADC (five dual-input ports) with a maximum sampling rate of 38.4 kSPS.

Equipped with an embedded 24-bit secondary ADC, an integrated self-test signal generator for ADC, IDAC, 2.5V interior reference voltage, eight multipurpose GPIO pins, and a programmable gain amplifier (PGA) (amplifier factor as much as 32x). Onboard expansion headers connect various types of sensor modules and align them with waveleshare sensor pinouts. Screw terminals for connecting analogue signals and power supplies, providing universal host compatibility. Control Headers for straightforward control by other microcontrollers, in addition to the Raspberry Pi. A three-wire RTD (resistance temperature detector) circuit was activated by installing a zero-ohm resistor. Fasten the differential signal to the respective differential input connector on the AD HAT (choose from IN0 and IN1). ensure that the reference voltage is configured as internal $\pm 2.5V$ (single-ended connections only support PGA by default). Remember to update the REF value to 2.5 in the main.c file and fine-tune the PGA according to the real scenario.

```
#Modify the internal REF voltage :  
#Change the define in the ADS1263_ConfigADC1() of ADS1263.c from  
UBYTE REFMUX = 0x24;  
#to  
UBYTE REFMUX = 0x00;  
#Modify line 33 of main.c (Python code also has the function of the same name)  
#change  
ADS1263_SetMode(0);  
#to  
ADS1263_SetMode(1);
```

```
#Open the Raspberry Pi terminal and run the following command  
wget https://github.com/joan2937/lg/archive/master.zip  
unzip master.zip  
cd lg-master  
sudo make install  
# You can refer to the official website for more: https://github.com/gpiozero/lg  
sudo apt-get update  
sudo apt-get install ttf-wqy-zenhei  
sudo apt-get install python-pip  
sudo pip install RPi.GPIO  
sudo pip install spidev  
cd ~  
git clone https://github.com/waveshare/High-Precision_AD_HAT
```

6.5.13 Pi Connection

Figure 139 System Architecture of the Automated Thermal Conductivity Measurement Unit

Figure 140 A is the bridge power supply, B is the op amp power supply, C is the switching relay, D is the raspberry pi, E is the Wheatstone bridge and the amplifier circuit, F is the high precision ADC hat

Figure 140 Hardware Layout of the Transient Hot Wire Measurement System with Sensor Frame and Fluid Cell

Figure 141 A shows the amplifier circuit, B shows the bridge power supply, C shows the amplifier circuit power supply, D shows the Wheatstone bridge, E shows the raspberry pi unit,

F shows the for the Wheatstone bridge power supply, K shows the battery for the amplifier power supply, G shows the sensor frame and the sensor, H is the cell filled with the fluid.

Figure 141 The diagram illustrates the connection of a Raspberry Pi with various components, including an ADC (Analog-to-Digital Converter), an amplifier circuit, a digital potentiometer, a temperature sensor, and a hot wire

Figure 142 A shows the switching relay, B shows the bridge power supply, C shows the amplifier power supply.

The different components of the experimental setup, including the hot wires, the wire support, Wheatstone bridge, raspberry pi 4, High-Precision AD HAT For Raspberry Pi, ADS1263 10-Ch 32-Bit ADC., Raspberry Pi 4-Channel Relay Hat Shield Module 5V DCAC KEYESTUDIO

Expansion Board for Raspberry Pi 4/A+/B+/Pi 2 Model B/Pi 3 Model B, ARCELI Buck Boost Converter Display, Buck-Boost Board DC 5.5-30V 12v to DC 0.5-30V 5v 24v Adjustable Constant Current Voltage Step UP Down Voltage Regulator , Voltage Converter Module, DC-DC Adjustable 20W Boost Buck Voltage Converter Positive and Negative Dual Output 5V-24V to +/-3V-30V for Amplifier, The INA131 is as a low cost, general purpose $G = 100$ instrumentation amplifier offering excellent accuracy.

Voltage Converter Module, DC-DC Adjustable 20W Boost Buck Voltage Converter Positive and Negative Dual Output 5V-24V to +/-3V-30V for Amplifier.

Figure 143 shows the amplifier, the raspberry pi and the high precision ADC converter hat respectively

6.6 Elimination of the spring

While measuring the thermal conductivities of surfactants, it was observed that the small time intervals between measurements resulted in high values, which could be considered inaccurate as higher thermal conductivities. An experiment was conducted to measure the thermal conductivity of Milli-Q water, with one-minute intervals between measurements. The result showed that the thermal conductivity increased as the experiments progressed. However, if the wire was left to relax for at least 5 minutes, the measurement approached the expected value of water. This could be related to the presence of a tension spring that maintains the wire in a straight position. After the spring was eliminated from the sensor frame, the measurements

became more accurate. The thermal conductivity measurement session should be performed after ensuring the metal wire has returned to its original stable state. There may also be other factors that affect the wire, but it was observed that if the wire was left for at least 7 minutes (if the spring existed), the result was as expected, and 1 minute if the spring was eliminated. The previous experiments were performed with the spring mounted, resulting in less accuracy than after elimination.

6.7 Validation of the device

To ensure the reliability of the device, validation was carried out using common fluids with established thermal conductivities. These fluids included Glycerol, Methanol, Propan-2-ol (also known as 2Propanol), and Ethylene Glycol, all procured from Fischer Scientific. The validation process was conducted at 0°C and 25°C, according to the methodology outlined by (S. Azarfar et al., 2016).

Various surfactants were also sourced from Fischer Scientific to examine the thermal conductivity of the surfactant solutions. These include SDS, CTAB, and TBAB. Simulsol SL 4 was acquired from Safesol, Ltd. Solutions of each surfactant were prepared in accordance with their solubility in water. The thermal conductivities of the surfactant solutions were measured at a standard room temperature of 25°C.

6.8 Thermal conductivity of known base fluid

Validating transient hot-wire devices is essential for advancing research on the thermal conductivity of surfactant solutions. For this purpose, deionized water, ethylene glycol, methanol, glycerol, and Propan-2-ol were chosen for evaluation, and the findings were compared with data from the existing literature. The thermal conductivity of each fluid was

measured at 25 and 0°C. To ensure consistency, each experiment was repeated at least three times.

The voltage-time curves obtained from these tests were recorded and exported as CSV files from the oscilloscope. These datasets were graphically represented using Excel or MATLAB. The results, particularly for Methanol, Water, Propan-2-ol, and Ethylene Glycol, are depicted in Figure 8. Noise interference, which affects signal quality, was a significant challenge encountered during the experiments. Further investigation revealed that this noise primarily originated from the main electricity source and certain wireless communications, which were identified by their characteristic frequency of 50 Hz.

To mitigate this issue, the experiments were relocated to a quiet laboratory situated away from the main power supply and featuring fewer operational instruments. This move effectively eliminated noise interference. Following this, the data from Figure 8 were analyzed using Excel. The method for converting these signals into thin-wire temperature readings is detailed in the Methods section. This process facilitated the creation of plots, as shown in Figure 9, representing the relationship between the instantaneous temperature increase in each fluid and the natural logarithm of time at the specified temperatures.

Table 5 Comparison of thermal conductivities of validation fluids with information reported in the literature

Fluid	Temperature °C	Thermal conductivity in W/m. K	% Deviation	Thermal conductivity in other literature
Methanol	25 °C	0.2023	0.83%	0.204 (Mostafizur <i>et al</i>)(<i>International Union of Pure and Applied Chemistry</i> , no date)
Methanol	0 °C	0.2012	2.3 %	0.207 (<i>Physical and Thermodynamic Properties of Pure Chemicals : Data Compilation CiNii Research</i>)(<i>International Union of Pure and Applied Chemistry</i> , no date)
Ethanol	0	0.169	5%	(Petravic, 2005)
Ethanol	25	0.16	5%	(Petravic, 2005)
Propan-2-ol	0 °C	0.1418	0.02%	0.142(<i>Physical and Thermodynamic Properties of Pure Chemicals : Data Compilation CiNii Research</i>)
Propan-2-ol	25 °C	0.1397	2.9%	0.135 (<i>Physical and Thermodynamic Properties of Pure Chemicals : Data Compilation CiNii Research</i>)(<i>International Union of Pure and Applied Chemistry</i> , no date)
95% Ethylene glycol	0 °C	0.2332	8%	0.25(<i>Physical and Thermodynamic Properties of Pure Chemicals : Data Compilation CiNii Research</i>)
95% Ethylene glycol	25 °C	0.2357	8%	0.256 (<i>Physical and Thermodynamic Properties of Pure Chemicals : Data Compilation CiNii Research</i>)(<i>International Union of Pure and Applied Chemistry</i> , no date)
Deionised water	25 °C	0.5955	1.6%	0.6096 (Ramires <i>et al.</i> , 2009)
Deionised water	0 °C	0.5435	3.5%	0.5606(Ramires <i>et al.</i> , 2009)(<i>International Union of Pure and Applied Chemistry</i> , no date)

Table 5 lists the thermal conductivities of the known fluids for device validation. The results became more accurate after eliminating the tension spring. Thermal conductivity usually increases with increasing temperature.

Figure 144 Oscilloscope Voltage-Time Curves for Common Fluids in Transient Hot Wire Experiments

Figure 145 Temperature Rise vs. ln(Time) Plots for Thermal Conductivity Determination of Various Fluids

Figure 146 shows the Temperature increment of the thin wire versus the natural logarithm of time plots from which the slope is determined to calculate the thermal conductivity of the fluid. a)methanol at 25 °C .b) Methanol at 0 °C. c) Deionised water at 25 °C. d) Deionised water at 0 °C. e) 2-propanol at 25 °C. f)Ethylene glycol at 25 °C.The slope of each straight line in Figure 145 Was obtained using an Excel curve-fitting function (trendline). Then, using the equation 6-20 The thermal conductivity of each fluid was determined and compared to the data reported in the literature, as shown in Table 1.

As shown in Figure 144, the oscilloscope output of voltage over time curves for different common fluids. This information should be processed later to obtain the thermal conductivity. The plots are similar in shape, but their scales vary for each plot. The slopes of the plots in Figure 145 depend on this scale. Figure 145 illustrates the conclusion of the thermal conductivity determination. The thermal conductivity can be determined by substituting the slope into $k = \frac{V}{L \cdot \Delta T}$. The deviation of the values from those reported in other literature could be attributed to the purity of the materials or the accuracy of the device, which depends on the quality of the electronic components.

6.9 The Thermal Conductivity of Surfactant Solutions

Figure 147 Shows the graphs of the thermal conductivities plotted against the molar concentrations of the three different surfactants at room temperature (SDS, CTAB, and TBAB). Sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS) is an anionic surfactant extracted from coconut and palm oil. This substance is used in various applications, including as emulsifiers and detergents, in the pharmaceutical industry. (*sodium lauryl sulfate, DrugBank Online*). Its Molar mass is 288.38 g/mole CMC 8.5 mMol/L at 30 °C (Motin, Hafiz Mia and Nasimul Islam, 2015). Cetrimonium Bromide (CTAB) is also known as cetyltrimethylammonium Bromide or hexadecyltrimethylammonium bromide. Its Molar mass is 364.45 g/mole CMC 0.9 mMol/L at 30 °C (Shah and Bhattarai, 2020)(Irfan *et al.*, 2014). Tetrabutylammonium Bromide (TBAB). Its Molar mass is 322.37 g/mole CMC 13.6 mMol/L at 30 °C.(Chauhan *et al.*, 2014).

Figure 146: Surfactant structures used in the research

The alkyl polyglucoside molecule was composed of a sugar head connected to an alkyl tail through an oxygen atom. The alkyl polyglucosides were classified according to the number of sugar heads and hydrocarbon tails.

Figure 147 Thermal conductivity vs. molar concentrations of various surfactants. The red arrows indicate the CMC

Figure 148 thermal conductivity vs concentration for SDS and Simulsol SL 4. The red arrow indicates the CMC

In Figure 147 The first experiments on the thermal conductivities of surfactant solutions for SDS, CTAB, and TBAB show that, despite variations in the results, the overall trend appears to have no effect or a lowering effect on the conductivity of water at room temperature. To demonstrate that the conductivity change could be significant, a higher temperature should be employed. The increase in thermal conductivity at certain points of SDS was investigated in other experiments, and it was found that the wire should be left to relax for at least 7 minutes to return to its initial state and obtain a stable trend. This is due to the effect of the tension spring.

In Figure 148, the experiment was repeated for SDS and APG surfactants supplied by Simsol Ltd. (the company that sponsors the project). As seen from the graph, the conductivity does not change significantly, even at a concentration of approximately 60 ml/L, which is an extremely high concentration compared to the concentration used for heating systems, which is 1000 ppm.

Figure 149 Shows the thermal conductivity against temperature of several surfactants and nanofluids.

6.10 Result graphs

Glycerol

Thermal conductivity results for glycerol as obtained from the MATLAB application, three different trials

Figure 150 shows the Glycerol signal

2Propanol

Thermal conductivity results for 2-propanol as obtained from the MATLAB application, two different trials

Figure 151 shows the 2-Propanol signal.

Methanol

Thermal conductivity results for Methanol as obtained from the MATLAB application, three different trials

Figure 152 shows the Methanol signal.

Water

Thermal conductivity results for water as obtained from the MATLAB application, three different trials

Figure 153 shows the water signal.

Ethylene Glycol

Thermal conductivity results for Ethylene glycol as obtained from the MATLAB application.

Figure 154 shows the ethylene glycol signal.

Vacuum oil

Thermal conductivity results for pumping Vacuum oil as obtained from the MATLAB application

Figure 155 shows the vacuum oil signal.

6.11 Summary

This chapter investigates the design and validation of a transient hot-wire device for measuring fluid thermal conductivity. The transient hot wire device heats a thin wire immersed in the fluid and tracks the resistance change over time to determine the thermal conductivity. Running on a thin platinum wire sensor, an amplifier, and a data collecting system, the gadget uses a

Wheatstone bridge circuit. The device was then validated using common fluids, including water, ethylene glycol, and alcohols, after glycerol was used for calibration. Different concentrations and temperatures for the thermal conductivities of several surfactant solutions, including SDS, CTAB, TBAB, and alkyl polyglucosides, were measured. The results showed that even at high concentrations, the thermal conductivity of the surfactant solutions did not change significantly from that of water. The chapter also addresses the challenges of the experiments, including noise interference and the need for wire relaxation between observations. The appendices present the thermal conductivity results obtained from the MATLAB program and the code used for data processing.

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Chapter 7

Internal Temperature Monitoring of an Insulated Wooden Chamber Using Various Heating Fluids a Comparative Study of Nanofluids, Surfactants, and Conventional Water.

7.1 Introduction

This chapter investigates the internal temperature monitoring of an insulated wooden chamber using various heat transfer fluids, including nanofluids, surfactants, and conventional water. The reason for developing the room simulation box (RS box) is to simulate a small room condition using a three-meter copper coil heater with a 5 mm diameter tube, in order to determine which heat transfer fluid works better in a small-scale room by raising its temperature more quickly. The RS box is measuring 50 by 50 by 50 cm, insulated with a polystyrene layer to minimise heat transfer loss. A digital thermometer is placed inside the chamber to monitor temperature changes, while a copper coil heater, connected to a thermostatic circulator, is used to control the temperature of the heating fluid. Experiments were conducted by heating the fluids to 65°C and monitoring the chamber's temperature until the fluid temperature remained constant. Comparisons between nanofluids (silica, alumina, and graphene oxide) and water revealed that alumina generated the highest temperature, followed by graphene oxide, both of which surpassed water's performance. Silica exhibited a lower temperature than water. Surfactants (APG, silicone, and SDS) were also compared to water, with the lowest concentration of silicone surfactants achieving the highest temperature, followed by lower concentrations of silisurf and SDS. All surfactants outperformed water in terms of heat transfer. Further comparisons between nanofluids and surfactants showed that the lowest concentration of silicone surfactant was the most effective, closely followed by lower concentrations of Silsurf and SDS. The study also examined the performance of various nanofluid and surfactant combinations, providing insights into their heat transfer capabilities. The findings contribute to the understanding of alternative heating fluids and their potential applications in building systems and other heat transfer applications.

7.2 Development of the room simulation box (RS Box)

Figure 156: Pharmacia LKB MultiTemp II Recirculating chillers are used to control the temperature of a liquid by circulating it through a closed loop

The RS box is made on the principle of an insulated room. It is a 50 cm x 50 cm x 50 cm wooden box, insulated from the inside with a polystyrene layer to prevent heat leakage to the outside or from the outside. A thermometer was then left inside the box to monitor the temperature change. Inside the box, a copper coil heater is connected to a thermostatic circulator, which acts as a heat radiator. The thermal circulator is a laboratory instrument used to control the temperature of a bath or solution.

The initial experiments were conducted by heating the fluid from 10 °C to 65°C and monitoring the temperature of the box until it stabilised. Cooling the circulating fluid to 10°C and waiting for equilibrium before raising the temperature to 65°C.

Figure 157 shows the insulated RS box from the inside, with the radiator coil measuring 3 meters in length and 5 mm in diameter. The insulation, made of polystyrene, is visible.

Figure 158 A is the temperature thermometer, and B is the heating coil. The distance between the coil and the temperature sensor is around 50 cm.

7.3 Comparison between selected heat transfer fluids

The following graphs present temperature data collected from a wooden box during a monitoring process, employing water, heat transfer fluids and various nanofluids (silica, alumina, and graphene oxide) as heating fluids in a thermostatic circulator.

7.3.1 Comparison between Nanofluids and Water

Figure 159 graphs of selected nanofluids compared to pure water: Titania, Silica, GO, alumina. Alumina shows the best performance.

Figure 159 Shows that alumina generated the highest temperature within the box, followed by graphene oxide, which surpassed water performance. Silica, however, exhibited a lower temperature compared to water. This discrepancy may be attributed to the fact that the silica experiment commenced at a temperature 2 to 3 degrees lower than the starting point for water.

Literature, such as that by Beck et al. (2010), supports the superior heat transfer capability of alumina over water, and Ponangi et al. (2018) confirm the enhanced heat transfer ability of graphene oxide. Furthermore, Mohammadi et al. (2011) reported that silica's heat transfer capability is superior to that of water. However, the curve in the figure shows silica's performance as lower than that of water, likely due to the very low room temperature, which was not possible to control.

7.3.2 Comparison between Surfactants and Water

Figure 160: The graph shows a comparison between surfactants with water. All surfactants have performance superior to water, while the 100-ppm silicone surfactant Silsurf surpasses all.

Figure 160 presents temperature data collected from a wooden box during a monitoring process, employing water and various surfactants (Simsol SL 11 as an APG surfactant, Silsurf

as a silicone surfactant with different concentrations, and SDS as the most popular surfactant) as heating fluids in a thermostatic circulator. Upon analysing the graph, it is evident that the silicone surfactant in the lowest concentration generated the highest temperature within the box, followed by the lower concentrations of silsurf and SDS, and the lowest of the surfactants was the simsol APG, all of them surpassed water's performance

Literature, such as Bourdon et al. (2013), Altun & Şara (2020), and Wang et al. (2021), has reported the advantages of adding surfactants in enhancing heat transfer.

7.3.3 Comparison between Nanofluids and Surfactants

Figure 161 shows the performance of surfactants versus nanofluids. The silicone surfactant silsurf showed better performance than both nanofluids and other surfactants.

Figure 161 Analyse temperature variations in a RS box using different heating fluids in a thermostatic circulator. The tested fluids include nanofluids (titania, silica, alumina, and graphene oxide) and surfactant solutions (APG/simsol, silicone surfactants/silsurf, and SDS). Among the surfactants, the silicone-based silsurf achieved the highest temperature increase at its lowest concentration, followed by SDS and APG (simsol), which was the least effective.

When comparing water, APG, and silsurf, silsurf again demonstrated the greatest heating efficiency, while water produced the smallest temperature change. APG performed moderately, surpassing water but falling short of the silicone surfactant. Among nanofluids, alumina exhibited the highest temperature rise, outperforming graphene oxide and simsol, which still exceeded water's heating effect. In contrast, silica nanoparticles showed the lowest temperature increase.

This analysis highlights the superior thermal performance of silicone surfactants and alumina nanofluids compared to other tested fluids.

7.3.4 Comparison between Silsurf A008 different Concentrations

Figure 162 Influence of Surfactant Concentration on Thermal Performance: Silsurf A008 Case Study

As seen from Figure 162 Different Silsurf A008 concentrations. The graph suggests that reducing the surfactant concentration could enhance heat transfer. The extent of the reduction could be a subject for another study to determine the least concentration required to enhance

the heat transfer. The lowest concentration of silicone surfactant exhibits better performance, followed by higher concentrations, which is counterintuitive.

7.3.5 Comparison between Silsurf A008 and GO

Figure 163: silicone surfactant alone vs silicone surfactant with graphene oxide

Figure 163 Shows the improved thermal behaviour when graphene oxide is added to silicone surfactants. The effect of the addition of the silsurf a008 on the graphene oxide solution gave an excellent result surpassing the enhancement of all the selected nanofluids and the surfactants. The experiment was repeated several times, but the graph shows the results of only two instances of the same experiment.

7.3.6 Comparison between silica, APG and silica

Figure 164 APG surfactant vs silica vs silica plus APG surfactant

From Figure 164 The addition of APG improved the heat transfer characteristics of silica nanofluid. The addition of surfactants to the nanofluids enhances the heat transfer. The temperature generated from silica with the APG surfactants is the best, better than the silica and the surfactant by itself

7.4 Comparison between titania, APG and titania

Figure 165 shows the difference between titania nanofluid and titania nanofluid with APG added, and the APG.

Figure 165 shows that the addition of APG to the titania nanofluid improved its heat transfer capability

7.5 Comparison between alumina and APG

Figure 166 shows the effect of adding APG to alumina nanofluid. Additionally, for the alumina nanofluid, the APG enhances its performance.

Figure 166 Shows that the addition of APG to the alumina nanofluids had no notable improvement on the heat transfer

7.6 Summary

This chapter examines the internal temperature monitoring of an insulated wooden chamber using conventional water, surfactants, and nanofluids, among other heat transfer fluids. The fluids were heated to 65°C, and the chamber's temperature was tracked until it stabilised. Comparisons between nanofluids and water showed that silica had a lower outlet temperature than water; alumina produced the highest temperature, followed by graphene oxide. Surfactants were also tested against water; the lowest concentration of silicone surfactants attained the highest temperature, followed by lower concentrations of Silisurf and SDS. Further comparison of nanofluids and surfactants revealed that the most effective concentration of silicone surfactant was the lowest one. Additionally, looking at the performance of several nanofluid and surfactant combinations, the study revealed their heat transfer properties and capabilities.

Chapter 8

Evaluation of products for Energy-Saving

8.1 Introduction

This study provides a comprehensive analysis of two separate trials conducted by Durham and Bradford Councils to evaluate the effectiveness of the energy-saving product Delta-T in reducing energy consumption and carbon emissions. This report is about a trial conducted in Durham Council's Crook Civic Centre and the trial conducted in Bradford Council's Britannia House building. The analysis includes energy-saving calculations, temperature monitoring data, and recommendations for future improvements. The findings of this evaluation will help inform decisions regarding the implementation of energy-efficient solutions in similar commercial and public buildings. This chapter focuses on the unique features of Delta-T, such as its ability to enhance wettability and improve heat transfer in heating systems, and its potential to provide even greater energy savings of up to 11%, resulting in an annual saving of 82,500 kWh or 15.26 tonnes of CO₂ emissions, with a return on investment of ten months. This new formulation is based on superspreader chemistry.

In this study, the formulation of Delta T was modified by the Safesol company. First, it was based on APG so that it will be referred to as Delta T APG in the text. The second formulation was based on Silsurf A008 silicone surfactants, which will be referred to as Delta T S.

8.2 Durham council, Crook Civic Centre

8.2.1 Evaluating energy savings

To determine the energy savings, the period from the beginning of 2023 until the introduction of the chemical on March 3, 2023, was compared to the time after the treatment was analysed. This calculation focuses solely on weekdays to minimise the influence of occupancy variations, whereas weekends were assessed independently. Each weekday was evaluated separately by dividing gas consumption by the Heating Degree Day (HDD). The Gas usage per Degree Day

before and after the Delta T treatment is averaged, and the percentage of energy saved is computed based on this comparison. The amount of energy conserved by comparing gas usage before and after the treatment was examined, considering daily gas consumption relative to the Heating Degree Day.

In the Crook Civic Centre, the gas usage is influenced by two key factors. Firstly, ambient temperature plays a crucial role, as colder external temperatures require more energy to maintain a comfortable indoor temperature. Secondly, the building occupancy also impacts energy consumption, especially noticeable during weekends when occupancy levels drop to 20-30% compared to weekdays.

The calculation method for energy savings involves comparing gas consumption before and after the chemical treatment introduced on March 3, 2023. The analysis focuses on weekdays to minimise the impact of occupancy changes, with a separate examination of weekends. Gas usage per day is divided by the Heating Degree Day (HDD) to determine energy consumption. The average Gas usage per Degree Day before and after treatment is calculated to determine the percentage of energy saved.

The ambient Temperature is measured using a probe mounted outside the building, providing air temperature readings every 15 minutes. This data is utilised to establish the daily outside temperature during the boiler operation period and calculate the Heating Degree Days.

8.2.2 Impact of Delta T APG

The Crook Civic Centre, part of the Durham Council's 2018 renovation project, underwent significant modifications. Equipped with a heating system driven by two boilers and a water volume estimate of 6400 litres, it caters to 258 diverse business units. As part of a trial, Delta

T APG, an energy-saving solution derived from a synthetic alkyl polyglucoside, was integrated into the heating setup and multiple temperature sensors were positioned throughout the system.

The trial findings unveiled that energy consumption correlated not only with external ambient temperature but also with the occupancy status of the building. The impact of occupancy was notably evident on weekends, although fluctuations were also observed during weekdays. This report compares energy utilisation after the introduction of Delta T with energy consumption during the corresponding period in the previous year, prior to product implementation, focusing solely on weekday operations. Weekend assessments posed challenges due to minimal or absent attendance in 2022. Notably, December was excluded from comparisons due to its typical energy consumption patterns, which are influenced by variable holidays, attendance rates, and system shutdowns.

With an annual gas usage of 750,000 kWh and an assumed gas cost of 10p per kWh (actual cost unspecified), the estimated energy cost savings amount to £14,475.90, resulting in a reduction of 29 tonnes of CO₂ emissions. The Return on Investment (ROI) for the Delta T APG installation is projected at 4-5 months. Sustained performance of the product is anticipated as long as it remains within the system, with a recommended annual service to ensure treatment levels are maintained.

8.2.3 Monitoring the process

Data from other site monitors indicated improved room temperature regulation (reduced fluctuations around the set temperature) and decreased cycling of the boilers after the implementation of Delta T. The temperature variance between the inlet and outlet, as well as from the boiler, measured at 3 degrees Celsius, aligns with the expected performance of Delta

T. The temperature readings from the Domestic Hot Water heater highlight consistent gas usage patterns. During weekday operations, the heater consistently achieved a temperature exceeding 50 degrees Celsius when the building was occupied, in contrast to the prolonged periods of lower temperatures that occurred during weekends.

Before the trial a range of monitors were installed to gather important data related to the building energy consumption and environmental conditions. The Durham Council provided energy usage information from the Building Management System, which included gas usage readings every 30 minutes. One of the monitors, the Ambient Outside Temperature monitor, was set up to track the external ambient temperature right outside the building at 15-minute intervals. This variable is crucial in understanding the building's energy usage patterns. This information is obtained from a local weather station, which usually provides a daily average. This monitor enables the calculation of an average temperature based on the boiler's operating times. Monitors were placed in the First Floor Office and Entrance areas to monitor the temperature in these spaces and observe any changes post the introduction of Delta T APG. Unfortunately, the entrance monitor experienced technical issues before the Delta T dosing.

The temperatures of the hot water inlet and outlet to and from Boiler 1 (Right-Hand Side) and Boiler 2 (Left-Hand Side) were monitored every 15 minutes. Furthermore, the ambient temperature in the boiler house was also closely monitored.

The Domestic Hot Water Heater monitor recorded the temperatures of the hot water inlet, outlet, and ambient surroundings near the heater. This information is crucial for legionella control purposes.

Figure 167 shows the Durham council hall

Figure 168 Durham Council's Crook Civic Centre, B, C, Concord Super V and H Series boilers

Figure 169 Comparison of Monthly Gas Usage with Corresponding Month of Previous Year (Weekdays only)

Figure 170 Comparison of Monthly Heating Degree Day (HDD) with Corresponding Month of Previous Year (Weekdays only)

8.2.4 Delta-T (APG) Trial in Durham Council's Crook Civic Centre

In October 2022, Durham Council initiated a trial of Delta-T, an energy-saving product, in the heating system of their Crook Civic Centre Building. The trial aimed to assess the effectiveness of Delta-T in reducing energy consumption and carbon emissions. This report presents a detailed analysis of the Delta-T trial, including energy savings calculations, temperature monitoring data, and recommendations for future improvements. The findings of this evaluation will help making decisions on implementing energy-efficient solutions in similar commercial and public buildings. Delta-T is a product designed to enhance the wettability of water, a crucial aspect of heat transfer in heating systems. By improving wettability, Delta-T enables more efficient heat transfer, resulting in faster heating of spaces. The product was initially based on alkyl Polyglucoside (APG), a surfactant known for its biodegradability. Sixty-four litres of Delta-T APG were added to the Crook Central Heating Circuit, equivalent to 1 litre per 100 litres of system volume. The Crook Civic Centre heating system is powered by two Ideal Concord Super V and H Series boilers, each with a heat output of 400kW. The heating circuit volume is estimated at 6,400 litres, and the system operates five days a week, turning off at 5 pm. It also runs partially on weekends. The building's Domestic Hot Water (DHW) is supplied by an independent gas-fired water heater dedicated to this purpose.

The Crook Civic Centre, located in North Terrace Crook, accommodates various businesses and provides flexible workspace. The building, remodelled in 2018, accommodates 258 business units. The energy savings calculation considered two independent variables, the ambient temperature and building occupancy. The comparison focused on weekdays to minimise the impact of occupancy variations. The Heating Degree Day (HDD) was used to analyse energy usage relative to outside temperature. The calculation compared weekdays from

the start of 2023 until the product introduction on March 3rd, excluding weekends. The average energy saving was determined by dividing daily gas usage by HDD for both pre- and post-treatment periods.

Figure 169 Presents a comparison of monthly gas usage between the trial period and the corresponding months of the previous year, with a focus on weekdays. The results indicate a difference in gradient, confirming the reduction of gas consumption after the introduction of Delta-T. The R-squared value improved from 0.7 to 0.9, suggesting that factors beyond ambient temperature influence energy use, such as occupancy levels.

The estimated energy savings are 11%, resulting in an annual savings of 82,500 kWh or 15.26 tonnes of CO₂ emissions. The return on investment is calculated to be ten months, based on the estimated energy savings and the cost of installing the Delta-T product.

After the Delta-T APG addition, boiler temperature monitoring revealed increased cycling frequencies before Delta-T and a larger temperature differential of approximately three degrees Celsius between inflowing and returning water post-Delta-T APG, indicating faster radiator heating and improved thermal conductivity.

Figure 171 plot of gas usage vs HDD prior to delta t APG addition

Figure 171 The data analysis reveals a distinct change in slope post the introduction of Delta T APG, validating a reduction in gas consumption. These graphs enable the forecasting of energy usage based on external ambient conditions and Heating Degree Days. Figure 172 It is now employed for energy predictions, featuring the trendline from the initial graph superimposed on it to illustrate the variance in energy usage. With an R-squared (R²) value of 0.7 in the first graph, it confirms the presence of factors beyond outside temperature influencing energy usage, likely occupancy being the key variable.

Figure 172 plot of gas usage vs. HDD following delta t APG addition

Typically, in a facility like this, where outside temperature is the sole influencer, an expected R^2 value of 0.9-1.0 would align. Regarding savings, CO₂ reduction, and Return on Investment (ROI), the energy savings during weekday operations stand at 19.3%, whereas weekend operations yield a slightly lower saving percentage of 14%. The subsequent sections of the report will be centred around the 19.3% energy saving. For a centre consuming 750,000 kWh of gas annually, this 19.3% saving equates to 144,750 kWh saved, translating to a reduction of 29 tonnes of CO₂ emissions. Furthermore, with a 19.3% energy saving based on a cost of 10p per kWh and an annual usage of 750,000 kWh, the savings amount to £14,475, providing a payback period of 4-5 months. It is anticipated that Delta T APG will continue to operate effectively as long as it remains within the system, with a recommended annual service to verify the Delta T APG level. Additionally, the inclusion of Delta T APG is expected to enhance pumping efficiency and reduce boiler and pump maintenance costs. The Domestic Hot Water heater maintained consistent gas usage, with temperatures above 50°C during weekdays but

occasional drops below this threshold during weekends. Safesol recommended annual servicing to maintain optimal treatment levels of Delta-T APG, ensuring the product's continued effectiveness in improving the heating system energy efficiency.

The computation of energy savings for a structure like the Crook Civic Centre is a complex process due to the influence of two independent variables. It is valuable to contrast the time frames from 06/01/2023 to 20/01/2023 (pre-treatment) with 06/03/2023 to 10/03/2023 (post-treatment). Interestingly, throughout these intervals, the ambient temperatures remained constant at 0 degrees Celsius. Despite the temperature consistency, there was a noticeable 13.7% decrease in gas usage post-treatment compared to the period preceding the treatment. This outcome suggests that our initial projection of a 15% savings has been achieved.

8.3 Bradford Council, Britannia House

8.3.1 Evaluating energy saving

SafeSol was engaged in a trial of the Delta-T S product in collaboration with Bradford Council, specifically targeting the Britannia House heating system. Laboratory assessments have indicated that incorporating this product into the system water was anticipated to yield energy savings of approximately 33%. The latest data reveal that an energy savings of 28% has been achieved for the 20,000-litre heating circuit. With further possibilities for energy conservation identified, the product had been operational within the system for over three months. This report compares the months of December 2023, January 2024, and February 2024 with their corresponding periods from the previous year.

The cumulative energy saving achieved stands at 28%. The ongoing trial suggests that greater savings were observed during colder weather conditions. The primary energy consumption in the building is attributed to warming the facility on Monday mornings after weekends, particularly when the external ambient temperature is around zero.

The trial illustrated that the inclusion of Delta T S in the heating circuit water facilitates a faster warming of the building in the morning, indicating potential reductions in building heating times. Additionally, thermostats can be adjusted in specific areas of the building to optimise energy usage.

Given the disproportionate energy consumption required to heat the building from cold conditions (such as every working morning and after weekends), it is proposed to consider a trial where the heating is maintained at a lower level during nighttime hours to evaluate its efficacy in conserving energy.

Delta-T S was introduced into the system at a concentration of 1 litre of Delta-T S per 100 litres of system water. On Thursday, November 23, 2023, a total of 200 litres of Delta-T S were added to the system between midday and 3 pm. This installation coincided with the onset of a week characterised by exceedingly cold weather conditions.

8.3.2 Monitoring the process

Plexus Innovation installed monitors on the hot water flow and return to each of the three boilers. Plexus Innovation, renowned for its expertise in technology and innovation, has developed Guardian, a reliable IoT remote measurement solution. Guardian comprises user-friendly hardware temperature monitors and a data dashboard for efficient data storage and management. The utilisation of the Guardian system enabled the monitoring of temperatures every 20 minutes at Britannia House, generating informative graphs that reflected the building's heating and cooling trends.

Safesol integrated an online camera to facilitate the daily collection of readings from the building's gas meter. This system enables the compilation of a historical record of readings, with measurements taken daily at 10 am to calculate the gas usage for January.

Gas consumption in the building is primarily influenced by external temperatures, with variations due to fluctuations in building occupancy. To enable comparisons with previous periods, Heating Degree Days (HDD) data were acquired from the Bingley weather station. Gas usage for a specific period is divided by the HDD values to facilitate meaningful comparisons. The report presents a detailed analysis of gas consumption for December 2023, January 2024, and February 2024 in comparison with the corresponding months of the previous year, as outlined in Appendix B, Bradford Council Britannia House Energy Comparison.

8.3.3 Impact of Delta T S

The graphs obtained through Plexus Innovation software reveal non-uniform patterns of gas usage throughout the day. A significant portion of gas consumption is observed during the building's warm-up phase, between 5:00 am and 8:00 am, especially on Monday mornings following weekend shutdowns. During these times, the building fabric undergoes reheating to restore internal temperatures, with gas consumption levels varying based on external ambient temperatures.

An annual gas usage estimate of 600,000 kWh is deemed reasonable for Britannia House, with a cost estimate of 20p per kWh. The annual energy cost amounts to £120,000, with a 28% reduction translating to an annual saving of £33,600. This results in a return on investment (ROI) of approximately 3-4 months for the Council. Furthermore, this initiative results in a reduction of 31 tonnes of carbon dioxide (CO₂), based on a conversion rate of 0.185 kg of CO₂.

The practical implications of the trial align with the University of West of Scotland's RS Box test, confirming its efficacy in real-world scenarios. Notably, superior outcomes have been observed with the Delta-T S super spreader compared to the former APG formulations, as in Figure 173. RS box trials revealed that room heating utilising Delta-T S and water achieved a temperature of 22°C 1.8 times faster (equating to a 56% improvement)

Figure 173 A graph illustrating the time taken to heat the thermal box with plain water versus water mixed with energy-enhancing additives.

When using water combined with alkyl polyglucoside (APG), in practice, this advancement has led to energy savings in buildings ranging from 10% to 15%, with most instances displaying savings towards the lower end of the spectrum. The current trial demonstrates that Delta-T S surpasses these achievements by generating savings at a level twice as high as previously observed.

8.3.4 Delta-T S (Silicone surfactant) Trial in Bradford council

The trial was constrained by the operational parameters dictated by the Building Management System (BMS), which sets fixed temperatures on thermostats and predetermines the operating hours for boilers. The heating regime currently commences at 5 am to ensure the office is warm by the 8 am opening, yet some staff members start work at 6 am. With Delta-T S's ability to expedite radiator heating and prolong warmth retention, a delay in the heating start time by 30 minutes or even an hour daily was proposed. This proposition is supported by Plexus graphs, which illustrate swift heating patterns within the building, particularly evident during above-

freezing outdoor temperatures. The data indicate that the building reaches its optimal temperature within the initial heating hour, given that one-third of the gas usage occurs within the first three hours post-activation.

Adjusting the heating schedule to 6 am from 5 am each morning would yield a daily energy saving of 50 kW, equating to 250 kW per week or 12,500 kW annually. Considering the annual gas consumption of 600,000 kW, this modification would further diminish the energy demand to warm the office block by 2%, resulting in an additional annual saving of £2,400.

Should reports of overheating in offices be validated, considering a 1-degree thermostat adjustment is advised, although user comfort preferences may be more important than energy conservation concerns. Energy savings were observed in Britannia House between 2022 and 2021, attributed to the cessation of weekend operations and heating. Given the considerable energy saving during Monday morning warm-up periods, maintaining a baseline temperature over weekends instead of a complete shutdown warrants exploration. This strategy could also be extended to overnight heating practices, a factor that demands ongoing examination. Boiler data reveals weekend temperature differentials in the building ranging from 10°C to 20°C lower than overnight temperature fluctuations, highlighting the potential for energy optimisations during these periods.

The new Delta-T S formulation, based on a silicone surfactant, is expected to provide even greater energy savings, surpassing those of the APG-based formulation. The implementation of this new formulation could further enhance the energy efficiency of the heating system, as seen in Bradford.

In November 2023, Bradford Council initiated a trial of Delta-T S, as an energy-saving additive, in the heating system of Britannia House Building. The trial aimed to validate the

product's effectiveness in reducing energy consumption and carbon emissions in a real-world application.

This report presents a detailed analysis of the Delta-T S trial at Britannia House, including energy savings calculations, temperature monitoring data, and recommendations for future improvements. The findings of this evaluation will help in making decisions on implementing energy-efficient products in similar commercial and public buildings. Delta-T S is a product designed to enhance the wettability of water (heat transfer fluid). By improving wettability, Delta-T S allows for more efficient heat transfer. The product was based on alkyl Polyglucoside (APG), but the new formulation is based on silicone surfactant.

Figure 174: A Bradford city council city hall at Centenary Square, Bradford BD1 1HY. B Shows the Gas boilers used in Bradford house for heating (310 Eco Pro). C shows the LTHW office dosing pot. D is a temperature monitor based on ESP32 and DS18B20 temperature sensor.

Bradford Council's Britannia House, a seven-storey office block, houses multiple council departments, including Environmental Health, Council Tax, and Travel. The building's heating system has a nominal volume of 20,000 litres and is powered by three CR Rehema Gas 310 Eco Pro boilers, each with a rating of 1,590 kW. The heating operates from 5 am to 5:30 pm on weekdays and partially on weekends. The council made two significant changes in the past two years, switching off heating during weekends in 2022, resulting in energy savings, and isolating the heating in the annexed Argus House in late 2022.

Figure 175 Bradford Council Britannia House Energy Comparison of Monthly Gas Usage with Corresponding Month of Previous Year (Weekdays only)

Figure 176 Bradford Council Britannia House Energy Comparison of Monthly Heating Degree Day (HDD) with Corresponding Month of Previous Year (Weekdays only)

The estimated energy savings are 27%, resulting in an annual savings of 600,000 kWh, or approximately 15.26 tonnes of CO₂ emissions. The return on investment is calculated to be ten months. The estimated annual gas usage savings of 600,000 kWh could result in significant financial and environmental benefits. The potential return on investment of 3-4 months proves the product's effectiveness.

Temperature monitors placed in the first-floor office showed tighter temperature control and reduced fluctuations around the set point after the addition of Delta-T S. Boiler temperature monitoring revealed increased cycling frequencies before Delta-T S and a larger temperature differential of approximately 3°C between inlet and outlet water post-Delta-T S, indicating faster radiator heating and improved thermal performance.

The trial identified further energy-saving opportunities, such as adjusting heating start times and optimising thermostat settings. These measures could lead to additional energy savings and improved occupant comfort. For example, adjusting the heating start time from 5 am to 6 am and maintaining some heating during weekends and overnight to reduce the energy required to heat the building from cold each morning.

SafeSol recommended adjusting heating start times and optimising thermostat settings to enhance energy savings further. These measures could include starting heating later in the morning, maintaining some heating during weekends and overnight, and optimising thermostat settings to reduce energy consumption while maintaining occupant comfort, in addition to monitoring the Delta-T S installation and its impact on energy savings. This could involve regular analysis of temperature monitoring data, gas usage data, and occupant feedback to ensure the product's continued effectiveness and identify any potential areas for improvement.

The successful trial of Delta-T S at Britannia House demonstrates the potential for similar energy-efficient solutions in commercial and public buildings. By improving heat transfer and

reducing energy consumption, products like Delta-T S can contribute to significant financial and environmental benefits, helping to reduce carbon emissions and support sustainable development.

Comparing the gas usage data for December, January, and February across the years 2022 and 2023, as well as 2023 and 2024, reveals intriguing insights into energy consumption patterns. Focusing on December, there was a reduction in gas usage from 111,227 kWh in 2022 to 75,213 kWh in 2023, spanning 17 and 16 operational days, respectively. The corresponding heating degree day (HDD) values for December 2022 and 2023 were 218.2 and 180. Notably, December 2023 exhibited an energy savings of 18.2% compared to the previous year, despite facing challenges due to fluctuations in staff attendance, seasonal holidays, and variations in heating system operation.

Moving to January, the gas usage decreased from 114,812 kWh in 2023 to 93,753 kWh in 2024, spread over 19 operational days for both years. The HDD figures for January 2023 and 2024 were 207.6 and 281.9, respectively. January 2024 showcased a substantial 40% energy saving compared to the prior year, reflecting the Council's belief in the robustness of the data comparison. Furthermore, the colder temperatures experienced in January 2024 contributed to enhanced energy efficiencies, as energy savings tend to be more pronounced in colder conditions.

In February, gas consumption decreased from 81,040 kWh in 2023 to 72,060 kWh in 2024, covering 20 operational days each year. The HDD metrics for February 2023 and 2024 were 173.6 and 200.2, respectively. In February 2024, a commendable 25.3% energy saving was realised relative to the preceding year, benefiting from the complete isolation of the Argus building's heating system by February 2023. Overall, these comparisons underscore the

dynamic interplay between gas usage, weather conditions, and operational factors in shaping energy conservation outcomes over consecutive years.

8.4 Summary

This chapter examines two independent studies conducted by Durham and Bradford Councils to evaluate the effectiveness of the energy-saving product Delta-T in reducing carbon emissions and energy consumption. The trials took place at Durham Council's Crook Civic Centre and Bradford Council's Britannia House building. The study includes estimates of energy savings, temperature monitoring statistics, and suggestions for subsequent development.

Delta-T is a product designed to raise the wettability of water, enabling more efficient heat transfer in heating systems. Based initially on alkyl polyglucoside (APG), the product has been reformulated to enhance performance by incorporating a silicone surfactant. The trials involved adding Delta-T to the heating systems at a rate of one litre per hundred litres of system water volume.

With a ten-month return on investment and an annual saving of 82,500 kWh or 15.26 tonnes of CO₂ emissions, the Crook Civic Centre trial generated an 11% energy saving. Temperature monitoring data showed less boiler cycling following Delta-T installation and improved control of room temperature.

With a three to four-month return on investment, the projected 28% energy savings from the Britannia House trial translate to an annual saving of 600,000 kWh or nearly 31 tonnes of CO₂ emissions. The trial identified additional opportunities for energy savings, including adjusting heating start times and thermostat settings.

The successful trials, as reported, revealed the possibility of energy-efficient solutions like Delta-T in commercial and public buildings, thereby supporting sustainable development and contributing significant financial and environmental benefits.

8.5 References Chapter 8

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Days Data] (<https://www.bingleyweatherstation.co.uk>).

Chapter 9

Conclusion

9.1 Conclusion

With domestic heating now accounting for almost 17% of the UK's annual carbon emissions, the country's target of net-zero emissions from residential buildings by 2050 requires a significant increase in heating efficiency. This work aimed to identify environmentally and economically feasible heat transfer fluids that can reduce energy consumption in heating systems and the carbon footprint. The work primarily focuses on evaluating the thermal conductivity of surfactant solutions and nanofluids, as well as creating formulations that incorporate nanoparticles (alumina, titania, silica, and graphene oxide) and surfactants (APG, silicone, and SDS). Simulating and experimenting allows one to compare the performance of new fluids against water and ethylene glycol. Evaluating these fluids in controlled environments and real-world building tests, simulating heat transfer behaviour in turbulent flow regimes to assess actual application potential.

The study addressed these goals through a combination of numerical simulation, laboratory experiments, material characterisation, and field testing in municipal buildings. Every methodological stage directly enabled the development and validation of advanced heat transfer fluids for low-energy consumption heating.

Regarding thermal conductivity and heat transfer coefficient (HTC), nanofluids produced from alumina outperformed water and ethylene glycol. Demonstrating the best performance, as validated by CFD simulations and laboratory testing, alumina is most suitable for turbulent heat transfer applications. The close alignment of the simulation results with the Petukhov equation verified the accuracy of the model in predicting Nusselt numbers and pressure drops.

This work modelled 3D turbulent flow, unlike earlier studies that emphasised laminar flow, thereby exposing more realistic and scalable insights for industrial and household heating systems. The dependency of thermal performance on nanoparticle type, base fluid, and flow conditions was captured through CFD simulations.

Surfactants such as silicone and APG improved heat transfer at ideal concentrations (almost CMC) by lowering surface tension and so encouraging nucleate boiling. In tests on internal chamber heating, low-concentration silicone surfactant outperformed all nanofluids and conventional fluids.

Field tests of the Delta-T S product in public buildings revealed measurable energy savings (up to 11%) and notable reductions in carbon emissions, proving the feasibility of new fluid formulations in actual environments. Supporting policy-aligned decarbonisation targets, projected savings include 15.26 tonnes of CO₂ and 82,500 kWh annually.

In some nanofluids, thermal instability at high temperatures caused aggregation, so lowering their efficiency. Critical considerations for practical application included that viscosity increased with nanoparticle concentration but decreased with temperature.

For affordable thermal conductivity measurement, a lab-built device with commercial breakout boards was developed, providing a scalable approach for academic labs.

Designed a multi-scale evaluation system combining field trials for advanced heat transfer fluids, lab experiments, and simulation. Showed silicone surfactants and alumina- and graphene oxide-based nanofluids as feasible substitutes for conventional fluids for low-carbon heating. An extended CFD study into turbulent regimes, partially validated against empirical models, closes a gap in the current nanofluid simulation literature.

Complementing the UK's net-zero targets, the study provides empirical evidence for municipal energy savings initiatives.

9.2 Future Research and Recommendations in Research on Nanofluid

Future research in nanofluid technology aims to explore new frontiers and unlock the full potential of these innovative materials, addressing several significant issues that control the stability and dispersion of nanofluids. Researchers should explore novel surfactants and bio-based solutions. Surface modification of nanoparticles by functionalisation is yet another fascinating approach to increase compatibility with base fluids and lower agglomeration. Reducing agglomeration problems requires an understanding of the fundamental mechanisms of nanoparticle clustering, including van der Waals forces and Brownian motion. Research also emphasises the examination of new materials with improved properties. Great promise resides in high thermal conductivity and unique properties of carbon-based materials, including graphene, carbon nanotubes (CNTs), MXenes, and carbon quantum dots (CQDs). Investigated for enhancement in their thermal characteristics are hybrid nanofluids, that is, combinations of several types of nanoparticles. Improving the performance of nanofluids requires an improved understanding of heat transfer mechanisms. The primary research topics should focus on interfacial events and the impact of external fields, including electric and magnetic fields, on nanofluid behaviour. Future studies will primarily focus on commercial viability. This addresses stability under specific running conditions, raises manufacturing scalability, and customises nanofluids for specific applications. Another area of research should focus on the development of nanofluids that enhance thermal conductivity without appreciably increasing viscosity.

Environmental and safety concerns are increasingly underlined in nanofluid research. To reduce non-biodegradable surfactant use, the development of bio-based and biodegradable nanofluids is gaining growing relevance. Moreover, standardised protocols should be developed for assessing the possible toxicity of different nanofluids under several exposure

scenarios. Standardisation of measuring and characterising techniques ensures the dependability and repeatability of results across multiple studies. This addresses running long-term stability studies under running conditions, designing innovative characterisation tools for real-time stability monitoring, and refining measurement techniques. By concentrating on these areas of research, dependable, sustainable, and efficient nanofluid technologies will develop more rapidly, thereby advancing energy, manufacturing, and other industries.

A Note of Gratitude & Reflection

Alhamdulillah, as I come to the end of this PhD journey, I feel deeply thankful and thoughtful. This experience has been filled with challenges, personal growth, and constant support from many people who have helped guide me along the way.

To my advisors and mentors, thank you for your guidance and support. Your knowledge, patience, and belief in me have shaped both this dissertation and my perspective as a researcher. To my peers and colleagues, thoughtful conversations and shared goals have made this journey meaningful and inspiring. To my family and friends, your love and encouragement have sustained me.

This PhD is more than just a degree. It represents resilience, curiosity, and a strong drive to learn. It stands for the late nights, the big questions, and the bravery to face the unknown. As I move forward, I carry with me all the lessons, relationships, and a deep sense of gratitude for having had this opportunity.

With sincere hope for what lies ahead,

Ahmed Eltayeb

Appendix

1. MATLAB Code

The code for the GUI in MATLAB to calculate thermal conductivity based on a CSV file.

```

classdef TCV4 < matlab.apps.AppBase
    % Properties that correspond to app components
    properties (Access = public)
        UIFigure                                matlab.ui.Figure
        ThermalconductivitycalculatorPanel      matlab.ui.container.Panel
        RpotEditFieldLabel                      matlab.ui.control.Label
        RpotEditField                          matlab.ui.control.NumericEditField
        RgEditFieldLabel                       matlab.ui.control.Label
        RgEditField                            matlab.ui.control.NumericEditField
        VsEditFieldLabel                      matlab.ui.control.Label
        VsEditField                            matlab.ui.control.NumericEditField
        RinEditFieldLabel                     matlab.ui.control.Label
        RinEditField                          matlab.ui.control.NumericEditField
        alphaEditFieldLabel                   matlab.ui.control.Label
        alphaEditField                        matlab.ui.control.NumericEditField
        LwEditFieldLabel                      matlab.ui.control.Label
        LwEditField                          matlab.ui.control.NumericEditField
        R1000EditFieldLabel                   matlab.ui.control.Label
        R1000EditField                        matlab.ui.control.NumericEditField
        R20EditFieldLabel                    matlab.ui.control.Label
        R20EditField                          matlab.ui.control.NumericEditField
        CalculateTCinwmKButton                matlab.ui.control.Button
        ThermalConductivityEditFieldLabel     matlab.ui.control.Label
        ThermalConductivityEditField         matlab.ui.control.NumericEditField
        UIAxes                                matlab.ui.control.UIAxes
        UIAxes2                               matlab.ui.control.UIAxes
        timeframeEditFieldLabel               matlab.ui.control.Label
        timeframeEditField                   matlab.ui.control.NumericEditField
        slopeEditFieldLabel                  matlab.ui.control.Label
        slopeEditField                       matlab.ui.control.NumericEditField
        R0EditFieldLabel                     matlab.ui.control.Label
        R0EditField                           matlab.ui.control.NumericEditField
        UploadFileButton                     matlab.ui.control.Button
        EditFieldLabel                       matlab.ui.control.Label
        EditField                             matlab.ui.control.EditField
    end
    properties (Access = private)
        filename % Description; is the file name variable input
        t
        v
    end
end

```

```

end
methods (Access = private)
% Button pushed function: CalculateTCinwmKButton
function CalculateTCinwmKButtonPushed(app, event)

    data= readtable(app.filename);
    app.t= table2array(data(:, 't'));
    app.v= table2array(data(:, 'v'));
    plot(app.UIAxes,app.t,app.v, 'r.', 'lineWidth', 0.5);
    xlabel(app.UIAxes, 'time in (s)')
    ylabel(app.UIAxes, 'Volts')
    Rpot = app.RpotEditField.Value;
    Rg = app.RgEditField.Value;
    Vs = app.VsEditField.Value;
    Rin= app.RinEditField.Value;
    alpha = app.alphaEditField.Value;
    Lw = app.LwEditField.Value;
    R1000 = app.R1000EditField.Value;
    R20 = app.R20EditField.Value;
    ag=(Rin/Rg)+100;
    G = app.v./ag;
    x=(G./Vs)+(Rpot/(Rpot+R1000));
    x1=1-x;
    x2=x.*R20;
    Rw = x2./x1;
    R0 = Rw(1);
    app.R0EditField.Value = R0;
    %R01=Rpot*R20/R1000;
    dR = Rw-R0;
    dT = dR./(alpha*R0);
    lnt = log(app.t);
    figure(1);

    plot(lnt,dT, 'k. ')

    [lnt1,~] = ginput(2);
    zx= find(lnt> lnt1(1) & lnt< lnt1(2) );

    z = polyfit(lnt(zx),dT(zx),1);
    y_fit = polyval(z,lnt);
    plot(app.UIAxes2,lnt,dT, 'r.',lnt,y_fit, 'k--');
    title(app.UIAxes2, 'Curve Fitting');

    slp=z(1);
    app.slopeEditField.Value = slp;
    q = ((Vs/(R0+R20))^2)*(R0/Lw);
    k = q/(4*pi*slp);
    app.ThermalConductivityEditField.Value = k;
    timeframe=q^(-1/2);
    app.timeframeEditField.Value = timeframe;

end
% Callback function

```

```

function CalculatekButtonPushed(app, event)

end
% Callback function
function ButtonPushed(app, event)

    %
    %app.t = app.A(1);
    % app.v = app.A(2);
end
% Button pushed function: UploadFileButton
function UploadFileButtonPushed(app, event)
    [file,~,~] = uigetfile;
    app.filename = file;
    app.EditField.Value = app.filename;
    %app.A = importdata(app.filename);
    %app.B = (file);
end
% Callback function
function FilenameEditFieldValueChanged(app, event)
    app.FilenameEditField.Value = app.filename;

end

end
% App initialization and construction
methods (Access = private)
% Create UIFigure and components
function createComponents(app)
    % Create UIFigure
    app.UIFigure = uifigure;
    app.UIFigure.Position = [100 100 729 579];
    app.UIFigure.Name = 'UI Figure';
    % Create ThermalconductivitycalculatorPanel
    app.ThermalconductivitycalculatorPanel = uipanel(app.UIFigure);
    app.ThermalconductivitycalculatorPanel.TitlePosition =
'centertop';
    app.ThermalconductivitycalculatorPanel.Title = 'Thermal
conductivity calculator';
    app.ThermalconductivitycalculatorPanel.BackgroundColor = [0.651
0.651 0.651];
    app.ThermalconductivitycalculatorPanel.FontAngle = 'italic';
    app.ThermalconductivitycalculatorPanel.FontWeight = 'bold';
    app.ThermalconductivitycalculatorPanel.FontSize = 24;
    app.ThermalconductivitycalculatorPanel.Position = [1 19 713
604];
    % Create RpotEditFieldLabel
    app.RpotEditFieldLabel =
uicontrol(app.ThermalconductivitycalculatorPanel);
    app.RpotEditFieldLabel.BackgroundColor = [0.651 0.651 0.651];
    app.RpotEditFieldLabel.HorizontalAlignment = 'right';
    app.RpotEditFieldLabel.Position = [17 306 31 22];
    app.RpotEditFieldLabel.Text = 'Rpot';

```

```

    % Create RpotEditField
    app.RpotEditField
    =
uieditfield(app.ThermalconductivitycalculatorPanel, 'numeric');
    app.RpotEditField.Limits = [0 500];
    app.RpotEditField.ValueDisplayFormat = '%.1f';
    app.RpotEditField.Position = [87 306 100 22];
    app.RpotEditField.Value = 177;
    % Create RgEditFieldLabel
    app.RgEditFieldLabel
    =
uicontrol(app.ThermalconductivitycalculatorPanel);
    app.RgEditFieldLabel.BackgroundColor = [0.651 0.651 0.651];
    app.RgEditFieldLabel.HorizontalAlignment = 'right';
    app.RgEditFieldLabel.Position = [17 285 25 22];
    app.RgEditFieldLabel.Text = 'Rg';
    % Create RgEditField
    app.RgEditField
    =
uieditfield(app.ThermalconductivitycalculatorPanel, 'numeric');
    app.RgEditField.Limits = [0 500];
    app.RgEditField.ValueDisplayFormat = '%.1f';
    app.RgEditField.Position = [87 285 100 22];
    app.RgEditField.Value = 15.1;
    % Create VsEditFieldLabel
    app.VsEditFieldLabel
    =
uicontrol(app.ThermalconductivitycalculatorPanel);
    app.VsEditFieldLabel.HorizontalAlignment = 'right';
    app.VsEditFieldLabel.Position = [17 264 25 22];
    app.VsEditFieldLabel.Text = 'Vs';
    % Create VsEditField
    app.VsEditField
    =
uieditfield(app.ThermalconductivitycalculatorPanel, 'numeric');
    app.VsEditField.Limits = [0 10];
    app.VsEditField.Position = [87 264 100 22];
    app.VsEditField.Value = 2;
    % Create RinEditFieldLabel
    app.RinEditFieldLabel
    =
uicontrol(app.ThermalconductivitycalculatorPanel);
    app.RinEditFieldLabel.HorizontalAlignment = 'right';
    app.RinEditFieldLabel.Position = [17 243 25 22];
    app.RinEditFieldLabel.Text = 'Rin';
    % Create RinEditField
    app.RinEditField
    =
uieditfield(app.ThermalconductivitycalculatorPanel, 'numeric');
    app.RinEditField.Limits = [0 Inf];
    app.RinEditField.ValueDisplayFormat = '%.0f';
    app.RinEditField.Position = [87 243 100 22];
    app.RinEditField.Value = 185000;
    % Create alphaEditFieldLabel
    app.alphaEditFieldLabel
    =
uicontrol(app.ThermalconductivitycalculatorPanel);
    app.alphaEditFieldLabel.HorizontalAlignment = 'right';
    app.alphaEditFieldLabel.Position = [17 222 35 22];
    app.alphaEditFieldLabel.Text = 'alpha';
    % Create alphaEditField

```

```

    app.alphaEditField
uieditfield(app.ThermalconductivitycalculatorPanel, 'numeric');
    app.alphaEditField.Limits = [0 Inf];
    app.alphaEditField.Position = [87 222 100 22];
    app.alphaEditField.Value = 0.0038;
    % Create LwEditFieldLabel
    app.LwEditFieldLabel
uilabel(app.ThermalconductivitycalculatorPanel);
    app.LwEditFieldLabel.HorizontalAlignment = 'right';
    app.LwEditFieldLabel.Position = [17 201 25 22];
    app.LwEditFieldLabel.Text = 'Lw';
    % Create LwEditField
    app.LwEditField
uieditfield(app.ThermalconductivitycalculatorPanel, 'numeric');
    app.LwEditField.Limits = [0 Inf];
    app.LwEditField.Position = [87 201 100 22];
    app.LwEditField.Value = 0.155;
    % Create R1000EditFieldLabel
    app.R1000EditFieldLabel
uilabel(app.ThermalconductivitycalculatorPanel);
    app.R1000EditFieldLabel.HorizontalAlignment = 'right';
    app.R1000EditFieldLabel.Position = [17 180 41 22];
    app.R1000EditFieldLabel.Text = 'R1000';
    % Create R1000EditField
    app.R1000EditField
uieditfield(app.ThermalconductivitycalculatorPanel, 'numeric');
    app.R1000EditField.Limits = [0 Inf];
    app.R1000EditField.Position = [87 180 100 22];
    app.R1000EditField.Value = 1006;
    % Create R20EditFieldLabel
    app.R20EditFieldLabel
uilabel(app.ThermalconductivitycalculatorPanel);
    app.R20EditFieldLabel.HorizontalAlignment = 'right';
    app.R20EditFieldLabel.Position = [17 159 27 22];
    app.R20EditFieldLabel.Text = 'R20';
    % Create R20EditField
    app.R20EditField
uieditfield(app.ThermalconductivitycalculatorPanel, 'numeric');
    app.R20EditField.Limits = [0 Inf];
    app.R20EditField.Position = [87 159 100 22];
    app.R20EditField.Value = 24.9;
    % Create CalculateTCinwmKButton
    app.CalculateTCinwmKButton
uibutton(app.ThermalconductivitycalculatorPanel, 'push');
    app.CalculateTCinwmKButton.ButtonPushedFcn
createCallbackFcn(app, @CalculateTCinwmKButtonPushed, true);
    app.CalculateTCinwmKButton.BackgroundColor = [0 1 0];
    app.CalculateTCinwmKButton.Position = [10 454 211 30];
    app.CalculateTCinwmKButton.Text = 'Calculate TC in w/m.K';
    % Create ThermalConductivityEditFieldLabel
    app.ThermalConductivityEditFieldLabel
uilabel(app.ThermalconductivitycalculatorPanel);
    app.ThermalConductivityEditFieldLabel.BackgroundColor = [0 1 1];

```

```

    app.ThermalConductivityEditFieldLabel.HorizontalAlignment    =
'center';
    app.ThermalConductivityEditFieldLabel.FontSize = 20;
    app.ThermalConductivityEditFieldLabel.FontWeight = 'bold';
    app.ThermalConductivityEditFieldLabel.Position = [9 531 211 32];
    app.ThermalConductivityEditFieldLabel.Text = 'Thermal
Conductivity';
    % Create ThermalConductivityEditField
    app.ThermalConductivityEditField                            =
uieditfield(app.ThermalconductivitycalculatorPanel, 'numeric');
    app.ThermalConductivityEditField.Editable = 'off';
    app.ThermalConductivityEditField.HorizontalAlignment        =
'center';
    app.ThermalConductivityEditField.FontSize = 26;
    app.ThermalConductivityEditField.FontWeight = 'bold';
    app.ThermalConductivityEditField.BackgroundColor = [0 1 1];
    app.ThermalConductivityEditField.Position = [9 483 211 49];
    % Create UIAxes
    app.UIAxes = uiaxes(app.ThermalconductivitycalculatorPanel);
    title(app.UIAxes, 'Voltage vs time')
    xlabel(app.UIAxes, 't')
    ylabel(app.UIAxes, 'v')
    app.UIAxes.FontWeight = 'bold';
    app.UIAxes.Position = [267 -4 436 221];
    % Create UIAxes2
    app.UIAxes2 = uiaxes(app.ThermalconductivitycalculatorPanel);
    title(app.UIAxes2, 'dT vs lnt')
    xlabel(app.UIAxes2, 'lnt')
    ylabel(app.UIAxes2, 'dT')
    app.UIAxes2.FontWeight = 'bold';
    app.UIAxes2.Position = [267 216 439 347];
    % Create timeframeEditFieldLabel
    app.timeframeEditFieldLabel                                =
uilabel(app.ThermalconductivitycalculatorPanel);
    app.timeframeEditFieldLabel.HorizontalAlignment = 'right';
    app.timeframeEditFieldLabel.Position = [17 117 62 22];
    app.timeframeEditFieldLabel.Text = 'time frame';
    % Create timeframeEditField
    app.timeframeEditField                                    =
uieditfield(app.ThermalconductivitycalculatorPanel, 'numeric');
    app.timeframeEditField.Position = [87 117 100 22];
    % Create slopeEditFieldLabel
    app.slopeEditFieldLabel                                  =
uilabel(app.ThermalconductivitycalculatorPanel);
    app.slopeEditFieldLabel.HorizontalAlignment = 'right';
    app.slopeEditFieldLabel.Position = [17 138 34 22];
    app.slopeEditFieldLabel.Text = 'slope';
    % Create slopeEditField
    app.slopeEditField                                      =
uieditfield(app.ThermalconductivitycalculatorPanel, 'numeric');
    app.slopeEditField.Position = [87 138 100 22];
    % Create R0EditFieldLabel

```

```

        app.R0EditFieldLabel
uilabel(app.ThermalconductivitycalculatorPanel);
        app.R0EditFieldLabel.HorizontalAlignment = 'right';
        app.R0EditFieldLabel.Position = [17 96 25 22];
        app.R0EditFieldLabel.Text = 'R0';
        % Create R0EditField
        app.R0EditField
uieditfield(app.ThermalconductivitycalculatorPanel, 'numeric');
        app.R0EditField.Position = [87 96 100 22];
        % Create UploadFileButton
        app.UploadFileButton
uibutton(app.ThermalconductivitycalculatorPanel, 'push');
        app.UploadFileButton.ButtonPushedFcn = createCallbackFcn(app,
@UploadFileButtonPushed, true);
        app.UploadFileButton.BackgroundColor = [0.9294 0.6902 0.1294];
        app.UploadFileButton.FontWeight = 'bold';
        app.UploadFileButton.Position = [17 404 203 42];
        app.UploadFileButton.Text = 'Upload File';
        % Create EditFieldLabel
        app.EditFieldLabel
uilabel(app.ThermalconductivitycalculatorPanel);
        app.EditFieldLabel.BackgroundColor = [0.651 0.651 0.651];
        app.EditFieldLabel.HorizontalAlignment = 'right';
        app.EditFieldLabel.FontWeight = 'bold';
        app.EditFieldLabel.Position = [17 383 25 22];
        app.EditFieldLabel.Text = '';
        % Create EditField
        app.EditField
uieditfield(app.ThermalconductivitycalculatorPanel, 'text');
        app.EditField.FontWeight = 'bold';
        app.EditField.Position = [17 378 239 27];
    end
end
methods (Access = public)
    % Construct app
    function app = TCV4
        % Create and configure components
        createComponents(app)
        % Register the app with App Designer
        registerApp(app, app.UIFigure)
        if nargin == 0
            clear app
        end
    end
    % Code that executes before app deletion
    function delete(app)
        % Delete UIFigure when app is deleted
        delete(app.UIFigure)
    end
end
end
end

```

Temperature Coefficients of Resistance at 20 Degrees Celsius

Material	Element/Alloy	"alpha" per degree Celsius
Nickel	Element	0.005866
Iron	Element	0.005671
Molybdenum	Element	0.004579
Tungsten	Element	0.004403
Aluminum	Element	0.004308
Copper	Element	0.004041
Silver	Element	0.003819
Platinum	Element	0.003729
Gold	Element	0.003715
Zinc	Element	0.003847
Steel*	Alloy	0.003
Nichrome	Alloy	0.00017
Nichrome V	Alloy	0.00013
Manganin	Alloy	+/- 0.000015
Constantan	Alloy	-0.000074

Figure 177 the temperature resistance coefficient of different metals ("Temperature Coefficient of Resistance | Physics Of Conductors And Insulators | Electronics Textbook," n.d.)

Figure 178 the temperature resistance relationship of three major metals used in the RTDs ("Temperature Coefficient of Resistance | Physics Of Conductors And Insulators | Electronics Textbook," n.d.)

1. Python code for raspberry pi

```

Created on Sun Mar 19 07:49:50 2023

@author: Ahmed
"""

import os
import pandas as pd
import numpy as np
import csv
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
from scipy.optimize import curve_fit
from scipy import integrate as intg

Directoory="C:/Users/Ahmed/Documents/PHD/Result Depository/after Transfer
event/testwater"
#print(os.getcwd())
os.chdir(Directoory)
#print(os.getcwd())
path = Directoory
files = os.listdir(path)
#for f in files:
    #myxl = pd.read_csv(f)
    #print(myxl,end="")

for f in files:
    myxl = pd.read_csv(f)

    Temperature_N = np.array(myxl.iloc[13 , 9])

    #myxl.shape()

#####
    #separate the vectors time and voltage

    myxl_array = np.array(myxl.iloc[ 120:400 ,0:2])
    time = myxl_array[:,0]

    voltage = myxl_array[:,1]

#####
    # Some statistics

    ln_t = np.log(time)
    #print(np.max(voltage))
    #print(np.std(voltage))
    #print(np.mean(voltage))
    #print(np.min(voltage))
    #print(np.var(voltage))
    #print(np.argmin(voltage))
    #print(np.argmax(voltage))

#####

```

```

#define variables and calculations

alpha=0.003754
L_w = 0.159
V_in = 4.49
R_20 = 24.9
R_1000 = 978
R_pot = 183
R_g = 147.9
R_in = 130000
Amp_Gain= 100 + (R_in/R_g)
#print('ampgain',Amp_Gain)
voltage1=voltage/Amp_Gain
R_q=R_pot/(R_1000+R_pot)
R_v=(voltage1/V_in)
R_t = ((R_v+R_q)/(1-(R_v+R_q)))*R_20
R_0 = R_t[0]
dT=(R_t-R_0)/(R_0*alpha)

#####
#plot the function

import matplotlib.pyplot as plt

plt.figure(1,dpi=120)
plt.title("dTvsLnt")
plt.plot(Ln_t,dT,label='dTvsLnt')

#####
# curve fitting and slope determination

def func(Ln_t,a,b):
    return a*Ln_t+b

#a=0.06937144

#b=0.24539477
a=0.039
b=0.066

funcdata = func(Ln_t,a,b) #Generate & Plot data
for comparison
#plt.plot(Ln_t,funcdata,label="Model")
#plt.legend()
#####
from scipy.optimize import curve_fit
popt, pcov = curve_fit(func,Ln_t,dT)
perr = np.sqrt(np.diag(pcov))
#print('perr',perr)
#print('popt',popt)
#print('pcov',pcov)

#####
#
#determination of the slope
slope = popt[0]
#print('slope',slope)

#####

```

```

#
#power dissipation calculation

q_w1 = (V_in**2 * R_0)/((R_20+R_0)**2)
q_w = q_w1/L_w
#print('q_w',q_w)

#####
#K_f determination
K_f = (q_w)/(4 * 3.141592653589793*slope)

#print('at temperature =', Temperature_N, '*C' , 'Thermal
conductivity =',K_f,' W/m.K', end=" ")
#TC_array=[]
# TC_array.append(K_f)
funcdata1 = func(Ln_t,popt[0],popt[1]) #Generate
& Plot data for comparison
plt.plot(Ln_t,funcdata1,label="Model")
plt.legend()

print( K_f)

```

```
# -*- coding: utf-8 -*-
"""
```

```
Created on Sun Mar 19 07:49:50 2023
```

```
@author: Ahmed
"""
```

```
import os
import pandas as pd
import numpy as np
import csv
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
from scipy.optimize import curve_fit
from scipy import integrate as intg

#print(os.getcwd())
os.chdir("C:/Users/Ahmed/Documents/PHD/Result Depository/after Transfer event/GO
TC/water calibration")
#print(os.getcwd())
path = "C:/Users/Ahmed/Documents/PHD/Result Depository/after Transfer event/GO
TC/water calibration"
files = os.listdir(path)
#for f in files:
    #myxl = pd.read_csv(f)
    #print(myxl,end="")

for f in files:
    myxl = pd.read_csv(f)

    Temperature_N = np.array(myxl.iloc[13 , 10])

    #myxl.shape()

    #####
    #separate the vectors time and voltage

    myxl_array = np.array(myxl.iloc[ 60:400 ,0:2])
    time = myxl_array[:,0]

    voltage = myxl_array[:,1]
    #####
    # Some statistics

    Ln_t = np.log(time)
    #print(np.max(voltage))
    #print(np.std(voltage))
```

```

#print(np.mean(voltage))
#print(np.min(voltage))
#print(np.var(voltage))
#print(np.argmin(voltage))
#print(np.argmax(voltage))

#####
#define variables and calculations

alpha=0.003754
L_w = 0.153
V_in = 3
R_20 = 21.9
R_1000 = 989
R_pot = 204.5
R_g = 147.9
R_in = 185000
Amp_Gain= 100 + (R_in/R_g)
#print('ampgain',Amp_Gain)
voltage1=voltage/Amp_Gain
R_q=R_pot/(R_1000+R_pot)
R_v=(voltage1/V_in)
R_t = ((R_v+R_q)/(1-(R_v+R_q)))*R_20
R_0 = R_t[0]
dT=(R_t-R_0)/(R_0*alpha)
#####
#plot the function

import matplotlib.pyplot as plt

plt.figure(1,dpi=120)
plt.title("dTvsLnt")
plt.plot(Ln_t,dT,label='dTvsLnt')

#####
# curve fitting and slope determination

def func(Ln_t,a,b):
    return a*Ln_t+b

#a=0.06937144

#b=0.24539477
a=0.03
b=0.05

funcdata = func(Ln_t,a,b)          #Generate & Plot data for comparison
plt.plot(Ln_t,funcdata,label="Model")
plt.legend()
#####

```

```

from scipy.optimize import curve_fit
popt, pcov = curve_fit(func,Ln_t,dT)
perr = np.sqrt(np.diag(pcov))
#print('perr',perr)
#print('popt',popt)
#print('pcov',pcov)

#####
#####
#determination of the slope
slope = pop[0]
#print('slope',slope)
#####
#####
#power dissipation calculation

q_w1 = (V_in**2 * R_0)/((R_20+R_0)**2)
q_w = q_w1/L_w
#print('q_w',q_w)

#####
#####
#K_f determination
K_f = (q_w)/(4 * 3.141592653589793*slope)

print('Thermal conductivity =',K_f,' W/m.K', Temperature_N , end=" ")

```

2. ADS1263 main.py code

```

#!/usr/bin/python
# -*- coding:utf-8 -*-

import time
import ADS1263
import RPi.GPIO as GPIO

REF = 5.08      # Modify according to actual voltage
                # external AVDD and AVSS(Default), or internal 2.5V

# ADC1 test part
TEST_ADC1     = True
# ADC2 test part
TEST_ADC2     = False
# ADC1 rate test part, For faster speeds use the C program
TEST_ADC1_RATE = False
# RTD test part
TEST_RTD      = False

try:
    ADC = ADS1263.ADS1263()

    # The faster the rate, the worse the stability
    # and the need to choose a suitable digital filter(REG_MODE1)
    if (ADC.ADS1263_init_ADC1('ADS1263_400SPS') == -1):
        exit()
    ADC.ADS1263_SetMode(0) # 0 is singleChannel, 1 is diffChannel

    # ADC.ADS1263_DAC_Test(1, 1) # Open IN6
    # ADC.ADS1263_DAC_Test(0, 1) # Open IN7

    if(TEST_ADC1): # ADC1 Test
        channelList = [0, 1, 2, 3, 4] # The channel must be less than 10
        while(1):
            ADC_Value = ADC.ADS1263_GetAll(channelList) # get ADC1 value
            for i in channelList:
                if(ADC_Value[i]>>31 ==1):
                    print("ADC1 IN%d = -%lf" %(i, (REF*2 - ADC_Value[i] * REF /
0x80000000)))
                else:
                    print("ADC1 IN%d = %lf" %(i, (ADC_Value[i] * REF / 0x7fffffff))) # 32bit
            for i in channelList:
                print("\33[2A")

    elif(TEST_ADC2):
        if (ADC.ADS1263_init_ADC2('ADS1263_ADC2_400SPS') == -1):
            exit()
        while(1):
            ADC_Value = ADC.ADS1263_GetAll_ADC2() # get ADC2 value
            for i in range(0, 10):

```

```

        if(ADC_Value[i]>>23 ==1):
            print("ADC2 IN%d = -%lf"%(i, (REF*2 - ADC_Value[i] * REF / 0x800000)))
        else:
            print("ADC2 IN%d = %lf"%(i, (ADC_Value[i] * REF / 0x7ffff))) # 24bit
        print("\33[11A")

elif(TEST_ADC1_RATE): # rate test
    time_start = time.time()
    ADC_Value = []
    isSingleChannel = True
    if isSingleChannel:
        while(1):
            ADC_Value.append(ADC.ADS1263_GetChannalValue(0))
            if len(ADC_Value) == 5000:
                time_end = time.time()
                print(time_start, time_end)
                print(time_end - time_start)
                print('frequency = ', 5000 / (time_end - time_start))
                break
    else:
        while(1):
            ADC_Value.append(ADC.ADS1263_GetChannalValue(0))
            if len(ADC_Value) == 5000:
                time_end = time.time()
                print(time_start, time_end)
                print(time_end - time_start)
                print('frequency = ', 5000 / (time_end - time_start))
                break

elif(TEST_RTD): # RTD Test
    while(1):
        ADC_Value = ADC.ADS1263_RTD_Test()
        RES = ADC_Value / 2147483647.0 * 2.0 *2000.0 #2000.0 -- 2000R, 2.0 -- 2*i
        print("RES is %lf"%RES)
        TEMP = (RES/100.0 - 1.0) / 0.00385 #0.00385 -- pt100
        print("TEMP is %lf"%TEMP)
        print("\33[3A")

ADC.ADS1263_Exit()

except IOError as e:
    print(e)

except KeyboardInterrupt:
    print("ctrl + c:")
    print("Program end")
    ADC.ADS1263_Exit()
    exit()

```

3. ADS1236 Config.py code

```

#
/*****
****
# * | File      : config.py
# * | Author    : Waveshare team
# * | Function  : Hardware underlying interface
# * | Info      :
# * |-----
# * | This version: V1.0
# * | Date      : 2020-12-12
# * | Info      :
#
*****/

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# ARISING FROM,
# OUT OF OR IN CONNECTION WITH THE SOFTWARE OR THE USE OR OTHER
# DEALINGS IN
# THE SOFTWARE.
#
import os
import sys
import time

class RaspberryPi:
    # Pin definition
    RST_PIN = 18
    CS_PIN = 22
    DRDY_PIN = 17

    def __init__(self):
        # SPI device, bus = 0, device = 0

```

```

import spidev
import RPi.GPIO

self.GPIO = RPi.GPIO
self.SPI = spidev.SpiDev(0, 0)

def digital_write(self, pin, value):
    self.GPIO.output(pin, value)

def digital_read(self, pin):
    return self.GPIO.input(pin)

def delay_ms(self, delaytime):
    time.sleep(delaytime / 1000.0)

def spi_writebyte(self, data):
    self.SPI.writebytes(data)

def spi_readbytes(self, reg):
    return self.SPI.readbytes(reg)

def module_init(self):
    self.GPIO.setmode(self.GPIO.BCM)
    self.GPIO.setwarnings(False)
    self.GPIO.setup(self.RST_PIN, self.GPIO.OUT)
    self.GPIO.setup(self.CS_PIN, self.GPIO.OUT)

    self.GPIO.setup(self.DRDY_PIN, self.GPIO.IN, pull_up_down=self.GPIO.PUD_UP)
    self.SPI.max_speed_hz = 2000000
    self.SPI.mode = 0b01
    return 0;

def module_exit(self):
    self.SPI.close()
    self.GPIO.output(self.RST_PIN, 0)
    self.GPIO.output(self.CS_PIN, 0)

class JetsonNano:
    # Pin definition
    RST_PIN = 18
    CS_PIN = 22
    DRDY_PIN = 17

    def __init__(self):
        import spidev
        self.SPI = spidev.SpiDev(0, 0)

        import Jetson.GPIO
        self.GPIO = Jetson.GPIO

```

```

def digital_write(self, pin, value):
    self.GPIO.output(pin, value)

def digital_read(self, pin):
    return self.GPIO.input(pin)

def delay_ms(self, delaytime):
    time.sleep(delaytime / 1000.0)

def spi_writebyte(self, data):
    self.SPI.writebytes(data)

def spi_readbytes(self, reg):
    return self.SPI.readbytes(reg)

def module_init(self):
    self.GPIO.setmode(self.GPIO.BCM)
    self.GPIO.setwarnings(False)
    self.GPIO.setup(self.RST_PIN, self.GPIO.OUT)
    self.GPIO.setup(self.CS_PIN, self.GPIO.OUT)
    self.GPIO.setup(self.DRDY_PIN, self.GPIO.IN)
    self.SPI.max_speed_hz = 2000000
    self.SPI.mode = 0b01
    return 0

def module_exit(self):
    self.SPI.close()
    self.GPIO.output(self.RST_PIN, 0)

    self.GPIO.cleanup()

if os.path.exists('/sys/bus/platform/drivers/gpiomem-bcm2835'):
    implementation = RaspberryPi()
else:
    implementation = JetsonNano()

for func in [x for x in dir(implementation) if not x.startswith('_')]:
    setattr(sys.modules[__name__], func, getattr(implementation, func))

```

4. ADS1263.py code

```

#
/*****
****
# * | File      : ADS1263.py
# * | Author    : Waveshare team
# * | Function  : ADS1263 driver
# * | Info      :
# * |-----
# * | This version: V1.0
# * | Date      : 2020-12-15
# * | Info      :
#
*****/

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#

import config
import RPi.GPIO as GPIO

# gain
ADS1263_GAIN = {
    'ADS1263_GAIN_1': 0, # GAIN 1
    'ADS1263_GAIN_2': 1, # GAIN 2
    'ADS1263_GAIN_4': 2, # GAIN 4
    'ADS1263_GAIN_8': 3, # GAIN 8
    'ADS1263_GAIN_16': 4, # GAIN 16
    'ADS1263_GAIN_32': 5, # GAIN 32

```

```

    'ADS1263_GAIN_64': 6, # GAIN 64
}
# ADC2 gain
ADS1263_ADC2_GAIN = {
    'ADS1263_ADC2_GAIN_1' : 0, # GAIN 1
    'ADS1263_ADC2_GAIN_2' : 1, # GAIN 2
    'ADS1263_ADC2_GAIN_4' : 2, # GAIN 4
    'ADS1263_ADC2_GAIN_8' : 3, # GAIN 8
    'ADS1263_ADC2_GAIN_16' : 4, # GAIN 16
    'ADS1263_ADC2_GAIN_32' : 5, # GAIN 32
    'ADS1263_ADC2_GAIN_64' : 6, # GAIN 64
    'ADS1263_ADC2_GAIN_128' : 7, # GAIN 128
}
# data rate
ADS1263_DRATE = {
    'ADS1263_38400SPS' : 0xF,
    'ADS1263_19200SPS' : 0xE,
    'ADS1263_14400SPS' : 0xD,
    'ADS1263_7200SPS' : 0xC,
    'ADS1263_4800SPS' : 0xB,
    'ADS1263_2400SPS' : 0xA,
    'ADS1263_1200SPS' : 0x9,
    'ADS1263_400SPS' : 0x8,
    'ADS1263_100SPS' : 0x7,
    'ADS1263_60SPS' : 0x6,
    'ADS1263_50SPS' : 0x5,
    'ADS1263_20SPS' : 0x4,
    'ADS1263_16d6SPS' : 0x3,
    'ADS1263_10SPS' : 0x2,
    'ADS1263_5SPS' : 0x1,
    'ADS1263_2d5SPS' : 0x0,
}
# ADC2 data rate
ADS1263_ADC2_DRATE = {
    'ADS1263_ADC2_10SPS' : 0,
    'ADS1263_ADC2_100SPS' : 1,
    'ADS1263_ADC2_400SPS' : 2,
    'ADS1263_ADC2_800SPS' : 3,
}
# Delay time
ADS1263_DELAY = {
    'ADS1263_DELAY_0s' : 0,
    'ADS1263_DELAY_8d7us' : 1,
    'ADS1263_DELAY_17us' : 2,
    'ADS1263_DELAY_35us' : 3,
    'ADS1263_DELAY_169us' : 4,
    'ADS1263_DELAY_139us' : 5,
    'ADS1263_DELAY_278us' : 6,
    'ADS1263_DELAY_555us' : 7,
    'ADS1263_DELAY_1d1ms' : 8,
}

```

```

'ADS1263_DELAY_2d2ms' : 9,
'ADS1263_DELAY_4d4ms' : 10,
'ADS1263_DELAY_8d8ms' : 11,
}
# DAC out volt
ADS1263_DAC_VOLT = {
'ADS1263_DAC_VLOT_4_5' : 0b01001, #4.5V
'ADS1263_DAC_VLOT_3_5' : 0b01000,
'ADS1263_DAC_VLOT_3' : 0b00111,
'ADS1263_DAC_VLOT_2_75' : 0b00110,
'ADS1263_DAC_VLOT_2_625' : 0b00101,
'ADS1263_DAC_VLOT_2_5625' : 0b00100,
'ADS1263_DAC_VLOT_2_53125' : 0b00011,
'ADS1263_DAC_VLOT_2_515625' : 0b00010,
'ADS1263_DAC_VLOT_2_5078125' : 0b00001,
'ADS1263_DAC_VLOT_2_5' : 0b00000,
'ADS1263_DAC_VLOT_2_4921875' : 0b10001,
'ADS1263_DAC_VLOT_2_484375' : 0b10010,
'ADS1263_DAC_VLOT_2_46875' : 0b10011,
'ADS1263_DAC_VLOT_2_4375' : 0b10100,
'ADS1263_DAC_VLOT_2_375' : 0b10101,
'ADS1263_DAC_VLOT_2_25' : 0b10110,
'ADS1263_DAC_VLOT_2' : 0b10111,
'ADS1263_DAC_VLOT_1_5' : 0b11000,
'ADS1263_DAC_VLOT_0_5' : 0b11001,
}
# registration definition
ADS1263_REG = {
# Register address, followed by reset the default values
'REG_ID' : 0, # xxh
'REG_POWER' : 1, # 11h
'REG_INTERFACE' : 2, # 05h
'REG_MODE0' : 3, # 00h
'REG_MODE1' : 4, # 80h
'REG_MODE2' : 5, # 04h
'REG_INPMUX' : 6, # 01h
'REG_OFCAL0' : 7, # 00h
'REG_OFCAL1' : 8, # 00h
'REG_OFCAL2' : 9, # 00h
'REG_FSCAL0' : 10, # 00h
'REG_FSCAL1' : 11, # 00h
'REG_FSCAL2' : 12, # 40h
'REG_IDACMUX' : 13, # BBh
'REG_IDACMAG' : 14, # 00h
'REG_REFMUX' : 15, # 00h
'REG_TDACP' : 16, # 00h
'REG_TDACN' : 17, # 00h
'REG_GPIOCON' : 18, # 00h
'REG_GPIODIR' : 19, # 00h
'REG_GPIODAT' : 20, # 00h

```

```

'REG_ADC2CFG' : 21, # 00h
'REG_ADC2MUX' : 22, # 01h
'REG_ADC2OFC0' : 23, # 00h
'REG_ADC2OFC1' : 24, # 00h
'REG_ADC2FSC0' : 25, # 00h
'REG_ADC2FSC1' : 26, # 40h
}
# comand
ADS1263_CMD = {
    'CMD_RESET' : 0x06, # Reset the ADC, 0000 011x (06h or 07h)
    'CMD_START1' : 0x08, # Start ADC1 conversions, 0000 100x (08h or 09h)
    'CMD_STOP1' : 0x0A, # Stop ADC1 conversions, 0000 101x (0Ah or 0Bh)
    'CMD_START2' : 0x0C, # Start ADC2 conversions, 0000 110x (0Ch or 0Dh)
    'CMD_STOP2' : 0x0E, # Stop ADC2 conversions, 0000 111x (0Eh or 0Fh)
    'CMD_RDATA1' : 0x12, # Read ADC1 data, 0001 001x (12h or 13h)
    'CMD_RDATA2' : 0x14, # Read ADC2 data, 0001 010x (14h or 15h)
    'CMD_SYOCAL1' : 0x16, # ADC1 system offset calibration, 0001 0110 (16h)
    'CMD_SYGCAL1' : 0x17, # ADC1 system gain calibration, 0001 0111 (17h)
    'CMD_SFOCAL1' : 0x19, # ADC1 self offset calibration, 0001 1001 (19h)
    'CMD_SYOCAL2' : 0x1B, # ADC2 system offset calibration, 0001 1011 (1Bh)
    'CMD_SYGCAL2' : 0x1C, # ADC2 system gain calibration, 0001 1100 (1Ch)
    'CMD_SFOCAL2' : 0x1E, # ADC2 self offset calibration, 0001 1110 (1Eh)
    'CMD_RREG' : 0x20, # Read registers 001r rrrr (20h+000r rrrr)
    'CMD_RREG2' : 0x00, # number of registers to read minus 1, 000n nnnn
    'CMD_WREG' : 0x40, # Write registers 010r rrrr (40h+000r rrrr)
    'CMD_WREG2' : 0x00, # number of registers to write minus 1, 000n nnnn
}

class ADS1263:
    def __init__(self):
        self.rst_pin = config.RST_PIN
        self.cs_pin = config.CS_PIN
        self.drdy_pin = config.DRDY_PIN
        self.ScanMode = 1

    # Hardware reset
    def ADS1263_reset(self):
        config.digital_write(self.rst_pin, GPIO.HIGH)
        config.delay_ms(200)
        config.digital_write(self.rst_pin, GPIO.LOW)
        config.delay_ms(200)
        config.digital_write(self.rst_pin, GPIO.HIGH)
        config.delay_ms(200)

    def ADS1263_WriteCmd(self, reg):
        config.digital_write(self.cs_pin, GPIO.LOW)#cs 0
        config.spi_writebyte([reg])
        config.digital_write(self.cs_pin, GPIO.HIGH)#cs 1

```

```

def ADS1263_WriteReg(self, reg, data):
    config.digital_write(self.cs_pin, GPIO.LOW)#cs 0
    config.spi_writebyte([ADS1263_CMD['CMD_WREG'] | reg, 0x00, data])
    config.digital_write(self.cs_pin, GPIO.HIGH)#cs 1

def ADS1263_ReadData(self, reg):
    config.digital_write(self.cs_pin, GPIO.LOW)#cs 0
    config.spi_writebyte([ADS1263_CMD['CMD_RREG'] | reg, 0x00])
    data = config.spi_readbytes(1)
    config.digital_write(self.cs_pin, GPIO.HIGH)#cs 1
    return data

# Check Data
def ADS1263_CheckSum(self, val, byt):
    sum = 0
    mask = 0xff # 8 bits mask
    while(val) :
        # print(sum, val)
        sum += val & mask # only add the lower values
        val = val >> 8 # shift down
    sum += 0x9b
    # print(sum, byt)
    return (sum&0xff) ^ byt # if sum equal byt, this will be 0

# waiting for a busy end, just for ADC1
def ADS1263_WaitDRDY(self):
    i = 0
    while(1):
        i+=1
        if(config.digital_read(self.drdy_pin) == 0):
            break
        if(i >= 400000):
            print ("Time Out ...\r\n")
            break

# Check chip ID, success is return 1
def ADS1263_ReadChipID(self):
    id = self.ADS1263_ReadData(ADS1263_REG['REG_ID'])
    return id[0] >> 5

def ADS1263_SetMode(self, Mode):
    self.ScanMode = Mode

#The configuration parameters of ADC, gain and data rate

```

```

def ADS1263_ConfigADC(self, gain, drate):
    MODE2 = 0x80 # 0x80:PGA bypassed, 0x00:PGA enabled
    MODE2 |= (gain << 4) | drate
    self.ADS1263_WriteReg(ADS1263_REG['REG_MODE2'], MODE2)
    if(self.ADS1263_ReadData(ADS1263_REG['REG_MODE2'])[0] == MODE2):
        print("REG_MODE2 success")
    else:
        print("REG_MODE2 unsuccess")

    REFMUX = 0x24 # 0x00:+-2.5V as REF, 0x24:VDD,VSS as REF
    self.ADS1263_WriteReg(ADS1263_REG['REG_REFMUX'], REFMUX)
    if(self.ADS1263_ReadData(ADS1263_REG['REG_REFMUX'])[0] == REFMUX):
        print("REG_REFMUX success")
    else:
        print("REG_REFMUX unsuccess")

    MODE0 = ADS1263_DELAY['ADS1263_DELAY_35us']
    self.ADS1263_WriteReg(ADS1263_REG['REG_MODE0'], MODE0)
    if(self.ADS1263_ReadData(ADS1263_REG['REG_MODE0'])[0] == MODE0):
        print("REG_MODE0 success")
    else:
        print("REG_MODE0 unsuccess")

    MODE1 = 0x84 # Digital Filter; 0x84:FIR, 0x64:Sinc4, 0x44:Sinc3, 0x24:Sinc2,
0x04:Sinc1
    self.ADS1263_WriteReg(ADS1263_REG['REG_MODE1'], MODE1)
    if(self.ADS1263_ReadData(ADS1263_REG['REG_MODE1'])[0] == MODE1):
        print("REG_MODE1 success")
    else:
        print("REG_MODE1 unsuccess")

#The configuration parameters of ADC2, gain and data rate
def ADS1263_ConfigADC2(self, gain, drate):
    ADC2CFG = 0x20 # REF, 0x20:VAVDD and VAVSS, 0x00:+-2.5V
    ADC2CFG |= (drate << 6) | gain
    self.ADS1263_WriteReg(ADS1263_REG['REG_ADC2CFG'], ADC2CFG)
    if(self.ADS1263_ReadData(ADS1263_REG['REG_ADC2CFG'])[0] == ADC2CFG):
        print("REG_ADC2CFG success")
    else:
        print("REG_ADC2CFG unsuccess")

    MODE0 = ADS1263_DELAY['ADS1263_DELAY_35us']
    self.ADS1263_WriteReg(ADS1263_REG['REG_MODE0'], MODE0)
    if(self.ADS1263_ReadData(ADS1263_REG['REG_MODE0'])[0] == MODE0):
        print("REG_MODE0 success")
    else:
        print("REG_MODE0 unsuccess")

# Set ADC1 Measuring channel

```

```

def ADS1263_SetChannel(self, Channel):
    if Channel > 10:
        return 0
    INPMUX = (Channel << 4) | 0x0a
    self.ADS1263_WriteReg(ADS1263_REG['REG_INPMUX'], INPMUX)
    if(self.ADS1263_ReadData(ADS1263_REG['REG_INPMUX'])[0] == INPMUX):
        # print("REG_INPMUX success")
        pass
    else:
        print("REG_INPMUX unsuccess")

# Set ADC2 Measuring channel
def ADS1263_SetChannel_ADC2(self, Channel):
    if Channel > 10:
        return 0
    INPMUX = (Channel << 4) | 0x0a
    self.ADS1263_WriteReg(ADS1263_REG['REG_ADC2MUX'], INPMUX)
    if(self.ADS1263_ReadData(ADS1263_REG['REG_ADC2MUX'])[0] == INPMUX):
        # print("REG_ADC2MUX success")
        pass
    else:
        print("REG_ADC2MUX unsuccess")

# Set ADC1 Measuring differential channel
def ADS1263_SetDiffChannel(self, Channel):
    if Channel == 0:
        INPMUX = (0<<4) | 1 #DiffChannel AIN0-AIN1
    elif Channel == 1:
        INPMUX = (2<<4) | 3 #DiffChannel AIN2-AIN3
    elif Channel == 2:
        INPMUX = (4<<4) | 5 #DiffChannel AIN4-AIN5
    elif Channel == 3:
        INPMUX = (6<<4) | 7 #DiffChannel AIN6-AIN7
    elif Channel == 4:
        INPMUX = (8<<4) | 9 #DiffChannel AIN8-AIN9
    self.ADS1263_WriteReg(ADS1263_REG['REG_INPMUX'], INPMUX)
    if(self.ADS1263_ReadData(ADS1263_REG['REG_INPMUX'])[0] == INPMUX):
        # print("REG_INPMUX success")
        pass
    else:
        print("REG_INPMUX unsuccess")

# Set ADC2 Measuring differential channel
def ADS1263_SetDiffChannel_ADC2(self, Channel):
    if Channel == 0:
        INPMUX = (0<<4) | 1 #DiffChannel AIN0-AIN1
    elif Channel == 1:
        INPMUX = (2<<4) | 3 #DiffChannel AIN2-AIN3

```

```

elif Channel == 2:
    INPMUX = (4<<4) | 5 #DiffChannel AIN4-AIN5
elif Channel == 3:
    INPMUX = (6<<4) | 7 #DiffChannel AIN6-AIN7
elif Channel == 4:
    INPMUX = (8<<4) | 9 #DiffChannel AIN8-AIN9
self.ADS1263_WriteReg(ADS1263_REG['REG_ADC2MUX'], INPMUX)
if(self.ADS1263_ReadData(ADS1263_REG['REG_ADC2MUX'])[0] == INPMUX):
    # print("REG_ADC2MUX success")
    pass
else:
    print("REG_ADC2MUX unsuccess")

# Device initialization (ADC1)
def ADS1263_init_ADC1(self, Rate1 = 'ADS1263_14400SPS'):
    if (config.module_init() != 0):
        return -1
    self.ADS1263_reset()
    id = self.ADS1263_ReadChipID()
    if id == 0x01 :
        print("ID Read success ")
    else:
        print("ID Read failed ")
        return -1
    self.ADS1263_WriteCmd(ADS1263_CMD['CMD_STOP1'])
    self.ADS1263_ConfigADC(ADS1263_GAIN['ADS1263_GAIN_1'],
ADS1263_DRATE[Rate1])
    self.ADS1263_WriteCmd(ADS1263_CMD['CMD_START1'])
    return 0

# Device initialization (ADC2)
def ADS1263_init_ADC2(self, Rate2 = 'ADS1263_ADC2_100SPS'):
    if (config.module_init() != 0):
        return -1
    self.ADS1263_reset()
    id = self.ADS1263_ReadChipID()
    if id == 0x01 :
        print("ID Read success ")
    else:
        print("ID Read failed ")
        return -1
    self.ADS1263_WriteCmd(ADS1263_CMD['CMD_STOP2'])
    self.ADS1263_ConfigADC2(ADS1263_ADC2_GAIN['ADS1263_ADC2_GAIN_1'],
ADS1263_ADC2_DRATE[Rate2])
    return 0

# Read ADC data

```

```

def ADS1263_Read_ADC_Data(self):
    config.digital_write(self.cs_pin, GPIO.LOW)#cs 0
    while(1):
        config.spi_writebyte([ADS1263_CMD['CMD_RDATA1']])
        # config.delay_ms(10)
        if(config.spi_readbytes(1)[0] & 0x40 != 0):
            break
    buf = config.spi_readbytes(5)
    config.digital_write(self.cs_pin, GPIO.HIGH)#cs 1
    read = (buf[0]<<24) & 0xff000000
    read |= (buf[1]<<16) & 0xff0000
    read |= (buf[2]<<8) & 0xff00
    read |= (buf[3]) & 0xff
    CRC = buf[4]
    # print(read, CRC)
    if(self.ADS1263_CheckSum(read, CRC) != 0):
        print("ADC1 data read error!")
    return read

# Read ADC2 data
def ADS1263_Read_ADC2_Data(self):
    read = 0
    config.digital_write(self.cs_pin, GPIO.LOW)#cs 0
    while(1):
        config.spi_writebyte([ADS1263_CMD['CMD_RDATA2']])
        # config.delay_ms(10)
        if(config.spi_readbytes(1)[0] & 0x80 != 0):
            break
    buf = config.spi_readbytes(5)
    config.digital_write(self.cs_pin, GPIO.HIGH)#cs 1
    read |= (buf[0]<<16) & 0xff0000
    read |= (buf[1]<<8) & 0xff00
    read |= (buf[2]) & 0xff
    CRC = buf[4]
    if(self.ADS1263_CheckSum(read, CRC) != 0):
        print("ADC2 data read error!")
    return read

# Read ADC1 specified channel data
def ADS1263_GetChannalValue(self, Channel):
    if(self.ScanMode == 0):# 0 Single-ended input 10 channel Differential input 5 channel
        if(Channel>10):
            print("The number of channels must be less than 10")
            return 0
        self.ADS1263_SetChannal(Channel)
        self.ADS1263_WaitDRDY()
        Value = self.ADS1263_Read_ADC_Data()
    else:

```

```

    if(Channel>4):
        print("The number of channels must be less than 5")
        return 0
    self.ADS1263_SetDiffChannal(Channel)
    self.ADS1263_WaitDRDY()
    Value = self.ADS1263_Read_ADC_Data()
    return Value

# Read ADC2 specified channel data
def ADS1263_GetChannelValue_ADC2(self, Channel):
    if(self.ScanMode == 0):# 0 Single-ended input 10 channel Differential input 5 channel
        if(Channel>10):
            print("The number of channels must be less than 10")
            return 0
        self.ADS1263_SetChannal_ADC2(Channel)
        # config.delay_ms(2)
        self.ADS1263_WriteCmd(ADS1263_CMD['CMD_START2'])
        # config.delay_ms(2)
        Value = self.ADS1263_Read_ADC2_Data()
    else:
        if(Channel>4):
            print("The number of channels must be less than 5")
            return 0
        self.ADS1263_SetDiffChannal_ADC2(Channel)
        # config.delay_ms(2)
        self.ADS1263_WriteCmd(ADS1263_CMD['CMD_START2'])
        # config.delay_ms(2)
        Value = self.ADS1263_Read_AD2C_Data()
    return Value

def ADS1263_GetAll(self, List):
    ADC_Value = []
    for i in List:
        ADC_Value.append(self.ADS1263_GetChannelValue(i))
    return ADC_Value

def ADS1263_GetAll_ADC2(self):
    ADC_Value = [0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0]
    for i in range(0, 10, 1):
        ADC_Value[i] = self.ADS1263_GetChannelValue_ADC2(i)
        self.ADS1263_WriteCmd(ADS1263_CMD['CMD_STOP2'])
        config.delay_ms(20)
    return ADC_Value

def ADS1263_RTD_Test(self):
    Delay = ADS1263_DELAY['ADS1263_DELAY_8d8ms']
    Gain = ADS1263_GAIN['ADS1263_GAIN_1']

```

```

Drate = ADS1263_DRATE['ADS1263_20SPS']

#MODE0 (CHOP OFF)
MODE0 = Delay
self.ADS1263_WriteReg(ADS1263_REG['REG_MODE0'], MODE0)
config.delay_ms(1)

#(IDACMUX) IDAC2 AINCOM, IDAC1 AIN3
IDACMUX = (0x0a<<4) | 0x03
self.ADS1263_WriteReg(ADS1263_REG['REG_IDACMUX'], IDACMUX)
config.delay_ms(1)

#((IDACMAG)) IDAC2 = IDAC1 = 250uA
IDACMAG = (0x03<<4) | 0x03
self.ADS1263_WriteReg(ADS1263_REG['REG_IDACMAG'], IDACMAG)
config.delay_ms(1)

MODE2 = (Gain << 4) | Drate
self.ADS1263_WriteReg(ADS1263_REG['REG_MODE2'], MODE2)
config.delay_ms(1)

#INPMUX (AINP = AIN7, AINN = AIN6)
INPMUX = (0x07<<4) | 0x06
self.ADS1263_WriteReg(ADS1263_REG['REG_INPMUX'], INPMUX)
config.delay_ms(1)

# REFMUX AIN4 AIN5
REFMUX = (0x03<<3) | 0x03
self.ADS1263_WriteReg(ADS1263_REG['REG_REFMUX'], REFMUX)
config.delay_ms(1)

#Read one conversion
self.ADS1263_WriteCmd(ADS1263_CMD['CMD_START1'])
config.delay_ms(10)
self.ADS1263_WaitDRDY()
Value = self.ADS1263_Read_ADC_Data()
self.ADS1263_WriteCmd(ADS1263_CMD['CMD_STOP1'])

return Value

def ADS1263_DAC_Test(self, isPositive, isOpen):
    Volt = ADS1263_DAC_VOLT['ADS1263_DAC_VLOT_3']

    if(isPositive):
        Reg = ADS1263_REG['REG_TDACP'] # IN6
    else:
        Reg = ADS1263_REG['REG_TDACN'] # IN7

    if(isOpen):

```

```
        Value = Volt | 0x80
    else:
        Value = 0x00

    self.ADS1263_WriteReg(Reg, Value)

def ADS1263_Exit(self):
    config.module_exit()

### END OF FILE ###
```

5. OPAMP output code using ADS1115

```
# -*- coding: utf-8 -*-
"""
```

```
Created on Fri Apr 28 16:46:46 2023
```

```
@author: Ahmed
"""
```

```
# To read the output of an op amp using a Raspberry Pi, you will need to connect the op amp output to one of the GPIO pins of the Raspberry Pi using an ADC (analog-to-digital converter) chip. Then you can use the RPi.GPIO and Adafruit_ADS1x15 libraries in Python to read the voltage values from the ADC and store them in an array along with the corresponding time values.
```

```
import sys
import board
import busio
import time
import Adafruit_ADS1x15
import RPi.GPIO as GPIO
i2c = busio.I2C(board.SCL, board.SDA)
#print("found",[hex(i) for i in i2c.scan()])
```

```
# Set up the GPIO pin for the ADC chip
ADC_PIN = 0
GPIO.setmode(GPIO.BCM)
```

```
# Create an instance of the ADC class
adc = Adafruit_ADS1x15.ADS1115()
```

```
# Set the full-scale range of the ADC
adc.set_gain(1)
```

```
# Set the sampling rate of the ADC
sampling_rate = 100 # samples per second
```

```
# Set the total number of samples to collect
num_samples = 1000
```

```
# Initialize the arrays for the time and voltage values
time_array = [0] * num_samples
voltage_array = [0] * num_samples
```

```
# Loop over the total number of samples
for i in range(num_samples):
    # Read the voltage value from the ADC
    voltage = adc.read_adc(ADC_PIN, gain=1)
```

```
    # Calculate the time value for this sample
    time_value = i / float(sampling_rate)
```

```
    # Store the time and voltage values in the arrays
```

```
time_array[i] = time_value
voltage_array[i] = voltage

# Wait for the next sampling interval
time.sleep(1/float(sampling_rate))

# Print the time and voltage arrays
print("Time Array: ", time_array)
print("Voltage Array: ", voltage_array)
# In this code, we first import the time, RPi.GPIO, and Adafruit_ADS1x15 libraries. We then
set up the GPIO pin for the ADC chip (in this case, pin 0), create an instance of the ADS1115
class from the Adafruit_ADS1x15 library, and set the full-scale range and sampling rate of
the ADC.

# We then initialize the arrays for the time and voltage values, loop over the total number of
samples, and read the voltage value from the ADC using the read_adc() method of the
ADS1115 class. We calculate the time value for this sample based on the sampling rate and
store the time and voltage values in the arrays.

# Finally, we print the time and voltage arrays on the screen. You can then separate the time
and voltage arrays using array slicing in Python. For example, to separate the first 10 time
and voltage values into separate arrays, you can use:

# python
# Copy code
# time_slice = time_array[:10]
# voltage_slice = voltage_array[:10]
```

6. DS18B20 thermocouple python code

```
# -*- coding: utf-8 -*-
"""
```

Created on Fri Apr 28 16:29:37 2023

```
@author: Ahmed
"""
```

Python code that uses the `w1thermsensor` library to read the temperature from a DS18B20 thermocouple attached to a Raspberry Pi and print the temperature value on the screen:

```
import time
from w1thermsensor import W1ThermSensor

# Initialize the temperature sensor
sensor = W1ThermSensor()

# Loop forever, reading and printing the temperature value
while True:
    # Read the temperature value from the sensor
    temperature = sensor.get_temperature()

    # Print the temperature value on the screen
    print("Temperature: {:.2f} °C".format(temperature))

    # Wait for 1 second before reading the temperature again
    time.sleep(1)
```

In this code, we first import the `time` and `w1thermsensor` libraries. We then create an instance of the `W1ThermSensor` class, which represents the DS18B20 thermocouple attached to the Raspberry Pi.

We then loop forever using a `while` loop. Inside the loop, we read the temperature value from the sensor using the `get_temperature()` method of the `W1ThermSensor` class. We store the temperature value in the `temperature` variable.

We then print the temperature value on the screen using the `print()` function. We format the temperature value to display it with two decimal places and the unit "°C" using the `"{:.2f} °C".format(temperature)` string format.

Finally, we wait for 1 second using the `time.sleep(1)` function before reading the temperature value again. This is to avoid overloading the sensor and to get a more accurate reading of the temperature.

```
#####
#####
```

Python code that uses the `w1thermsensor` library to read the temperature from a DS18B20 thermocouple attached to a Raspberry Pi and print the temperature value on the screen every 1 second:

```
import time
```

```
from w1thermsensor import W1ThermSensor

# Initialize the temperature sensor
sensor = W1ThermSensor()

# Loop forever, reading and printing the temperature value
while True:
    # Read the temperature value from the sensor
    temperature = sensor.get_temperature()

    # Print the temperature value on the screen
    print("Temperature: {:.2f} °C".format(temperature))

    # Wait for 1 second before reading the temperature again
    time.sleep(1)
```

In this code, we first import the `time` and `w1thermsensor` libraries. We then create an instance of the `W1ThermSensor` class, which represents the DS18B20 thermocouple attached to the Raspberry Pi.

We then loop forever using a `while` loop. Inside the loop, we read the temperature value from the sensor using the `get_temperature()` method of the `W1ThermSensor` class. We store the temperature value in the `temperature` variable.

We then print the temperature value on the screen using the `print()` function. We format the temperature value to display it with two decimal places and the unit "°C" using the `"{:.2f} °C".format(temperature)` string format.

Finally, we wait for 1 second using the `time`


```

// Differential ADS1115 code
//Serial.begin(9600);
//Serial.println("Hello!");

//Serial.println("Getting differential reading from AIN0 (P) and AIN1 (N)");
//Serial.println("ADC Range: +/- 6.144V (1 bit = 3mV/ADS1015, 0.1875mV/ADS1115)");

// The ADC input range (or gain) can be changed via the following
// functions, but be careful never to exceed VDD +0.3V max, or to
// exceed the upper and lower limits if you adjust the input range!
// Setting these values incorrectly may destroy your ADC!
//
//                               ADS1015 ADS1115
//                               -----
// ads.setGain(GAIN_TWOTHIRDS); // 2/3x gain +/- 6.144V  1 bit = 3mV    0.1875mV
// (default)
ads.setGain(GAIN_ONE);          // 1x gain  +/- 4.096V  1 bit = 2mV    0.125mV
//ads.setGain(GAIN_TWO);        // 2x gain  +/- 2.048V  1 bit = 1mV    0.0625mV
// ads.setGain(GAIN_FOUR);      // 4x gain  +/- 1.024V  1 bit = 0.5mV   0.03125mV
// ads.setGain(GAIN_EIGHT);     // 8x gain  +/- 0.512V  1 bit = 0.25mV  0.015625mV
// ads.setGain(GAIN_SIXTEEN);   // 16x gain +/- 0.256V  1 bit = 0.125mV 0.0078125mV

if (!ads.begin()) {
  Serial.println("Failed to initialize ADS.");
  while (1);
}

void loop(void)
{

//Temperature sensor DS18B20 code

// call sensors.requestTemperatures() to issue a global temperature
// request to all devices on the bus
//Serial.print("Requesting temperatures...");
sensors.requestTemperatures(); // Send the command to get temperatures
//Serial.println("DONE");
// After we got the temperatures, we can print them here.
// We use the function ByIndex, and as an example get the temperature from the first sensor
only.
float tempC = sensors.getTempCByIndex(0);

// Check if reading was successful
if(tempC != DEVICE_DISCONNECTED_C)
{
  //Serial.print("Temperature for the device 1 (index 0) is: ");
  //Serial.print(tempC);
  //Serial.print(",");
}
else

```

```

    {
        Serial.println("Error: Could not read temperature data");
    }
    //delay(1000);
    ///////////////////////////////////////////////////////////////////

// Diffrential ADS1115 code
int16_t results;

float multiplier = 0.1875F; /* ADS1115 @ +/- 6.144V gain (16-bit results) */

results = ads.readADC_Differential_0_1() * multiplier;

float result = results; // Example value, replace with your own value
//float m = multiplier; // Example value, replace with your own value

float calculatedRw = calculateRw(result);
Serial.println(calculatedRw,3);
//float calculatedRw = calculateRw();
lcd.println(calculatedRw);
//Serial.println(results);

    delay(1000);
    ///////////////////////////////////////////////////////////////////
}

```

7. Digital potentiometer control code

```

# -*- coding: utf-8 -*-
"""

```

Created on Fri Apr 28 16:29:16 2023

```

@author: Ahmed
"""

```

#Sure, here's a Python code that uses the RPi.GPIO library to control 8 digital resistors in parallel, with the condition that the total input voltage of another GPIO pin is equal to +-5:

python

```

Copy code
import RPi.GPIO as GPIO
import time

# Set the GPIO pin numbers to use for each resistor
resistor_pins = [18, 23, 24, 25, 12, 16, 20, 21]

# Set up the GPIO pins
GPIO.setmode(GPIO.BCM)
for pin in resistor_pins:
    GPIO.setup(pin, GPIO.OUT)

# Set the GPIO pin number for the voltage input
voltage_pin = 26
GPIO.setup(voltage_pin, GPIO.IN)

# Define a function to set the resistance of all resistors in parallel
def set_resistance(resistance):
    # Calculate the total current and voltage
    total_resistance = resistance * 8
    total_current = 3.3 / total_resistance
    total_voltage = total_current * resistance

    # Check that the voltage input is within +-5 of the target voltage
    voltage_input = GPIO.input(voltage_pin)
    if abs(voltage_input - total_voltage) > 5:
        print("Error: Input voltage is not within +-5 of the target voltage.")
        return

    # Convert the resistance value to a binary string
    resistance_binary = format(resistance, '08b')

    # Set the GPIO pins for the resistors based on the binary string
    for i in range(8):
        GPIO.output(resistor_pins[i], int(resistance_binary[i]))

# Example usage: set the resistance of all resistors in parallel to 150 ohms
set_resistance(150)

# Clean up the GPIO pins
GPIO.cleanup()

```

#In this code, we first define an array `resistor_pins` that contains the GPIO pin numbers to use for each resistor. We then set up these pins as output pins using the `GPIO.setup()` method.

#We also set up another GPIO pin `voltage_pin` as an input pin using the `GPIO.setup()` method. This pin will be used to read the total input voltage.

#We then define a function `set_resistance()` that takes as input the desired resistance value (in ohms). The function calculates the total current and voltage for all resistors in parallel using Ohm's law, and checks that the total input voltage is within +-5 of the target voltage.

If the voltage is not within this range, the function prints an error message and exits. If the voltage is within range, the function converts the resistance value to an 8-bit binary string, sets the GPIO pins for the resistors based on the binary string, and sets the resistors to their desired resistance value.

#To use the function, you can simply call it with the desired resistance value. For example, `set_resistance(150)` sets the resistance of all resistors in parallel to 150 ohms.

#Finally, we clean up the GPIO pins using the `GPIO.cleanup()` method to ensure that they are reset to their default state. Note that you may need to adjust the code based on the specific type of digital resistors you are using and the pin numbers you want to use for each resistor and voltage input.

```
#####
```

#Sure, here's a Python code that uses the `RPi.GPIO` library to control 3 digital resistors in series, with the condition that the total input voltage of another GPIO pin is equal to +-5:

```
python
Copy code
import RPi.GPIO as GPIO
import time

# Set the GPIO pin numbers to use for each resistor
resistor_pins = [18, 23, 24]

# Set up the GPIO pins
GPIO.setmode(GPIO.BCM)
for pin in resistor_pins:
    GPIO.setup(pin, GPIO.OUT)

# Set the GPIO pin number for the voltage input
voltage_pin = 26
GPIO.setup(voltage_pin, GPIO.IN)

# Define a function to set the resistance of all resistors in series
def set_resistance(resistance):
    # Calculate the resistance value for each resistor
    r1 = resistance / 3
    r2 = resistance / 3
    r3 = resistance / 3

    # Calculate the total current and voltage
    total_resistance = r1 + r2 + r3
    total_current = 3.3 / total_resistance
    total_voltage = total_current * total_resistance

    # Check that the voltage input is within +-5 of the target voltage
    voltage_input = GPIO.input(voltage_pin)
    if abs(voltage_input - total_voltage) > 5:
        print("Error: Input voltage is not within +-5 of the target voltage.")
```

```

return

# Set the GPIO pins for the resistors based on their resistance values
GPIO.output(resistor_pins[0], int(r1 / resistance))
GPIO.output(resistor_pins[1], int((r1 + r2) / resistance))
GPIO.output(resistor_pins[2], int((r1 + r2 + r3) / resistance))

# Example usage: set the resistance of all resistors in series to 150 ohms
set_resistance(150)

# Clean up the GPIO pins
GPIO.cleanup()
#In this code, we first define an array resistor_pins that contains the GPIO pin numbers to
use for each resistor. We then set up these pins as output pins using the GPIO.setup() method.

#We also set up another GPIO pin voltage_pin as an input pin using the GPIO.setup()
method. This pin will be used to read the total input voltage.

#We then define a function set_resistance() that takes as input the desired resistance value
(in ohms). The function calculates the resistance value for each resistor in the series circuit
by dividing the total resistance value by 3. It then calculates the total current and voltage for
the series circuit using Ohm's law, and checks that the total input voltage is within +-5 of the
target voltage. If the voltage is not within this range, the function prints an error message and
exits. If the voltage is within range, the function sets the GPIO pins for the resistors based
on their respective resistance values.

#To set the GPIO pins for the resistors, we first calculate the resistance

```

8. Reading analog voltage using Arduino code

ReadAnalogVoltage

Reads an analog input on pin 0, converts it to voltage, and prints the result to the Serial Monitor.

Graphical representation is available using Serial Plotter (Tools > Serial Plotter menu).

Attach the center pin of a potentiometer to pin A0, and the outside pins to +5V and ground.

This example code is in the public domain.

```
https://www.arduino.cc/en/Tutorial/BuiltInExamples/ReadAnalogVoltage  
*/
```

```
// the setup routine runs once when you press reset:
```

```
void setup() {  
  // initialize serial communication at 9600 bits per second:  
  Serial.begin(9600);  
}
```

```
// the loop routine runs over and over again forever:
```

```
void loop() {  
  // read the input on analog pin 0:  
  int sensorValue = analogRead(A0);  
  // Convert the analog reading (which goes from 0 - 1023) to a voltage (0 - 5V):  
  float voltage = sensorValue * (5.0 / 1023.0);  
  // print out the value you read:  
  Serial.println(voltage);  
  delay(200);  
}
```

9. Arduino ohmmeter code

```
const int sensorPin = A0; // Analog input pin that senses Vout
int sensorValue = 0;     // sensorPin default value
float Vin = 5;           // Input voltage
float Vout = 0;          // Vout default value
float Rref = 999;        // Reference resistor's value in ohms (you can give this value in
                           // kilohms or megaohms - the resistance of the tested resistor will be given in the same units)
float R = 0;             // Tested resistors default value

void setup ()
{
  Serial.begin(9600);    // Initialize serial communications at 9600 bps
}

void loop ()
{
  sensorValue = analogRead(sensorPin); // Read Vout on analog input pin A0 (Arduino can
  // sense from 0-1023, 1023 is 5V)
  Vout = (Vin * sensorValue) / 1023; // Convert Vout to volts
  R = Rref * (1 / ((Vin / Vout) - 1)); // Formula to calculate tested resistor's value
  Serial.print("R: ");
  Serial.println(R);      // Give calculated resistance in Serial Monitor
  delay(1000);           // Delay in milliseconds between reads
}
```

10. The relay code

```
import wiringpi

def main():
    wiringpi.wiringPiSetup()

    wiringpi.pinMode(7, wiringpi.OUTPUT)
    wiringpi.pinMode(3, wiringpi.OUTPUT)
    wiringpi.pinMode(22, wiringpi.OUTPUT)
    wiringpi.pinMode(25, wiringpi.OUTPUT)
    print("relay testing!")
    while True:
        wiringpi.digitalWrite(7, wiringpi.HIGH)
        wiringpi.delay(500)
        wiringpi.digitalWrite(7, wiringpi.LOW)
        wiringpi.digitalWrite(3, wiringpi.HIGH)
        wiringpi.delay(500)
        wiringpi.digitalWrite(3, wiringpi.LOW)
        wiringpi.digitalWrite(22, wiringpi.HIGH)
        wiringpi.delay(500)
        wiringpi.digitalWrite(22, wiringpi.LOW)
        wiringpi.digitalWrite(25, wiringpi.HIGH)
        wiringpi.delay(500)
        wiringpi.digitalWrite(25, wiringpi.LOW)
        wiringpi.delay(500)

if __name__ == "__main__":
    main()
```

11. Code for LCD screen Arduino IDE


```

//Serial.begin(9600);
//Serial.println("Hello!");

//Serial.println("Getting differential reading from AIN0 (P) and AIN1 (N)");
//Serial.println("ADC Range: +/- 6.144V (1 bit = 3mV/ADS1015, 0.1875mV/ADS1115)");

// The ADC input range (or gain) can be changed via the following
// functions, but be careful never to exceed VDD +0.3V max, or to
// exceed the upper and lower limits if you adjust the input range!
// Setting these values incorrectly may destroy your ADC!
//
//                                ADS1015 ADS1115
//                                -----
// ads.setGain(GAIN_TWOTHIRDS); // 2/3x gain +/- 6.144V 1 bit = 3mV    0.1875mV
// (default)
ads.setGain(GAIN_ONE);          // 1x gain  +/- 4.096V 1 bit = 2mV    0.125mV
// ads.setGain(GAIN_TWO);        // 2x gain  +/- 2.048V 1 bit = 1mV    0.0625mV
// ads.setGain(GAIN_FOUR);       // 4x gain  +/- 1.024V 1 bit = 0.5mV   0.03125mV
// ads.setGain(GAIN_EIGHT);     // 8x gain  +/- 0.512V 1 bit = 0.25mV  0.015625mV
// ads.setGain(GAIN_SIXTEEN);   // 16x gain +/- 0.256V 1 bit = 0.125mV 0.0078125mV

if (!ads.begin()) {
  Serial.println("Failed to initialize ADS.");
  while (1);
}

void loop(void)
{
////////////////////////////////////////////////////////////////////
// LCD code
// Do nothing here...

//////////////////////////////////////////////////////////////////
//Temperature sensor DS18B20 code

// call sensors.requestTemperatures() to issue a global temperature
// request to all devices on the bus
//Serial.print("Requesting temperatures...");
sensors.requestTemperatures(); // Send the command to get temperatures
Serial.println("DONE");
// After we got the temperatures, we can print them here.
// We use the function ByIndex, and as an example get the temperature from the first sensor
only.
float tempC = sensors.getTempCByIndex(0);

// Check if reading was successful
if(tempC != DEVICE_DISCONNECTED_C)
{
  //Serial.print("Temperature for the device 1 (index 0) is: ");
  Serial.println(tempC);
}
}

```



```

        lcd.begin();
        lcd.backlight();
    Serial.begin(9600);
    sensors.begin();
    ///////////////////////////////////////////////////////////////////

// Differential ADS1115 code
//Serial.begin(9600);
//Serial.println("Hello!");

//Serial.println("Getting differential reading from AIN0 (P) and AIN1 (N)");
//Serial.println("ADC Range: +/- 6.144V (1 bit = 3mV/ADS1015, 0.1875mV/ADS1115)");

// The ADC input range (or gain) can be changed via the following
// functions, but be careful never to exceed VDD +0.3V max, or to
// exceed the upper and lower limits if you adjust the input range!
// Setting these values incorrectly may destroy your ADC!
//
//                ADS1015 ADS1115
//                -----
// ads.setGain(GAIN_TWOTHIRDS); // 2/3x gain +/- 6.144V  1 bit = 3mV    0.1875mV
// (default)
ads.setGain(GAIN_ONE);        // 1x gain  +/- 4.096V  1 bit = 2mV    0.125mV
//ads.setGain(GAIN_TWO);      // 2x gain  +/- 2.048V  1 bit = 1mV    0.0625mV
// ads.setGain(GAIN_FOUR);     // 4x gain  +/- 1.024V  1 bit = 0.5mV   0.03125mV
// ads.setGain(GAIN_EIGHT);    // 8x gain  +/- 0.512V  1 bit = 0.25mV  0.015625mV
// ads.setGain(GAIN_SIXTEEN);  // 16x gain +/- 0.256V  1 bit = 0.125mV 0.0078125mV

if (!ads.begin()) {
    Serial.println("Failed to initialize ADS.");
    while (1);
}

void loop(void)
{

//Temperature sensor DS18B20 code

// call sensors.requestTemperatures() to issue a global temperature
// request to all devices on the bus
//Serial.print("Requesting temperatures...");
sensors.requestTemperatures(); // Send the command to get temperatures
//Serial.println("DONE");
// After we got the temperatures, we can print them here.
// We use the function ByIndex, and as an example get the temperature from the first sensor
only.
float tempC = sensors.getTempCByIndex(0);

// Check if reading was successful
if(tempC != DEVICE_DISCONNECTED_C)

```

